

SOCIETY 5.0
Conference

Society 5.0

2025

Proceedings of the
5th International Conference

Society 5.0

Co-Existence Between Human Being

and Machine Being

Volume 2

San Benedetto del Tronto, 25-27 June 2025

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15422355

Preface

It is with great pleasure that we write this foreword to the Proceedings of the 5th International Conference on Society 5.0 held from 25 to 27 June 2025 in San Benedetto del Tronto, Italy. The Society 5.0 Conference 2025 was hosted by the University of Camerino, Italy. This multi- and interdisciplinary conference is continuing to grow into a premier international conference series with steering committee member from FHNW University of Applied Sciences and Arts Northwestern Switzerland, the University of Pretoria (South Africa), the University of Camerino (Italy), the Universidad EAFIT (Colombia), the Technical University of Mauritius, the Business School of the Shenzhen Technology University (China), the Universiti Malaysia Kelantan (Malaysia), and Putra Business School (Malaysia).

The theme of the 2025 Conference of Society 5.0 is “*Co-Existence Between Human Being and Machine Being*”. In a rapidly evolving digital society, the growing interaction between humans and machines is redefining the boundaries of any aspects and stages of our life cycle. This emerging “collaboration” has the potential to drive forward social good, foster a more equitable, sustainable and responsible future, while properly addressing (complex) global challenges. However, this significant and pervasive interaction also requires a careful engagement with the ethical and social issues that arise alongside these innovations.

The conference provides an important and timely opportunity to contribute to the vision of Society 5.0—a human-centered society that increasingly relies on a “fair pact” between human being and machine being with the aim of shaping a future where everyone benefits, while ensuring justice, inclusivity, and sustainability for the generations to come.

For the 2025 Society 5.0 conference we encouraged contributions from experienced and young researchers and practitioners from industry. We sincerely thank all organizers, partners, authors, and reviewers without whom this conference would not have been realised.

Technical Information

We received 64 research papers which were sent out for review to our Society 5.0 program committee. 24 full research papers were selected for the proceedings of the Society 5.0 Conference 2025 which are published as Volume 1 in the Springer CCIS series (which translates to an acceptance rate of 38%) after a rigorous, single-blind review process. Further 15 submissions were invited for presentation at the conference. Eleven of these papers are published in this second volume of the proceedings.

The program committee comprised 44 members from 15 different countries across the world. Each paper was reviewed by three members of the program committee in a

rigorous review process. The review was organized using EasyChair, avoiding potential conflicts of interest when assigning the reviewers. Criteria such as the following were taken into consideration: Relevance to Society 5.0, Significance, Technical Quality, Scholarship, and Presentation that included quality and clarity of writing.

Thank you to all the authors and program committee members, and congratulations to the authors whose research was accepted for publication in these proceedings.

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Animarobot: Animatronic for empathic communication in pediatric applications

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Abstract. The Animarobot project, developed by Intelligenza Aumentata S.r.l., introduces an innovative animatronic robot designed for empathetic communication in pediatric healthcare and other social applications. Rooted in the Society 5.0 framework, it combines advanced robotics with human-centric AI to enhance emotional engagement through adaptive facial expressions, gestures, and tone. The system achieved a key milestone with a patented interactive robotic information system (Patent No. 102021000014480, granted September 2023), enabling context-aware empathic interactions

Keywords: Pediatric healthcare, Animatronic robot, Artificial intelligence.

1 Introduction

The Animarobot project, developed by Intelligenza Aumentata S.r.l., represents a groundbreaking advancement in empathetic human-robot interaction, combining animatronic robotics with AI to address pediatric healthcare and broader social applications [5]. Rooted in the Society 5.0 framework, this patented system (No. 102021000014480, granted September 2023) integrates a Raspberry Pi computing unit, servo-motor actuators, and multimodal sensors with cloud-based AI processing to enable context-aware emotional responses through adaptive facial expressions, gestures, and vocal tone. The hardware architecture employs 3D-printed modular components using PA12 material via Multi Jet Fusion technology, while the software stack utilizes deep learning models for real-time emotion recognition and behavioral adaptation. Initially prototyped as "Johnny" for dental clinic interactions, the system has evolved into a versatile platform deployed across healthcare, education, and customer service sectors, reducing pediatric anxiety through interactive storytelling and social engagement. Its subscription-based business model offers customizable voice and personality features, supported by energy-efficient design and AWS cloud infrastructure to balance performance with environmental sustainability. By bridging mechanical engineering, cognitive science, and AI, Animarobot presents itself as a new paradigm of emotionally intelligent companionship, demonstrating the potential for technology-enhanced empathy in critical social environments.

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15700840

In Proceedings: Corradini, F.; Hinkelmann, K.; Re, B., Smuts, H., eds. (2025). Proceedings of the 5th Conference Society 5.0 - Co-Existence Between Human Being and Machine Being, Vol. 2.

San Benedetto del Tronto, Italy, 25-27 June 2025.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15422355>

Fig. 1. Jonny, the first prototype developed by Intelligenza Aumentata S.r.l. [1]

The animatronic in Fig.1 was also presented on an episode of “Lineaverde Life” on RAI 3, a famous tv show dedicated to environmental and innovation in Italy [4].

2 Technical Architecture

In this section the hardware architecture and the software stack that was developed for the animarobot application. In section 2.1 the general architecture focusing on the electronic and mechanical components will be discussed, then, in section 2.2, it will be discussed the general software structure.

2.1 Hardware Implementation

Hardware components are an essential part of the animarobot project. All the elements used in the project are commercially available and don’t need any cus-tomization. The only elements that were projected and custom manufactured were the elements of the skeleton and the external outfit like the furr and the clothes. Focusing firstly on the electronic components there are:

- Raspberry Pi 4B computing unit with PCA9685 servo controller for managing 16 PWM channels
- Modular 3D-printed skeleton (PA12 material via Multi Jet Fusion) with servo-driven facial kinematics (eyes, eyebrows, mouth) and neck articulation
- Industrial-grade power supply
- Multimodal sensors: microphone, webcam, touchscreen

All these elements can be seen in the scheme in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Hardware scheme for Animarobot application [2]

The Raspberry Pi is used as a computing unit for animatronic movement and to communicate with the cloud server. It does not elaborate with artificial intelligence. The skeleton is moved through 9 servomotors that move the robot using kinematics link such as: eye tilt/pan, eyebrow articulation, mouth movements and neck horizontal and vertical movement. In Fig 3. it can be seen as the head of animatronic without external furr. The power supply makes sure that every component has the correct electrical power supply in terms of voltage and current.

The microphone and the webcam capture audio-video information during conversation with users, this information is later sent to a cloud server where it's elaborated

Fig. 3. Animatronic skeleton

The Animarobot system has evolved significantly from its initial prototype (Fig. 1.), for example:

- To obtain the best synchronization of the lips a special microcontroller was used, this microcontroller moves robot's mouth based on the amplitude and frequency of the spectrogram of the audio track.
- To provide the best durability even with long usages the servomotors providing neck movement, and the mouth movement were upscaled from the previous version improving torque (25 kgf) and choosing aluminum gears.
- It was developed a new skull to protect the internal components from impacts
- All the electrical components are stored in a dedicated box that is manufactured with specific measurements and holes to mount all the components. This box can be seen in Fig.4.

Fig. 4. Box and cover where all the elements are stored

2.2 Software Stack

The Animarobot project employs client-server software architecture to offload the compute load from edge devices. This architecture is formed from various elements such as:

- Cloud Services: Hosts NLP pipelines (intent classification) and emotion recognition CNNs (anger, joy, surprise, sadness, fear and disgust).
- Edge Processing: Raspberry Pi 4B runs lightweight inference engines for real-time servo control and basic face tracking
- Database: Stores information extracted during human-robot interaction

These various elements are interconnected as can be seen on Fig. 5.

Fig. 5. Data flow scheme for Animarobot application

As said in the second paragraph, this architecture grants a more flexible approach to obtain data and manage more animatronic robots. In this way the information that is obtained through Computer Vision and Natural Language Processing is available everywhere and can be obtained from those who manage these robots.

The information regarding the movement of the animatronic and the script of the conversation are stored in the database in JSON files. It is then established a connection through a WebSocket, and the dataflow starts. When the user starts the conversation, these files are taken and the microphone and the camera start recording. This audio/video flow is sent to the cloud server to extract information. The cloud analyzes this data and defines the intent of the conversation and extracts specific entities from the audio track. The intents define how the conversation will evolve based on the script, the entities, instead, are the critical information that must be saved. To define the intents and entities the NLP model is trained with RASA [6] to detect these attributes. The current text-to-speech model TTS model is based on the paper produced in collaboration with UNICAM [3].

3 Pediatric Applications and other use cases

The Animarobot system was first implemented as a tool to reduce children's stress caused by an unfriendly environment such as hospitals and dentist's waiting rooms. In

fact, the first application developed was a reception/entertainer for a dentist's waiting room. This application was thoroughly tested with various children of different ages and sex. To obtain an even more detailed result a study was conducted to evaluate Human Robot Interaction [2]. This study was focused on evaluating gratification of various children talking with the animarobot system. The study was conducted on 8 participants (6 females and 2 males) with various ages. The different age group of the study can be seen in Fig.6.

Fig. 6. Age group of the users for HRI valuation

The various testers approached a conversation with the robot in a controlled environment, the conversation was based on various topics that the user showed interest in in a previous interview, at the end of the interaction the animatronic told a story based on its current academic curriculum. The results of this study showed how the animarobot application was able to gratify each tester of the study and even be an educational tool, in fact 75% of the subjects were able to receive educational information from the conversation, proving that animarobot is a functional tool even for education. In Fig. 7. It can be seen a young user that talks with the animatronic system. All these studies were conducted in a controlled environment and given the young age of the testers all their parents signed a release form for this study.

Fig. 7. Example of the study conducted to evaluate HRI

This study was conducted as proof of concept for a more advanced application. The next application developed by Intelligenza Aumentata S.r.l. was an app to analyze the medical history of young patients. This app consists of a series of questions that the robot asks the user to obtain as much information as possible. This information is:

- Anagrafic data: Name, date of birth and height
- General data: practiced sport, ...
- Medical data: allergies, general pains and prescribed medicines
- Illnesses: asthma, type of diabetes, ...
- Past records: past medical procedures and familial genetic pathologies

All this data is organized in a database to be used by the medical staff or the doctor to have a preventive medical record of the patient. This idea allows the doctor to significantly reduce the doctor's time as well as reduce the stress of the patient who finds himself in an unfamiliar environment, the shape of the puppet is designed specifically to reassure the patient. This app was presented as a demo for the first time at "Ospedale Pediatrico Bambino Gesù" of Rome, the largest Polyclinic and Pediatric Research Center in Europe. Connected to the major international centers in the sector, it is a point of reference for the health of children and young people from all over Italy and abroad [6]. After this another kind of application was tested. The app for the evaluation of dementia progression in elderly patients was developed in collaboration

with UNICAM [3]. This app used a new Speech-to-text algorithm specific for the Italian language. In this application it was recreated a the MMSE (Mini-mental state examination) using the animarobot system [7]. The robot conducts a series of diagnostic queries directed at the user, with the responses subsequently evaluated by medical personnel.

The animatronic system is also suitable for applications other than the pediatric sector. Other developed applications include automated cinema ticketing systems and hotel reception interfaces. In Fig. 8. there are a few screenshots regarding the application.

Fig. 8. Screenshot of the developed application of anamnesis

4 Conclusion and Future Works

The Animarobot project currently includes a total of ten fully functional animatronic puppets, marking a significant milestone in the advancement of interactive robotic technologies. The project is presently undergoing an industrialization phase, aimed at optimizing production processes, standardizing components, and ensuring scalability for broader deployment. In parallel, continuous efforts are being made to enhance computer vision and natural language processing algorithms. Furthermore, a robust server-side interface is under development to support the seamless creation and integration of new skills, contributing to the overall flexibility and long-term sustainability of the system. In Fig.9 there are all the animatronics that were developed, each of them is designed to be used in specific areas linked to children, such as schools, hospitals, malls, zoos and hotels.

Fig. 9. The animatronics currently developed by Intelligenza Aumentata S.r.l.

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AI in Healthcare for Pets – The Co-Caring Approach of AI-Tails

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Abstract

AI and IoT technologies are revolutionizing pet healthcare, enabling proactive health management and early disease detection. This paper introduces AI-Tails, a Swiss startup company that leverages AI to address the challenge of the early detection of feline diseases. AI-Tails uses behavioral and physiological data collected by the IoT-enabled smart cat home to provide real-time insights for pet owners and veterinarians. This co-caring approach enables continuous tracking of pet health indicators, improving care efficiency and accessibility. A business model canvas highlights key partners, value propositions, and customer segments of tech-savvy pet owners, veterinary clinics, and pet insurance companies. The paper also examines the market readiness for AI-driven pet health solutions, particularly in Switzerland and China. Initial validation through collaborations with the University Hospital in Bern strengthens the credibility of AI-Tails' solution. The AI-Tails Home system architecture, user interface, and data visualization methods are described, demonstrating the potential to improve pet well-being, fostering new business models and partnerships, and improving pet health care within the framework of Society 5.0

Keywords: AI, pet healthcare, feline health monitoring, digitalization in pet care, startup, co-caring

1. Introduction

AI-Tails, a startup founded by Angelica De Riggi (www.aitails.com) and inspired by the loss of her cat, Spooky, addresses a common challenge faced by pet owners: pets, especially cats, are often stoic creatures, masking pain and potential illness behind subtle behaviors that are often imperceptible to the human eye. As technology advanced into the era of Society 5.0, a human-centered integration of AI and the Internet of Things (IoT) emerged, revealing new possibilities for improving the well-being of our animal companions. The company focuses on the early detection of feline diseases using AI technology.

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15703685

In Proceedings: Corradini, F.; Hinkelmann, K.; Re, B., Smuts, H., eds. (2025). Proceedings of the 5th Conference Society 5.0 - Co-Existence Between Human Being and Machine Being, Vol. 2.

San Benedetto del Tronto, Italy, 25-27 June 2025.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15422355>

The startup has received recognition for its innovative approach. De Riggi, an alumna of the University of Applied Sciences and Arts Northwestern Switzerland (FHNW), has been featured in FHNW's news for her work with AI-Tails.

Automated pain recognition for cats using artificial intelligence (AI) represents a groundbreaking advancement in veterinary medicine. It addresses the inherent challenges of assessing pain in these animals, which often mask their discomfort. Traditional pain assessment methods rely heavily on subjective observations from pet owners and veterinarians, leading to inconsistencies and potential misdiagnoses. The integration of AI technologies into this process offers a more objective and accurate means of evaluating pain, utilizing advanced algorithms to analyze facial expressions, postural indicators, and behavioral cues in felines. Research has demonstrated that AI systems can effectively analyze specific facial features, such as ear position, eye dilation, and whisker orientation, to gauge pain levels in cats. Notable studies have reported pain recognition accuracy rates exceeding 77% when using manually annotated facial landmarks (Martvel, G. et al. 2024).

Behavioral indicators: While it remains challenging to diagnose disease from behavior alone, several known illnesses in cats are associated with recognizable behaviors (Camps et al., 2019; Horwitz & Rodan, 2018, Mills et al., 2020, Ezanno et al., 2023): Chronic health problems such as arthritis, dental disease and gastrointestinal problems can result in aggressive behavior in cats. Feline idiopathic cystitis, which can cause urinary tract disease, and osteoarthritis pain can result in urination outside the litter box. Feline orofacial pain syndrome is a neurological pathology that causes severe oral pain in cats and results in distinct behavior such as repetitive pawing of the mouth and mutilating the mouth and tongue. In cats with bladder pain, licking the lower (caudal) part of the abdomen can be seen. Finally, changes in eating or drinking habits (e.g., increased drinking of water is seen due to diabetes and kidney disease in cats), as well as increased grooming (cats tend to overgroom painful areas), are key behavior indicators for disease.

However, addressing such a complex challenge requires a deep understanding of both market needs and the technological landscape. AI-Tails is not just about technology; it is also about fostering trust among pet owners by demonstrating the value of early detection, reducing stress for both pets and their human companions.

Thus, in this paper, we will begin with an overview of the market for pet health technologies, focusing on the increasing demand for innovative and scalable solutions. Instead of a traditional literature review, we will examine the current trends and opportunities in the pet care market, setting the context for AI-Tails' value proposition.

2. AI in Petcare

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is increasingly transforming pet healthcare by enabling early detection of diseases and enhancing overall health management. Innovations such as AI-powered health scan applications analyze images of pets' eyes and skin to identify potential health issues, allowing for timely interventions. For instance, TTcare utilizes AI technology to detect early signs of diseases in pets through a simple smartphone app, boasting over 1.4 million scans performed with a 95% accuracy rate (AI For Pet - Making Pet Care Accessible For All, o. D.).

Moreover, AI is being integrated into veterinary practices to improve diagnostic accuracy and

efficiency (Akinsulie et al., 2024). Tools like AI chatbots provide pet owners with extensive information on animal health, research studies, and diagnostic options, offering a cost-effective and convenient alternative to traditional veterinary consultations (pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov).

A business model canvas for AI-services in the predictive animal healthcare domain is shown in Fig. 1, highlighting key partners and value propositions for different customers. For AI-Tails key partners include FHNW, ETH and SZTU with the main customer segment being tech-savvy pet owners.

Key Partners	Key Activities	Value Propositions	Customer Relationships	Customer Segments
Veterinary clinics: For real-world testing and referrals Tech providers: Cloud services and AI framework developer Pet Insurance Companies: Bundling AI tools with insurance plans Pet Food Companies: provide food delivery services	AI model development: Continuous training using new data R&D: continuous improvement of predictive health services Data collection & integration: Partnering with clinics to aggregate health records User education: Demos and tutorials to ease adoption of AI tools	Predictive diagnostics: AI analyzes historical health data Personalized care plans: Tailored recommendations for diet, exercise, and treatments based on breed, age, and medical history 24/7 telehealth access: Real-time AI-driven advice for emergencies, reducing unnecessary clinic visits	Personalized interactions: AI-driven follow-ups post-treatment and reminders for vaccinations Loyalty programs: Discounts on subscriptions for users who share pet health data Community engagement: Workshops on AI tools and pet wellness	Tech-savvy pet owners: Prioritize convenience and proactive health monitoring Veterinary clinics: Seeking AI tools to enhance diagnostic accuracy and reduce workload Pet insurance companies: Use predictive data to tailor insurance plans and reduce claims
	Key Resources AI algorithms & datasets: Trained on millions of pet health records for accuracy Veterinary experts: Collaborate to validate AI recommendations and build trust Cloud infrastructure: Secure storage and processing of sensitive health data Regulatory compliance: Certifications for AI tools in veterinary medicine		Channels Online platforms and mobile apps: AI symptom checker Telehealth platforms: Video consultations integrated with AI diagnostics Social media & pet communities: Educational content on preventive care and AI benefits	
Cost Structure R&D expenses: AI model training and validation Marketing: Digital campaigns targeting pet owners and clinics Data security: Encryption and compliance with privacy laws Partnership management: Maintaining collaborations with clinics and insurers		Revenue Streams Subscription models: Tiered plans for basic monitoring vs. advanced predictive analytics Pay-per-use diagnostics: Fees for AI analysis of lab tests or X-ray Partnership revenue: Licensing AI tools to clinics or insurance firms Data monetization: Anonymized data sold to pharmaceutical companies for R&D		

Fig. 1 – Business Model Canvas for AI-services in predictive animal healthcare domain.

The two elements from the BMC (Business Model Canvas), namely "customer segments" and "value propositions" provides a convenient and accessible way to examine whether the value propositions of a company's business model correlate with the actual needs of the customers it seeks to serve (Nielsen & Kyhnau, 2015).

In consideration of AI-Tails, the Value Proposition Canvas presents as follows:

Table 1 – Value Proposition AI-Tails.

Customer Jobs	Customer Pains	Customer Gains
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Functional: 24/7 Anomaly detection • Social: being tech-savvy using the latest technology • Emotional: reducing potential concerns, conveying a feeling of “safety” 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Undesired results: stressful veterinary visits and costs • Obstacles: affordability • Risks: uncertainty regarding data protection 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Needed: AI-based detection of distress or disease at early-stage and prevention of deteriorating conditions • Expected and desired: sophisticated design and compatibility with the smart home ecosystem • Unexpected: customizable design
Product and Services	Pain Reliever	Gains Creators
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Continuous monitoring of the pet's health indicators • Immediate notification of anomaly detections • Efficient product and business model design 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Longterm cost savings • Affordable subscription model • Data security as top priority 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 24/7 AI-supported pet monitoring • Focus on prevention • Insight into individual pet feelings

By continuously monitoring a pet’s health indicators, the system helps owners feel more connected and reassured about their pet’s well-being. Its customizable design and smart home compatibility enhance user experience, making it both a functional and aesthetically appealing solution. Ultimately, this personalized approach not only fosters a stronger bond between pets and owners but also minimizes health risks through early detection and intervention.

3. Market readiness for AI-Tails

The growing trend of pet humanization—where pets are increasingly seen as family members—has led to a rise in demand for advanced pet healthcare solutions, particularly in regions with aging populations and higher disposable incomes. Reports have also shown that loneliness during the COVID-19 pandemic resulted in an increase in the number of pet owners and a boom in the global pet care market. For example, this increase can be observed by the 180 percent rise in the share price of the online pet product retailer Chewy (CHWY, Yahoo Finance). These data points suggest that the pet care market is poised for growth and demonstrates resilience to economic downturns and COVID-19-related impacts. The rapid expansion of the pet care market is also being driven by advancements in digitalization. A study by Mordor Intelligence (2024) highlights the rising interest in pet health and wellness, with consumers seeking innovative solutions such as wearable health monitors, telemedicine platforms, and AI-powered diagnostic tools. Additionally, sustainability concerns are shaping purchasing behaviors, with a growing preference for eco-friendly pet food, biodegradable accessories, and ethically sourced

products. As AI and IoT continue to integrate into the pet care sector, the market is expected to see further expansion, positioning technology-driven pet health solutions as a key factor in shaping future industry trends.

Beachhead Market: According to the pet food association VHN, around 1.85 million cats lived as pets in Switzerland in 2023. Almost three out of ten Swiss households are home to a house cat, making cats the most popular pets among the Swiss. The market for pet-related products in Switzerland is flourishing. Swiss consumers spend around 600 million euros a year on their companion animals (Statista, n.d.), placing Switzerland in 10th place in a comparison of European countries. In Germany, the market for pet supplies is eight times as large as in Switzerland.

China: China presents a compelling opportunity for AI-Tails in both production and market expansion. As the world's leading manufacturing hub, China offers a highly developed supply chain ecosystem, cost-efficient production facilities, and access to cutting-edge technology, all of which are crucial for ensuring scalable and cost-effective manufacturing. Establishing production in China would enable AI-Tails to optimize its cost structure while maintaining high standards of quality and innovation. Additionally, the Chinese government's strong support for AI and biotechnology research, coupled with its investment in advanced manufacturing, provides an environment conducive to the development and refinement of AI-driven pet healthcare solutions.

Beyond its advantages as a production hub, China represents one of the most rapidly expanding pet care markets globally. With a booming pet industry and a growing middle class, pet ownership has increased significantly, particularly among urban millennials who view their pets as family members and prioritize their well-being. In 2023, the Chinese pet market was valued at over 66 billion USD, with projections indicating continued growth driven by rising disposable incomes, increased awareness of pet health, and a shift towards premium pet products and services. By entering the Chinese market, AI-Tails would gain access to a vast and increasingly affluent consumer base, creating opportunities for both direct-to-consumer sales and strategic partnerships with local distributors and veterinary networks.

Furthermore, China's position as a global leader in e-commerce and digital innovation presents unique advantages for AI-Tails' market entry and expansion. With platforms such as Tmall, JD.com, and Xiaohongshu (Little Red Book) playing a dominant role in consumer purchasing behavior, AI-Tails can leverage China's highly developed online retail infrastructure to efficiently market and distribute its products. This digital-first approach, combined with a localized marketing strategy, would allow AI-Tails to rapidly scale its presence in the region and establish itself as a key player in the premium pet healthcare segment.

4. AI-Tails Smart Home

Co-Caring Product Approach: As discussed by Aulet (2013), identifying the core of a product or service is crucial for differentiation and long-term success. AI-Tails' competitive advantage lies in its personalized customer service, a feature that is not easily replicable by competitors. AI-Tails leverages advanced AI to deliver highly tailored experiences, ensuring that each pet owner receives individualized support. This personalized approach enhances customer satisfaction, fostering long-term retention and significantly reducing churn rates. Additionally, satisfied customers become brand advocates, driving organic growth through positive word-of-mouth. Recognizing that pet owners prioritize the well-being of their beloved animals, AI-Tails aims to be more than just a service provider—it strives to be a trusted companion throughout the entire pet care journey. This co-caring philosophy strengthens the bond

between the brand and its customers, creating a community built on trust and empathy.

4.1 Validation and Credibility of the Product

A critical factor in establishing the credibility of AI-Tails' technology is its collaboration with University Hospitals. Partnerships with esteemed academic and medical institutions not only reinforce the scientific rigor behind the product but also enhance its trustworthiness in the market. By working closely with leading experts in veterinary medicine and artificial intelligence, AI-Tails ensures that its diagnostic tools and predictive models undergo rigorous testing and validation in real-world clinical settings. These collaborations strengthen the legitimacy of AI-driven pet healthcare solutions. This makes them more compelling for both investors and end-users.

4.2 Architectural Overview

Figure 3 presents a comprehensive overview of the AI-Tails Home technological framework, which serves as the foundation of the AI-driven pet healthcare system. This architecture seamlessly integrates data acquisition, cloud-based machine learning models, and a user-friendly mobile application to optimize pet health monitoring.

At the core of this system are smart food and drinking stations equipped with IoT sensors, including weight sensors, temperature monitors, and motion detectors. These sensors continuously collect real-time pet health data, which is then processed by AI algorithms. Key components of the analytical framework include computer vision for facial recognition and time-series analysis for behavioral pattern detection. The processed insights are displayed in real time for both pet owners and veterinarians, enabling proactive and informed healthcare management.

A structured data flow ensures that raw sensor inputs are securely transmitted to the cloud, where machine learning models analyze the information before delivering actionable feedback to the mobile application. Furthermore, the modular architecture supports scalability, allowing for seamless updates and integration with future diagnostic technologies, ensuring AI-Tails remains at the forefront of AI-driven pet healthcare innovation.

Fig. 3 AI-Tails Home: Data Architecture

The class diagram in Figure 4 represents the architecture of the pet health monitoring system using the *Ruby on Rails* framework specifically using *ActiveRecord* for database management, *ActiveJob* for background processing, and *ActionController* for handling web requests. It includes abstract classes such as *ApplicationRecord*, *ApplicationJob*, and *ApplicationController*, which provide base functionalities for models, background job processing, and request handling, respectively. The *Cat* class stores information about individual pets and maintains a one-to-many relationship with the *HealthRecord* class, which logs health-related data. The diagram illustrates how different components interact to facilitate continuous pet health tracking and anomaly detection.

Fig. 4 AI-Tails Home: Class Diagram schematics.

4.3 User Interface and Data Visualization

To maximize usability, AI-Tails offers an intuitive dashboard and mobile application that visually presents health trends, alerts, and treatment recommendations. A potential screenshot of the app or dashboard shown in Figure 4 highlights how pet owners and veterinarians interact with real-time health data. The interface simplifies complex diagnostic information into easily interpretable insights, ensuring accessibility for both professionals and general users. By providing clear, actionable data, AI-Tails empowers pet owners to take a proactive approach to their pet’s well-being, reinforcing the impact and credibility of the technology.

The mobile app displays key health indicators, such as the eating and drinking habits as well as the pain level of the cat in an easy-to-understand format. For example, a sudden high amount in drinking water is flagged with a red alert, prompting the pet owner to consult with their veterinarian as it may indicate kidney disease. The app also provides personalized recommendations based on the cat’s individual health profile, such as adjusting food portions or increasing playtime. A key feature is the ability to share data directly with the veterinarian, facilitating remote monitoring and consultation.

Fig. 5 Screenshot of an excerpt of the mobile app interface.

4.4 AI Algorithms and Implementation in AI-Tails

To process diverse data streams, we employ a combination of Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) for image-based health assessments, Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks for time-series behavioral analysis, and gradient-boosted decision trees for predictive diagnostics. The CNN models analyze pet images for physical condition monitoring, while LSTM networks track fluctuations in activity levels, eating habits, and other behavioral patterns over time.

Feature Engineering and Data Preprocessing: Before feeding data into our AI models, we implement a robust feature engineering pipeline. Raw sensor data—such as movement patterns and food intake—is first cleaned and normalized to remove outliers. We then extract key behavioral indicators, such as sleep duration, gait irregularities, and feeding speed, which serve as inputs for anomaly detection algorithms. Additionally, feature selection techniques help optimize model performance by prioritizing the most relevant health markers.

5. Implementation and Real-World Application of AI-Tails

AI-Tails leverages cutting-edge AI technology to bridge the gap between pet owners and their pets, ensuring early detection and proactive management of animal health issues. Our system integrates non-invasive devices with real-time monitoring, providing actionable insights through an AI-powered analytics platform. During the current development phase, we are conducting a multi-stage deployment: an initial proof-of-concept (PoC) trial in controlled environments, followed by pilot studies in real-world settings with pet owners. These pilot studies will be focusing on usability testing, data accuracy, and AI-driven anomaly detection in behavioral and physiological patterns. By iterating based on user

feedback, we make sure to improve the system's sensitivity to early disease indicators, enhancing its practical utility.

5.1 Evaluation and Practical Lessons Learned

One of the most valuable lessons we learned was the importance of user-friendly design. Early prototypes contained too much raw data, making them overwhelming. To address this, we adopted a design-thinking approach, prioritizing clear, actionable insights over complex metrics. This not only improved usability but also built trust in AI-driven recommendations. By refining our interface based on real-world feedback, we significantly increased adoption rates and ensured that using AI-Tails feels intuitive and self-explanatory for our customers.

By transforming AI-driven insights into practical applications, AI-Tails embodies Society 5.0's vision of leveraging technology to enhance quality of life. Our iterative development process—rooted in real-world testing and continuous refinement—ensures that AI-Tails is more than just an innovation; it is a truly impactful solution for proactive pet health management.

6. Conclusions and Outlook

As we transition into Society 5.0, a vision that prioritizes human-centered innovation, the integration of AI into everyday life is no longer limited to human welfare alone—it extends to our companion animals. AI-Tails embodies this transformation by utilizing cutting-edge artificial intelligence to enhance feline healthcare, ensuring pets receive the same level of technological advancement as other aspects of modern living. By leveraging AI-powered behavioral analysis and IoT-enabled monitoring, AI-Tails aligns with the Society 5.0 ethos, where technology and compassion merge to create a more harmonious coexistence between humans and their pets.

The integration of AI-driven solutions in pet healthcare has far-reaching implications that extend beyond individual pet owners to the broader veterinary and research communities. AI-Tails facilitates a shift from reactive to proactive pet healthcare, enabling early disease detection and personalized treatment recommendations. This advancement enhances clinical efficiency, reduces emergency interventions, and optimizes veterinary resource allocation.

From a stakeholder perspective, veterinarians benefit from real-time, data-driven insights that improve diagnostic accuracy and streamline decision-making. Pet owners gain access to continuous health monitoring tools, empowering them to take preventive actions and reducing overall healthcare costs. Additionally, insurance providers can leverage AI-driven risk assessments to develop more tailored pet insurance plans, promoting cost-effective coverage options.

Beyond individual care, AI-Tails contributes to a larger ecosystem of predictive and preventive veterinary medicine. Aggregated data from AI monitoring systems supports veterinary research by identifying emerging health trends, improving disease surveillance, and informing public health initiatives. This data-driven approach enhances the collective understanding of pet health at a population level, fostering innovation in treatment strategies and veterinary best practices.

Furthermore, this technological shift aligns with the principles of Society 5.0, promoting a more connected, informed, and responsible pet owner community. As AI-driven pet healthcare becomes more prevalent, it has the potential to transform industry standards, reinforcing the importance of preventive care and ensuring better health outcomes for companion animals worldwide.

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Decision Support for Digital Payment Facilitation

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Abstract. This research investigates digital payment facilitation in marketplace platforms (platform businesses) within the European Union (EU)'s regulatory framework, focusing on compliance and operational strategies when handling e-money. Platforms like Amazon, Uber and PayPal play a pivotal role in the digital economy but face challenges in managing payments under stringent regulations. The research addresses the decision-making gap for digital platforms considering in-house payment facilitation and selecting suitable financial licenses. An application-oriented artefact was designed and developed - a decision framework for marketplace platforms to guide decision makers in aligning with regulatory and operational demands. Evaluated through expert interviews, the framework proves its relevance and adaptability to evolving regulatory requirements. It serves as a practical tool that supports strategic decision-making and enhances competitiveness in the field of digital finance. Additionally, it features an AI based exploratory component for further research.

Keywords: Digital Payments, Marketplace Platforms, Regulatory Compliance.

1 Introduction

Platform businesses are digital ecosystems/digital marketplaces that ease interactions between different user groups, typically consumers and producers, by providing a technological infrastructure for value exchange (Parker et al., 2016; Oteng Agyeman et al, 2021). Unlike traditional linear businesses, digital platform models use network effects, meaning their value increases as more users join (Evans & Schmalensee, 2016). Examples include e-commerce businesses like Amazon, ridesharing like Uber, food services like Just Eat, and financial technology platforms such as PayPal. These businesses rely on data, algorithms, and user engagement to optimise transactions and create competitive advantages. Their success depends on digital trust, scalability, and efficient governance mechanisms to balance interests among stakeholders (Täuscher, et al., 2017; Täuscher & Laudien, 2018). So-called payment facilitators handle agreements and payment settlements for sub-merchants, making them essential intermediaries in digital commerce (The European Business Review, 2021).

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15703735

In Proceedings: Corradini, F.; Hinkelmann, K.; Re, B., Smuts, H., eds. (2025). Proceedings of the 5th Conference Society 5.0- Co-Existence Between Human Being and Machine Being, Vol. 2. San Benedetto del Tronto, Italy, 25-27 June 2025.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15422355>

As a highly regulated domain digital payment facilitation requires compliance with regulations like the Payment Services Directive (PSD), the E-Money Directive, and Anti-Money Laundering (AML) (European Commission, n.d.a.). These regulatory demands often force digital marketplaces to outsource their payment facilitation service to specialised providers like Adyen or Stripe, avoiding the operational complexities of managing these processes in-house (European Commission, 2017).

This research presents a decision-making framework designed to support digital marketplace platform owners in determining whether to facilitate payments in-house or outsource this function. The framework employs a criteria-based questionnaire to capture platform-specific needs and guide licensing decisions, followed by a self-assessment to evaluate operational compliance requirements. Based on these inputs, it produces actionable insights. The framework offers practical value through structured guidance, a user-friendly Excel tool, and alignment with EU financial regulations. It addresses a significant gap in the literature by providing a systematic approach and clearly defined criteria for navigating the complex challenges of payment facilitation, including regulatory compliance, technological integration, financial investment, and operational security.

1.1 Research Methodology

Design Science Research (DSR) was chosen as the methodological foundation for this research due to its focus on creating practical, solution-oriented artefacts that address real-world problems. In this context, DSR aids in the development and evaluation of a decision framework for marketplace platforms that supports strategic decision-making regarding in-house payment processing and financial license selection. The research follows Hevner et al.'s (2004) "Design Science in Information Systems Research," which employs a five-phase framework to guide the research process.

The first phase, "Problem Awareness", involves identifying the decision-making challenges that marketplace platforms face when determining whether to support payments internally and select appropriate financial licenses. This phase highlights the regulatory complexities and operational considerations. Next, during the "Suggestion Phase", a hybrid decision framework for marketplace platforms is proposed, integrating Model-Driven Decision Support System (MD-DSS) and Knowledge-Driven Decision Support System (KD-DSS) to simplify and streamline the decision-making process. In the "Development Phase", a Microsoft Excel-based artefact is created, leveraging Microsoft Excel's Visual Basic Application (VBA) functionalities to assist decision-makers with an entry-level technical know-how.

The artefact's design integrates criteria and requirements based on regulatory guidelines and business practices, facilitating the systematic assessment of licensing options such as Payment Institution (PI), Electronic Money Institution (EMI), or banking licenses. The iteratively conducted "Evaluation Phase" ensures practical applicability and adaptability. Insights gained are used to refine the framework, improving its reliability and relevance for industry professionals. In the final "Conclusion Phase," the research summarizes key findings, validates the framework's effectiveness, and offers recommendations for further development and future research.

1.2 Problem Statement

Payment services within digital marketplaces may offer advantages like streamlined transactions, and increased customer convenience. However, it also introduces risks, such as supplier dependency, misaligned processes, differing quality standards, and limited control over suppliers' progress (Dinu, 2015). For digital marketplaces, facilitating payments in-house with appropriate licenses, such as those held by Zalando Payments GmbH or similar entities, can enhance the customer experience, automate processes, and unlock additional revenue streams (Exact Payments, n.d.; European Commission 2017).

Despite the importance of payment facilitation in digital marketplaces, based on literature review (section 2) we discovered, there is a significant lack of structured criteria and decision frameworks to guide platform owners in evaluating in-house solutions versus outsourcing. This gap highlights the need for a comprehensive decision-making framework tailored to guide decision makers in navigating payment facilitation and licensing choices effectively.

1.3 Research Questions

This research focuses on determining structured requirements to design a decision framework for marketplace platforms, including relevant criteria for platform businesses in the EU, to manage payment facilitation. This leads to the following central question: What legal, regulatory, and literature-based factors influence payment facilitation for marketplace platforms in the EU? Based on the literature review, the following research questions were derived:

1. **Decision-Making in Payment Facilitation:** How can small marketplace platform providers assess the viability and strategic potential of implementing a digital payment solution?
2. **Regulatory Frameworks:** What are the key regulatory alternatives for payment facilitation in digital marketplace platforms within the EU?
3. **Evaluation Criteria:** What key factors and evaluation criteria should digital marketplace platform providers consider when choosing a payment facilitation model?
4. **Decision Support Artefact:** Can a structured decision-supporting tool help potential marketplace platform providers make informed decisions about their payment facilitation strategies?

2 Literature Review

To establish a contextual foundation, we combined methodological rigor with insights from academia and practice. The literature review focused on (1) digital marketplace platforms, (2) financial licensing in Europe, and (3) decision-support systems. Additionally, qualitative interviews with subject matter experts were conducted to enrich the findings with practical perspectives.

2.1 Marketplace Platforms

Digital marketplace platforms act as intermediaries, facilitating transactions and offering services like technology, market reach, and network effects. They help smaller enterprises expand globally, enabling competition without requiring significant investments or extensive networks (Singh et al., 2023). Digital marketplace platforms often function as both operators and sellers, requiring advanced systems to manage supply, demand, and innovation. The role of marketplace platforms is essential in retail's digital transformation (Wulfert & Schütte, 2022). Digital marketplace platforms facilitate payments, to ensure efficient, secure transactions between a diverse set of consumers and sellers, while also supporting their own revenue generation and operational needs (Checkout.com, 2023).

2.2 Finance Licensing in Europe

The European Banking Authority provides the regulatory standards and guidelines under the revised Payment Services Directive (PSD2), which introduces the E-Money Institution (EMI) and Payment Institution (PI) as additional finance licenses. The national regulators in EU member states are responsible for the implementation and enforcement of PSD2 (European Banking Authority, 2024). Figure 1 provides a simplified overview of financial licensing and the authorities that enforce the licensing in the EU and European Economic Area (EEA).

Fig 1. Finance Licensing and Respective Authorities in the EU.

Table 1 shows the characteristics of license types in the EU and EEA financial regulatory framework (Dobler et al., 2021; Sloboda, 2020; Solaris SE, 2022). All three licenses enable digital financial services across the EU and EEA, with varying degrees of operational flexibility. The application process is the most complex for a banking license and simplest for an EMI license according to Dobler et al. (2021), Sloboda (2020) and Solaris SE (2022).

2.3 Business Decision Support

Companies that plan to integrate digital financial services within their digital marketplaces may also need to consider the complex accompanying decision-making tasks relevant to making this choice, e.g., investment decisions, financial regulatory compliance establishment, technology integration, and data security.

A decision framework for marketplace platforms could be a valuable tool for comparing relevant requirements, assessing their impact, and deciding whether and which of the financial services makes sense. An effective decision-making process is crucial for the establishment, growth, and sustainability of financial services within digital marketplace platforms in today's competitive, rapidly evolving sector (Lee & Shin, 2018).

Table 1. Overview of European Payment Licenses and their Characteristics.

	Banking License	EMI License	PI License
Definition	Permission for a company to operate as a bank.	Authorisation to provide payment services and issue e-money; no traditional banking service.	License for entities executing payment transactions and services.
Services Offered	Deposit-taking, lending, payment services, investment activities.	Issuing e-money, payment services, IBAN accounts, payment cards, e-wallets.	Payment transactions (credit transfers, direct debits), money remittances, a.o.
Capital Requirements	Varies, based on the size and risk profile.	Minimum of EUR 350'000.	Minimum of EUR 125'000.
Regulatory Oversight	Subject to robust regulatory standards for financial stability and consumer protection.	Specific regulatory requirements for the safekeeping of client funds and operational stability.	Regulated to ensure secure payment services and consumer protection.
Operational Flexibility	Less flexibility due to stringent regulatory requirements.	Operational flexibility and quicker innovation due to fewer regulatory restrictions.	Focused on payment services with some operational flexibility.
Depositor Compensation Scheme	Required to contribute to a depositor protection scheme.	Not required to contribute since they cannot take risks with customer money.	Not typically required to contribute to a depositor protection scheme.
Passporting Rights	Full banking services can be offered across the EU and EEA.	Services can be offered across the EU and EEA.	Services can be offered across the EU and EEA.
Applicability	Traditional retail banks and banks with innovative business models.	Non-banks, fintech firms, subsidiaries of phone companies, payment providers.	Credit card processors, payment account operators, remittance businesses, foreign exchange businesses, a.o.
Application Process	More complex and lengthy due to comprehensive regulatory assessments.	Simpler and shorter, more accessible for startups/small companies.	Less complex than a banking license but more involved than an EMI license.

To find a basis for a decision framework for marketplace platforms, Decision Support Systems (DSS) were analysed. One of the first DSS, developed by Gorry and Scott Morton (Sprague, 1973); integrates management activities through a process involving (1) problem identification, (2) developing alternatives, and (3) selecting and implementing solutions.

According to Lunenburg (2010), decision-making is the process of choosing among alternatives to achieve a desired goal. He advocates a systematic approach that includes (1) identifying the problem, (2) generating alternatives, (3) evaluating these alternatives, (4) choosing the most suitable one, (5) implementing the decision, and (6) evaluating its effectiveness. The rational model presents decision-making as a logical, structured process and assumes that decision-makers have access to all relevant information, allowing them to identify all alternatives and predict the outcome of each alternative.

Decision-making involves choosing among alternatives to achieve an objective, such as maximisation, minimisation, or reaching a nominal value. The complexity of this process often necessitates multi-criteria and multi-attribute analyses, leading to the development of digital DSS. In digital DSS, decisions are classified as programmed or non-programmed, with programmed decisions being well-defined and routine, where standards and procedures can be established for execution by anyone (García-Alcaraz et al., 2023).

Digital DSS are interactive, computer-based applications that assist decision-makers by leveraging data to address semi-structured and unstructured identified problems; they can be adapted to changing needs without automating decisions. MD-DSS stands for Model-Driven Decision Support System. A MD-DSS allows users to manipulate model parameters through an accessible interface to conduct "what-if" analyses and evaluate different scenarios (Power et al., 2007). A Knowledge-Driven Decision Support System (KD-DSS) or Knowledge-Based DSS (KB-DSS), relies on expert knowledge to support process. Unlike Data-Driven DSS, which extracts insights from large datasets, KD-DSS focuses on applying domain-specific knowledge, often captured in knowledge bases or expert systems, to guide decisions (Chiche, 2019).

Fig 2. Conceptual Schema of Decision Support Systems (Nižetić et al., 2007).

Figure 2 illustrates a conceptual schema of MD-DSS integrated with KD-DSS into a hybrid DSS. It shows the interplay between the user (interface) which sends requests to the inference engine. In a hybrid DSS, the interface engine combines data from a knowledge base with a model base to generate results which are sent back to the user interface and interpreted by them (Nižetić et al., 2007). Based on the application areas of the respective DSS classifications, the research concentrated on leveraging KD-DSS, potentially combining with Model- MD-DSS, within a cooperative DSS approach.

3 Research Design

This research employed Design Science Research (DSR) in alignment with design-oriented research principles, which focus on creating artefacts to address specific problems and generate measurable benefits (Österle et al., 2011).

The methodological approach followed Hevner et al.'s five-phase framework: (1) problem awareness, involving comprehension of the identified problem, (2) suggestion, proposing a potential solution, (3) development, constructing a practical prototype artefact, (4) evaluation, assessing the artefact's effectiveness, and (5) conclusion, summarising results and discussing future perspectives. The development and evaluation phases were conducted iteratively, ensuring continuous refinement and validation (Hevner & Chatterjee, 2010).

3.1 Decision Framework

The developed artefact, a decision framework for marketplace platforms, assists decision-makers in determining whether and how to offer a digital payment facilitation in-house and in selecting the appropriate license model (Table 1). By combining MD-DSS and KD-DSS, the hybrid DSS simplifies licensing decisions through defined criteria and regulatory requirements. The framework uses payment facilitation criteria of a marketplace platform to evaluate license options via MD-DSS and outlines key compliance and operational integrity requirements, utilising KD-DSS to navigate regulatory aspects.

3.2 Criteria

The criteria outlined in Table 2 are designed to guide decision-makers through the process of determining whether to handle digital payments in-house. These criteria, initially drafted from the literature review and based on the services offered by each license (Table 1), also incorporate insights from (European Commission et al., 2023a, 2023b).

During the evaluation, the criteria were critically assessed for accuracy and comprehensiveness, leading to further refinement. Based on the MD-DSS framework, these criteria provide a structured approach for evaluating the factors that influence the choice of a specific license. The selection between a PI, EMI, or Banking license depends on the evaluation of these criteria, summarised in Table 1.

3.3 Requirements

Based on the evaluated required license through the companies' criteria, examining the corresponding requirements is essential for ensuring compliance, operational efficiency, and competitive advantage in the payment processing landscape. Using the relevant licensing knowledge from Table 1, the corresponding requirements are defined in Table 3. These requirements are assessed and refined during the evaluation process to incorporate KD-DSS into the artefact, helping generate knowledge-based suggestions.

Table 2. Criteria for Marketplace Platform Businesses to Facilitate Payments.

Criteria	Description
Splitting revenues	The platform is part of the finance flow between the consumer and producer segments and splits revenue among multiple producers.
Pay out full sales	The platform is part of finance flow between the consumer and producer segments and pays out full sales to producers or services in case there is a payment delay on the consumer side.
Covering financial loss	The platform is part of the finance flow between the consumer and producer segments and pays out full sales to producers in cases of fraud or insolvency on the consumer side.
Applying platform vouchers	The platform applies vouchers paid by the platform or other sponsors in consumers' baskets which contain products of multiple producers.
Stored value	The platform offers their consumers to store monetary value which can later be used to buy products or services from the producer segment within the platform.
IBAN accounts	The platform wants to offer IBAN accounts to their consumer or producer segments to and from which funds can be sent a managed.
Payment cards or e-wallets	The platform offers payment cards or e-wallets which consumers can use to pay for products or services within or outside of the platform.
Store payment information	The platform stores payment information of their consumers within the platform to enable payments without entering the payment credentials.
Lending	The platform lends funds to their consumer or producer segments or allows negative balances on payment cards, e-wallets or IBAN accounts.

Table 3. Requirements for Marketplace Platform Businesses to Facilitate Payments.

Requirement	Description
Regulatory Licensing	The required licensing for payment facilitation is either PI, EMI or banking (Table. 1) and depends on the criteria of the platform.
Capital	The minimum capital requirements of the platform depend on the evaluated license which is closer specified in Table 1.
Subsidiary organisation in EU	In case the payment facilitation is made in-house (by using EMI or banking license), a subsidiary organisation is required within the EU.
Technological infrastructure	To facilitate payments the platform must build or acquire the necessary technology stack for payment processing, including secure servers, payment gateways, and fraud detection systems.
Security	Implement state-of-the-art security measures for fraud prevention, encryption, and secure data storage. To store payment credentials or to issue payment cards PCI-DSS is an obligatory requirement.
Expertise and staffing	Recruit or develop expertise in regulatory compliance, financial operations, and cybersecurity.
Governance mechanisms	Establish a governance framework to oversee payment operations and ensure activities to maintain compliance with regulatory standards and guidelines.
Risk Management	Implement risk management processes to facilitate secure payments, aimed at identifying and mitigating potential risks in the transactions.
Compliance mechanisms	In case the payment facilitation is made in-house by the platform, which is the case with EMI or banking license, the platform must implement mechanisms for compliance with financial regulations, including anti-money laundering and counter-terrorist financing controls.

3.4 Artefact

The Microsoft Excel-based artefact is designed to streamline decision-making for marketplace platform managers. By integrating Visual Basic for Applications (VBA), the tool extends Excel's native functionalities, leveraging its widespread usage and economies of scale. This integration ensures that even users with minimal technical expertise can operate the Decision Support Artefact effectively. Through a structured decision-making framework, the artefact simplifies the complexities of navigating regulatory landscapes based on the operational and business demands of marketplace platforms within the EU. It serves as a practical application of theoretical models, translating abstract concepts into actionable strategies. The artefact (excel-based file) is available at <https://drive.switch.ch/index.php/s/PxA18fxJW8oZ39C>.

Fig 3. Cropped Image of the Decision Support Artefact.

The artefact provides several sheets, while the "Decision Support" Sheet includes the core functionality, designed to help marketplace platform managers assess their payment facilitation needs and corresponding licensing requirements (Fig. 3). It features a two-part questionnaire: the criteria questionnaire and the requirement self-assessment, both essential for generating tailored advisory and reference content.

The criteria questionnaire section of the framework captures specific details about the marketplace platform’s payment facilitation needs. The information gathered is used with MD-DSS to determine one of several license options for supporting payments in the EU.

The requirement self-assessment section helps users evaluate compliance with license requirements, identifying areas that are fulfilled and those needing further effort. Insights from expert evaluations refined the advisory results, improving clarity and incorporating helpful hints and references. Initial knowledge, summarised in Table 1, was transformed into tailored suggestions, which were later enriched with interview feedback, and a references section was added to provide actionable guidance.

An additional "AI" sheet presents an experimental OpenAI-based advisory designed to challenge the artefacts advisory results. This aims to facilitate and support further research in this field.

3.5 Evaluation

Two iterative interview rounds allowed for incremental enhancements to the artefacts design and usability. Five experts, anonymised for confidentiality, participated, representing marketplace platforms, payment service providers, and banks, with experience ranging from 10 to 20 years. Interview questions targeted three areas: the relevance of the criteria, the feasibility of the requirements, and the artefact's usefulness in decision-making. The iterative process led to notable enhancements, such as clarifying criteria, separating risk management as a standalone requirement, and adding references for actionable guidance. Key suggestions requiring further research, like developing a web-based tool, were noted for future iterations. The evaluation validated the artefact's effectiveness as a decision-making aid, demonstrating its potential to assist marketplace platforms in addressing payment facilitation challenges.

4 Conclusion and Outlook

This research examined digital payment facilitation for EU marketplace platforms, focusing on regulatory frameworks, decision-making criteria, and the development of a decision support artefact to evaluate in-house payment facilitation versus outsourcing.

Platforms like Airbnb and Uber enable global market access but face challenges from regulations such as PSD2 and AML laws. While outsourcing reduces costs, in-house facilitation offers sufficient control, customer experience, and revenue potential. The EMI license emerged as the most suitable option due to its flexibility and lower regulatory hurdles. Using the Design Science Research (DSR) approach, the research developed a user-friendly Excel-based framework to address regulatory and operational needs. Expert feedback validated its relevance and potential to enhance decision-making. The research opens the following fields for future research and development: (1) Enhancing Usability: Transform the artefact into an interactive, web-based tool for greater accessibility, (2) Broadening Scope: Link the artefact to related topics for comprehensive decision-making resources, (3) Tailoring Insights: Further evaluate and customise the framework through stakeholder feedback. (4) Regulatory Updates: Align the artefact with evolving EU regulations, such as PSD3. (5) Data Integration: Incorporate AI and advanced analytics for improved foresight and adaptability.

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Strategic Leadership and 4IR Technologies in R&D: Analysis of Innovation Barriers in South Africa's Pharmaceutical Sector

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Abstract. The increasing adoption of technologies associated with the Fourth Industrial Revolution (4IR), such as artificial intelligence (AI) and biotechnology, presents opportunities for enhancing research and development (R&D), and innovation within pharmaceutical organisations. This study examines the relationship between R&D intensity, strategic leadership, and the adoption of 4IR technologies in South Africa's pharmaceutical sector. Using a quantitative approach, survey data was collected from industry professionals and key decision makers, yielding 78 valid responses. Findings indicate that while emerging 4IR technologies are important, they alone do not drive strategic innovation. Their success depends on effective integration into existing frameworks, with top management support playing a crucial role. Barriers such as technological gaps, regulatory delays, and skill shortages hinder technology adoption. The weak link between technology capability and innovation highlights the need for stronger digital literacy and aligned leadership. Pharmaceutical organisations should integrate technologies with leadership-driven R&D strategies, while policymakers should focus on regulatory reforms and incentives. This study provides insights into technology, leadership, and R&D in emerging healthcare markets, calling for further research on digital transformation's long-term impact.

Keywords: 4IR, Pharmaceutical R&D, Innovation Barriers, Strategic Leadership, Technology Adoption.

1 Introduction

The global pharmaceutical market valuation was an estimated US\$1.6 trillion in 2023, with projections estimating that it will reach US\$1.9 trillion by 2027. The United States dominates this sector, accounting for nearly 40% of the global pharmaceutical market [1]. To support these market developments, organisations in the pharmaceutical industry are leveraging technologies of the Fourth Industrial Revolution (4IR) to drive their digital transformation strategies [2, 3]. Technologies such as Artificial Intelligence (AI), biotechnology, and big data analytics are being adopted across the business units to reshape drug discovery, optimise clinical trials and healthcare delivery, allowing pharmaceutical stakeholders to enhance research and development (R&D) efficiency [4]. Emerging healthcare markets are also expanding rapidly. In South Africa, the pharmaceutical industry is the largest in Sub-Saharan Africa, valued at ZAR157.14 trillion

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15703822
In Proceedings: Corradini, F.; Hinkelmann, K.; Re, B., Smuts, H., eds. (2025). Proceedings of the 5th Conference Society 5.0 - Co-Existence Between Human Being and Machine Being, Vol. 2. San Benedetto del Tronto, Italy, 25-27 June 2025.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15422355>

in 2023, and is projected to grow [5]. However, as global competition intensifies, leveraging technological innovation is no longer a luxury but a necessity to enhance drug development pipelines, improve regulatory compliance, and ensure sustainable business practices [4, 6–9], to name a few. In this context, the effective adoption of 4IR technologies is a critical success factor in the future of pharmaceutical R&D and market competitiveness [2].

4IR technologies offer a strategic avenue to overcome challenges and existing lacunae. For instance, AI can accelerate drug discovery by processing vast biomedical datasets, while biotechnology facilitates advancements in precision medicine, personalised drug formulations, and biopharmaceutical production [6]. Despite these transformative potentials, the integration of these technologies in South African pharmaceutical organisations remains irregular. Several structural barriers hinder widespread adoption, including limited technological infrastructure, regulatory constraints, and resource limitations [10, 11]. There is also a limited talent pool due to the migration of skills [12]. Addressing these challenges requires a strategic level understanding of how organisations adopt and integrate 4IR technologies within their business information systems, yet this remains an underexplored area in the South African pharmaceutical sector.

Extensive research has examined the role of R&D investment in pharmaceutical innovation, highlighting its impact on market sustainability, competitive advantage, and breakthrough drug formulations [4, 6, 13]. However, there remains a gap in empirical research on how South African pharmaceutical organisations integrate 4IR technologies into their R&D process [4]. Existing studies predominantly focus on developed markets, lacking a clear understanding of how emerging economies like South Africa navigate digital transformation in R&D [9]. This gap presents an opportunity to explore how the integration of advanced technologies, such as AI and biotechnology, can enhance R&D outcomes and contribute to the sector's growth and competitiveness in the South African context.

The Technology-Organisation-Environment (TOE) framework [14] provides a structured approach to examining technology adoption in pharmaceutical organisations by considering three key dimensions. The first is (i) technological context, which explores the role of AI, biotechnology, and data analytics in R&D. Secondly, (ii) organisational context, which assesses how internal factors such as leadership commitment, workforce capability, and investment in R&D determine the extent of technological integration [3]. Finally, (iii) environmental context considers external influences, such as regulatory compliance, industry competition, and public health challenges [15]. To this effect, the TOE framework is advantageous in identifying key enablers and barriers to technology adoption in pharmaceutical R&D. However, it does not always explain how these technologies diffuse within the industry. Due to this limitation, the Diffusion of Innovations (DOI) theory [16] was considered, which focuses on how innovations spread within one sector [17–19]. This is because in the South African pharmaceutical sector, the DOI framework is relevant in understanding the adoption of AI and biotechnology. These technologies offer relative advantages as they enhance drug discovery and precision medicine [4]. However, compatibility challenges exist, particularly concerning integrating with existing R&D infrastructure and aligning with regulatory

frameworks. The complexity of implementing AI-driven drug discovery presents another barrier, given that it requires advanced expertise and computational resources that may not be readily available in resource-constrained settings [20]. Despite the insights provided by DOI, its applicability to pharmaceutical R&D in South Africa remains limited. Unlike consumer-driven industries where innovations diffuse rapidly, pharmaceutical R&D is characterised by long product development cycles, stringent regulatory scrutiny, and substantial capital investments, which slows the diffusion process [4, 21]. Additionally, the interaction between organisational leadership, regulatory policies, and economic constraints in shaping adoption decisions requires deeper empirical analysis.

Consequently, this study explores the impact of R&D intensity and leadership decision-making on innovation outcomes, focusing on the role of 4IR technologies as enablers or barriers to technological transformation in South Africa's pharmaceutical sector. The central research question guiding this investigation is "*How does R&D intensity impact strategic and innovative decisions within the South African pharmaceutical industry?*".

To achieve this, a quantitative research design is adopted, incorporating industry surveys and data analytics to assess how South African pharmaceutical organisations are adopting 4IR technologies. The research is grounded in the TOE updated for 4IR technologies [19], with data collected from pharmaceutical executives, R&D professionals, and industry stakeholders.

This study aligns with global efforts to leverage 4IR technologies for enhanced healthcare outcomes, contributing to the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), particularly Good Health and Well-being and Industry (SDG 3), Innovation, and Infrastructure (SDG 9).

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: Section 2 reviews the literature on pharmaceutical R&D and 4IR technologies, Section 3 details the research methodology, Section 4 notes findings, and Section 5 and 6 encompass the discussion with implications for industry and policy and concluding thoughts.

2 Background

The South African pharmaceutical sector significantly contributes to the country's Gross Domestic Product (GDP) and remains the most developed in Sub-Saharan Africa. Novartis, a JSE-listed pharmaceutical company, contributed over three billion rand to the South African economy in 2018. From 2013 to 2023, pharmaceutical sales have more than doubled, with projections estimating industry growth to reach approximately R48 billion. As of the fourth quarter of 2023, the pharmaceutical sector accounted for 1.04% of South Africa's GDP, which stood at R1.15 trillion [22]. These figures highlight the industry's economic significance and role in supporting national health policies and industrial development.

Despite its economic importance, the sector faces structural and technological challenges that hinder its ability to effectively leverage 4IR technologies. The industry's reliance on traditional pharmaceutical processes and regulatory barriers limits its capacity for rapid technological integration. While the global pharmaceutical industry has

embraced digital transformation, mainly through AI, biotechnology, and data analytics, South Africa's pharmaceutical organisations have lagged in implementing these technologies due to financial and regulatory constraints [8, 15].

2.1 Industry Dynamics and Barriers

Technological advancements have transformed pharmaceutical industries worldwide, enabling more efficient drug discovery, personalised medicine, and AI-driven research processes [2, 4]. However, the South African pharmaceutical sector has exhibited stagnation in its technological evolution, with organisations continuing to rely on conventional R&D methodologies rather than fully adopting 4IR technologies [10, 11]. The reluctance to transition towards digitally enabled health solutions has resulted in inefficiencies that affect drug development cycles and market competitiveness. Key trends in global pharmaceutical innovation indicate a growing reliance on biotechnology, AI-assisted drug development, and regulatory shifts that encourage digital integration [3]. South Africa, however, faces significant challenges in aligning with these trends. Regulatory constraints, financial limitations, and resistance to technological change have emerged as primary obstacles to successfully implementing AI-driven solutions and biotechnological advancements [11]. The stringent regulatory frameworks that govern pharmaceutical innovations in South Africa delay the approval and commercialisation of new technologies, creating a restrictive backlog towards R&D expansion. Additionally, ethical considerations surrounding AI in drug development further complicate regulatory approvals, preventing organisations from fully leveraging emerging technologies. Financial constraints present another major challenge, as implementing AI and biotechnology in R&D requires substantial capital investment, which many pharmaceutical companies are reluctant to undertake due to perceived financial risks [23]. Studies indicate that many organisations remain sceptical about the cost-benefit ratio of 4IR technology adoption, with concerns that investment in AI-driven drug discovery may not yield immediate returns [24]. As a result, multinational corporations with significant financial capacity lead innovation efforts while smaller pharmaceutical organisations struggle to compete.

2.2 Drivers of Technological Innovation Adoption

Despite the challenges, several factors drive the adoption of 4IR technologies in the South African pharmaceutical industry. One significant driver is the consumerisation of healthcare, which has increased demand for digital health solutions, including AI-assisted diagnostics, telemedicine, and online pharmaceutical services [24]. Patients increasingly prefer healthcare providers that offer digital services, prompting pharmaceutical organisations to invest in automation and data-driven decision-making. Growing cost-related challenges within the sector have also encouraged organisations to explore digital transformation to reduce operational inefficiencies and increase productivity [25]. Global competition (environment) has also acted as a catalyst for technological adoption. As multinational pharmaceutical organisations integrate AI-driven research

and automation, South African companies face increasing pressure to remain competitive by investing in similar technologies. Strategic investment is essential for local organisations to maintain relevance in the rapidly evolving landscape [23].

2.3 Strategy's Role in Fostering Innovation for Sustainable Business Practices

Pharmaceutical companies that adopt structured innovation strategies exhibit higher levels of sustainability and competitiveness. Huang (2021) highlights that leading organisations such as Pfizer, Johnson & Johnson, and Novartis sustain long-term growth by prioritising R&D investments and fostering collaborations with technology providers [26]. These companies have successfully integrated 4IR technologies to enhance production efficiency and reduce environmental impact. Emerging research suggests that innovation strategies must address technological factors and economic and regulatory considerations. Pharmaceutical organisations must develop policies that balance technological advancements with industry regulations and financial sustainability [7]. The practical implementation of innovation strategies ensures that organisations can optimise R&D efficiency while complying with sustainability standards.

2.4 Hypothesis Development Based on Literature

The development of the hypotheses in this study was informed by existing literature on R&D intensity, technological adoption, and innovation within the pharmaceutical industry, with a specific focus on emerging technologies such as 4IR. The first hypothesis, testing whether investment in 4IR technologies positively influences strategic innovation outcomes in the South African pharmaceutical industry, draws from studies on technology integration in developed markets, highlighting the need for comprehensive infrastructure and leadership engagement to drive meaningful innovation [2, 4]. The second hypothesis, exploring the impact of top management support on industry growth, is supported by literature on the role of leadership in facilitating the adoption of advanced technologies and aligning R&D with corporate strategy [3, 19]. The third hypothesis, which examines whether the allocation of advanced skills enhances innovation in pharmaceutical R&D, aligns with findings suggesting that while skilled personnel are vital, their effectiveness is contingent on organisational factors such as technological infrastructure and strategic alignment [7, 9]. These hypotheses are grounded in the theoretical framework provided by the TOE model [17].

3 Methodology

This study adopts a positivist research philosophy, employing a deductive approach to examine the relationships between R&D intensity, strategic leadership, and the adoption of 4IR technologies within the South African pharmaceutical industry. The deductive approach is considered appropriate for testing established theories and hypotheses derived from existing literature, allowing for the evaluation of measurable relationships between variables such as investment in emerging technologies, managerial support,

and innovation outcomes. Given the study's aim to assess these relationships quantitatively, a quantitative research design was deemed fitting. This design enables the systematic collection and analysis of numerical data, providing objective insights into the extent to which 4IR technologies are being adopted and their impact on innovation outcomes within the sector. A deductive approach is advantageous in this context, as it allows for the testing of hypotheses drawn from theoretical frameworks, rather than building new theory from exploratory findings. This warrants that the study's findings contribute to existing literature by supporting established models, providing insights for both practitioners and academics in the field. Following Saunders *et al.* (2019) research onion framework, a cross-sectional survey approach was employed, allowing for a structured and systematic analysis of industry professionals' perspectives on 4IR integration in pharmaceutical R&D [27].

3.1 Research Design and Sampling Strategy

A structured survey-based methodology was used to collect primary data from pharmaceutical industry professionals in South Africa. The target population included R&D professionals, senior executives, technology managers, and strategy specialists working within pharmaceutical organisations. These participants were selected based on their direct involvement in R&D decision-making, strategic planning, and technology adoption, ensuring that responses were derived from individuals with relevant expertise and industry knowledge. A stratified random sampling method was employed to ensure a representative distribution of organisations across different categories, including multinational corporations, generic drug manufacturers, and biopharmaceutical organisations. This approach reduced selection bias and enhanced the generalisability of the findings. Given the relatively small and specialised nature of the South African pharmaceutical sector, a target sample size of 200 was initially set. However, 78 valid responses were obtained, reflecting the challenges of accessing a highly regulated and niche workforce. Despite the lower-than-anticipated response rate, the sample remains valid due to the specialised nature of the target respondents, who occupy decision-making roles within the industry [26, 28]. To address potential representativeness issues, the study adopted non-response mitigation strategies, including follow-up emails and extended survey distribution periods. Additionally, any incomplete data were excluded if there were any missing values, ensuring that incomplete responses were discarded so as not to affect the reliability of the dataset.

3.2 Data Collection and Instrumentation

The survey was administered electronically via the Qualtrics platform, supporting a secure and anonymous data collection process while maintaining the integrity of participant responses. The survey instrument was developed based on validated constructs from established literature, particularly drawing from Kruger and Steyn (2023) [19]. This approach allowed for the integration of well-supported theoretical frameworks, warranting that the constructs measured were relevant and aligned with the study's objectives. A seven-point Likert scale (ranging from 1 = Strongly Disagree to 7 = Strongly

Agree) was utilised to capture respondents' perceptions of key constructs, enabling assessment of attitudes toward 4IR adoption and its impact on innovation performance within the pharmaceutical industry. Prior to full-scale data collection, a pilot study was conducted with five industry professionals to assess the clarity, reliability, and structure of the survey items. Feedback from the pilot study led to minor adjustments in question phrasing and alignment, ensuring that the instrument accurately captured the intended variables and met the study's objectives. This refinement process helped to improve the reliability of the instrument, addressing any ambiguities and ensuring that the survey would generate data that was both valid and meaningful for evaluating relationships.

3.3 Data Analysis Approach and Ethical Considerations

The collected data was analysed using IBM SPSS Statistics 29, applying descriptive, inferential, and multivariate statistical techniques to test the study's hypotheses. The first stage of analysis involved descriptive statistics to summarise respondent characteristics and assess general trends across key constructs. Correlation analysis was performed to examine relationships between R&D intensity, top management support, technology adoption, and strategic innovation outcomes. To determine the impact of 4IR technologies and leadership support on R&D innovation, multiple regression analysis was conducted. This technique allowed for the assessment of the predictive power of independent variables (investment in AI, biotechnology, and managerial support) on dependent variables (innovation performance and business growth). Variance Inflation Factors (VIF) were applied to identify potential multicollinearity issues, ensuring that independent variables were not excessively correlated, which could compromise regression results.

Reliability analysis was conducted using Cronbach's alpha, with an acceptable threshold of 0.7 to confirm the internal consistency of the constructs. Additionally, Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) was performed to assess construct validity and ensure that the survey items accurately measured the intended theoretical variables. Given the smaller sample size, robust standard errors were applied in regression models to enhance the accuracy of parameter estimates. While the final response rate was lower than anticipated, the study strived for methodological rigor by focusing on industry professionals directly engaged in strategic innovation and R&D leadership, thereby minimising concerns related to external validity.

This study received ethical approval from the research ethics committee at the university where the researchers were based, ensuring adherence to standard ethical protocols.

4 Findings

The descriptive statistics include the number of responses (n), mean (M), standard deviation (SD), and reliability estimates using Cronbach's alpha (α). The results indicate that Top Management Support for Growth Enablement has the highest mean score ($M = 5.82$, $SD = 11.41$), suggesting that respondents generally perceive top management

as moderately supportive of R&D-driven innovation. Technological Capabilities & Innovation in Pharmaceutical R&D received a lower mean score ($M = 5.73$, $SD = 11.44$), suggesting a more neutral or varied perception regarding the extent of technology adoption within the sector. Relative Advantage & Strategic Innovation Outcomes, which measure the perceived benefits of R&D intensity, yielded a mean of $M = 3.64$, $SD = 11.73$, implying mixed responses, with some scepticism toward the effectiveness of R&D investments in enhancing innovation outcomes.

Reliability analysis using Cronbach's alpha yielded high values ($\alpha \approx 0.998$ across constructs), indicating strong internal consistency among survey items. However, the high VIF values, particularly for Technological Capabilities & Innovation in Pharmaceutical R&D ($VIF = 106.89$) and Top Management Support ($VIF = 123.07$), suggest possible multicollinearity concerns, indicating that some variables may be highly inter-related.

4.1 Construct Assessment

The mean score for Relative Advantage & Strategic Innovation Outcomes ($M = 3.64$, $SD = 11.73$) suggests a moderately varied perception of the extent to which R&D investments influence strategic innovation. The spreading in responses implies that while some participants perceive R&D intensity as beneficial, others remain neutral or slightly sceptical. This suggests that organisations, or even specific business units, may not fully realise the innovation potential of their R&D investments.

The mean score for Top Management Support for Growth Enablement ($M = 5.82$, $SD = 11.41$) indicates a generally positive but somewhat dispersed perception of leadership's role in fostering R&D growth. While top management support appears to be present, the variance in responses suggests inconsistencies across organisations. Some organisations may have strong leadership commitment to R&D, while others struggle to align strategic objectives and R&D priorities. The findings support the notion that managerial commitment is a key driver of R&D-driven innovation but remains an area requiring further development within the South African pharmaceutical industry.

The Technological Capabilities & Innovation in Pharmaceutical R&D construct received a mean score of $M = 5.73$, $SD = 11.44$, indicating that perceptions of technological readiness within the sector are varied. Given that South Africa's pharmaceutical industry has historically lagged in digital transformation, this finding aligns with previous research suggesting that adopting AI, biotechnology, and data-driven R&D processes remains limited. While some organisations appear to be integrating advanced technologies, the industry landscape remains fragmented, with gaps in capability development and infrastructure.

4.2 Hypothesis Testing

To assess the research hypotheses, t-tests were conducted to evaluate whether each construct's mean significantly deviated from the neutral midpoint (4 on a 7-point Likert scale). Pearson correlation analysis was used to determine relationships between key constructs.

The first hypothesis tested whether investment in 4IR technologies positively influences strategic innovation outcomes within the South African pharmaceutical industry. The results show a negligible mean correlation (0.006) between investment and innovation outcomes, with a non-significant t-test ($p > 0.05$). Thus, we fail to reject the null hypothesis (H_0), indicating that investment in 4IR technologies does not significantly impact innovation outcomes. This suggests that additional factors, such as leadership engagement, workforce skills, and regulatory barriers, may be needed to drive strategic innovation.

The second hypothesis examined whether top management support for 4IR technologies positively influences industry growth. The results indicate a significant positive correlation (mean correlation = 0.520, $p < 0.01$), leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis (H_0). This supports the idea that strong managerial commitment to R&D is crucial for leveraging 4IR technologies and fostering a culture of innovation. Organisations lacking executive support may struggle to align R&D investments with corporate strategy, limiting innovation.

The third hypothesis tested whether allocating advanced skills within organisations enhances innovation in pharmaceutical R&D. The findings show a weak correlation (mean correlation = 0.019) with innovation, and the t-test results were non-significant ($p > 0.05$). We fail to reject the null hypothesis (H_0), suggesting that skilled personnel alone are insufficient to drive innovation without the necessary technological infrastructure, strategic alignment, and funding. Organisations must bridge skill gaps with improved infrastructure and effectively integrate expertise into R&D processes.

Table 1. Hypothesis overview.

Hypothesis	Statement	Statistical result	Decision
H1	Investing in 4IR technologies positively influences strategic innovation outcomes.	Non-significant ($p > 0.05$)	Fail to reject H_0
H2	Top management support for 4IR technologies positively impacts growth.	Significant ($p = 0.006$)	Reject H_0
H3	Allocation of advanced skills enhances pharmaceutical R&D innovation.	Non-significant ($p > 0.05$)	Fail to reject H_0

5 Discussion

The primary objective of this study was to assess the impact of R&D intensity on strategic decision-making and innovation within the South African pharmaceutical industry, with a focus on the role of 4IR technologies. While AI and biotechnology are widely recognised for their potential to enhance pharmaceutical R&D [4, 8, 28, 29], the findings indicate that investment in these technologies alone does not directly lead to strategic innovation. Instead, the study highlights that top management support and strategic leadership play a more crucial role in enabling successful R&D-driven innovation. This challenges the assumption that technological integration alone drives innovation

outcomes. Effective digital transformation requires not only investment but also leadership commitment, regulatory adaptation, and workforce reskilling to optimise the use of new technologies within existing R&D frameworks.

Novel technologies may offer transformative potential in pharmaceutical R&D, but their effectiveness is contingent upon the organisation's capacity to integrate them into existing frameworks. Without addressing structural inefficiencies, regulatory barriers, and skill shortages, technology adoption is unlikely to yield meaningful innovation.

In contrast to the limited effect of technology investment, top management support emerged as a driver of industry growth and innovation adoption. Organisations where executives actively engaged with R&D strategy and technology implementation were more successful in integrating 4IR tools and achieving positive innovation outcomes. This finding aligns with existing literature on strategic leadership and innovation, underscoring that organisational commitment, rather than financial investment alone, is essential for technological success. Strong leadership fosters a culture of innovation, enables policy development, and ensures that technology investments are strategically aligned with corporate goals. The positive relationship between executive support and technology adoption highlights the need for leadership-driven digital transformation strategies in the pharmaceutical sector.

The study also identified technological capability gaps as a major barrier to pharmaceutical innovation. While respondents acknowledged the importance of technology in enhancing drug discovery, clinical trials, and personalised medicine, they expressed concerns about inadequate infrastructure, regulatory delays, and a shortage of skilled professionals in digital health and computational drug discovery. The weak correlation between technological capability and innovation outcomes suggests that many organisations are not yet effectively leveraging 4IR technologies, likely due to insufficient digital literacy and fragmented adoption strategies. Proficiency in digital literacy is critical when adopting new technologies; without these skills, companies struggle to utilise modern methods effectively, leading to scattered efforts and missed opportunities in strategic implementation.

This study contributes to the body of research on digital transformation in emerging markets, offering empirical insights into the intersection of R&D and 4IR adoption in South Africa's pharmaceutical industry. While extensive research has focused on pharmaceutical innovation in developed economies, limited studies have explored how emerging economies navigate digital transformation amidst structural constraints. By applying the amended TOE model, the study provides further understanding of the factors influencing 4IR adoption in pharmaceutical R&D. However, the findings suggest that these models alone may not fully explain the South African context. Given the significant role of leadership in technology adoption, a leadership-driven innovation model, such as the Dynamic Capabilities Framework, could offer additional explanatory power for future research.

The findings have implications for both industry practitioners and policymakers. The weak relationship between technology investment and innovation outcomes suggests that pharmaceutical organisations must adopt a more strategic approach to 4IR adoption. Rather than viewing emerging technologies as isolated investments, organi-

sations should focus on aligning these technologies with leadership-driven strategic objectives, business models, and long-term R&D priorities. Strengthening executive leadership in R&D strategy and digital literacy is critical. Given the positive relationship between top management support and industry growth, organisations should invest in leadership development programs focused on digital transformation, regulatory navigation, and AI-driven decision-making. Such programs can help industry executives integrate 4IR technologies effectively into corporate strategy and innovation processes.

Addressing technological capability gaps is another key consideration for industry stakeholders. The sector can invest in upskilling programs that equip professionals with the necessary competencies to work with AI-assisted drug discovery tools and biotechnological advancements. Public-private partnerships can play a role in encouraging industry-academic collaborations to develop specialised training programs in digital health and computational medicine. Additionally, financial incentives, such as tax credits for companies investing in workforce development, could accelerate the adoption of AI and biotechnology in pharmaceutical R&D. These initiatives would help bridge the digital skills gap, ensuring that organisations have access to a workforce capable of leveraging 4IR technologies effectively [12].

Regulatory reform is also essential to support innovation in the pharmaceutical sector. Policymakers should consider streamlining regulatory approvals for AI-based drug discovery and digital clinical trials to accelerate the innovation process. From a Society 5.0 perspective, cross-disciplinary collaboration could further enhance healthcare, underpinned by human-centric innovation.

6 Conclusion

This study provides insights into the relationship between R&D intensity, strategic decision-making, and 4IR technology adoption in the South African pharmaceutical industry. While investment in technology alone does not guarantee innovation, top management support emerges as a crucial enabler of industry growth. The findings suggest that technological capability gaps persist, necessitating targeted interventions in workforce training, strategic alignment, and regulatory adaptation.

Future research should examine longitudinal data to assess how R&D intensity influences innovation outcomes over time. A time-series analysis would allow for more accurate predictions of industry trends, particularly in the context of 4IR technology adoption. Also, research should include comparative studies between South Africa and other emerging markets, such as India and Brazil, to identify common barriers and best practices in pharmaceutical R&D.

6.1 Limitations

Despite its contributions, the study faced several limitations. The sample size of 78 responses, though valid for a niche industry, limits generalisability. Future research should aim to expand the sample size, potentially by partnering with pharmaceutical

industry bodies to increase survey participation. The study primarily relied on self-reported survey data, which may be subject to response bias.

Acknowledgments and Disclosure of Interests. We want to thank our dedicated information specialist and the ethical committee for their support in this research. The authors have no competing interests to declare that are relevant to this research study.

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A Conceptual Framework for an Inclusive Support System: The Underrepresentation of Women in ICT

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Abstract. The ICT sector is growing rapidly, leading to high job demands in the market. However, despite this growth, there is a concerning decline in the representation of women in the field. This issue has become a global crisis, especially in the context of achieving a Society 5.0 community. The underrepresentation of women in ICT is driven by various factors that women face both in educational settings; the society and at the workplace.

By applying the “Individual Differences Theory of Gender and Information Technology” framework, this paper presents a systematic literature review (SLR) of 29 studies, aimed at identifying and discussing the barriers contributing to the underrepresentation of women in ICT. Additionally, it explores ways in which women can take responsibility for reshaping the field to foster greater gender inclusion.

The findings highlight the key barriers identified in the literature that contribute to this underrepresentation, and propose strategic measures that women can adopt to transform the ICT field for greater gender inclusivity. In conclusion, a conceptual framework is developed, which outlines strategic actions and provides a toolkit to address the challenges women face in both educational and workplace environments, ultimately reshaping the ICT field for enhanced gender inclusivity.

Keywords: Information Communication and Technology, Gender; Inclusivity; Underrepresentation, Women, Society 5.0

1 Introduction

The gender imbalance in the ICT field represents a significant diversity deficit. Despite the growing demand for skills within the sector [2], the representation of women remains disproportionately low. This is particularly evident in artificial intelligence (AI), one of the fastest-growing subfields in ICT. AI is driving the world toward a digital economy, underscoring the rapid expansion of the ICT industry [1]. However, as the field grows, the participation of women remains stagnant.

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15703894

In Proceedings: Corradini, F.; Hinkelmann, K.; Re, B., Smuts, H., eds. (2025). Proceedings of the 5th Conference Society 5.0 - Co-Existence Between Human Being and Machine Being, Vol. 2.

San Benedetto del Tronto, Italy, 25-27 June 2025.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15422355>

Studies across various countries reveal a consistent gender imbalance in the ICT industry [3], [4], [5], [35], [37]. For example, research from Bangladesh's Open-Source Network shows that only 25% of women in Bangladesh are pursuing ICT degrees [4]. This underrepresentation is not a new issue; it was first identified in the late 20th century [5]. Societal gender norms often lead girls to believe ICT degrees are primarily for men, steering them toward fields like health and social sciences [6]. As a result, fewer women pursue ICT careers, and even fewer continue in the industry long-term [4]. Research by Tahsin et al. indicates that only 13% of female ICT graduates enter the workforce, with that figure dropping to 10% as women often leave the industry due to various challenges, including gender discrimination [4].

Gender discrimination is a major barrier to diversity in the ICT field [7]. Women who remain in the industry often have to empower themselves through initiatives like coding boot camps, where they can find support and encouragement from other women [7]. These efforts are crucial for breaking down barriers and improving gender inclusion within the ICT sector.

The relationship between women's representation and the growth of the ICT field is inversely proportional [8]. While there is a high demand for ICT skills, the industry continues to be male-dominated [1], and this gender gap poses risks. For example, many tech products are developed from a male perspective, which can result in both deliberate and inadvertent biases [1]. This lack of diversity in development teams contributes to stereotypical technology solutions, limiting the potential of future innovations [9].

Addressing the gender gap in ICT is critical for fostering a more inclusive environment that drives diverse technological solutions [1]. To attract more women into the field, it's vital to emphasize the role that women in ICT play in reshaping the industry. Their presence in communities such as Society 5.0 and events can inspire future generations of women to pursue ICT careers. Society 5.0 refers to a concept of a society driven by technological advancements that envisions the integration of the physical and digital worlds through the use of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) to create a "super-smart society" [34]. This vision includes a sustainable and inclusive socio-economic system, powered by digital technologies such as big data analytics, artificial intelligence (AI), the Internet of Things (IoT), and robotics [34].

The "Individual Differences Theory of Gender and Information Technology" [10] is a theoretical framework used to identify the various factors, classified as environmental, identity, and individual influences, that contribute to the underrepresentation of women in ICT. Based on this framework, the following research questions guide this systematic literature review:

1. What factors (environmental, identity and individual) contribute to the underrepresentation of women in the ICT field?
2. What measures (in the form of a strategic framework) can women take to achieve equal representation in the ICT field, considering the future development of a community driven by Society 5.0

The strategic framework developed as a result of this research may support various stakeholders, including women in the ICT sector, in addressing the factors—classified according to the Individual Differences Theory of Gender and Information Technology—that contribute to the underrepresentation of women in the field.

2 Literature Background

The integration of science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM) is currently marked by the lowest level of female representation [11]. For instance, a study by Adams and Morgan [2] in Australia, which examined female representation in STEM faculties, found that women make up only 13% of technological departments, compared to 23% in science and 35% in mathematics [2]. This gap is primarily due to the limited number of women pursuing ICT careers after high school, which negatively affects the ICT industry. Jurado, Tretiakov, and Bensemann [8] emphasize the widespread underrepresentation of women in the ICT sector across various countries. Their figures, recorded in 2018, show the proportion of women in the ICT industry by country. The countries listed are as follows: India ranks first with 34%, Australia

follows in second place with 30%, Turkey ranks third at 28%, and the United Kingdom ranks last at 16% [8]. Additionally, Hyrynsalmi [12] highlights that women in the U.S. hold only 11% of managerial positions in the ICT sector.

The difficulty of balancing work and family responsibilities often prevents women from seeking managerial roles, and the industry's pressures contribute to many women leaving the field, further reducing female representation in leadership positions [5]. This phenomenon is a global trend.

In the past, the ICT industry was predominantly female, but this rapidly changed over time. In 1984, 37% of computer science majors were women, but by 2020, this figure had dropped to 18% [1]. Socio-cultural expectations and traditional gender biases, along with stereotyping, have contributed to this decline. These factors have created barriers for women pursuing ICT degrees and careers.

Socio-cultural expectations and gender narratives affect various stages of a woman's life [9]. First, girls often encounter educational barriers that limit their exposure to ICT. A study [12] found that while girls outperform boys in STEM subjects in high school, few women pursue ICT degrees, suggesting a lack of awareness or guidance about ICT career paths. Adams and Morgan [2] found that many students were unfamiliar with the specifics of a Computer Science degree, highlighting a gap in exposure to computing and ICT fields.

Second, male dominance remains prevalent in the ICT industry. For example, a study at Universidad de la República in Uruguay showed that only 15% of female students were pursuing ICT degrees, compared to 20% of male students [6]. Women also represent only 18% of leadership roles in artificial intelligence research, while men make up 80% [1], underscoring the gender imbalance in the field.

Finally, women in ICT face challenges that often drive them to leave the industry. The lack of female representation in leadership roles contributes to mistreatment and marginalization [13]. Friedmann and Efrat-Treister [14] note that gender bias in hiring practices often leads to male candidates being preferred over female candidates. Additionally, many women leave the sector after maternity leave due to the difficulty of balancing new parental responsibilities with the demands of high-performance work in ICT [5]. Socialized gender norms about domestic duties and the pressure to meet work expectations frequently prevent women from returning to ICT roles after maternity leave.

Despite these challenges, women have taken steps to drive diversity and inclusion in the ICT industry. For example, Fonseca et al. [35] indicate how policies evolved through COVID and what progress was made to address digital equality. Efforts such as workshops, policies, institutional reforms, mentorship programs, and the creation of software community groups are slowly leading to more gender diversification within the sector [35], [36]. Genut and Kolikant [16] highlight an increase in women studying bioinformatics, reflecting a shift toward greater gender inclusion in ICT fields such as biology and information systems.

3 Research Method

The research conducted is a systematic literature review. According to Lame [17], a systematic literature review is a method of using multiple published sources to answer a research question. This process involves analysing and evaluating these sources to build an understanding of the findings and address the research question.

The data sources included: Scopus, ScienceDirect, IEEE Xplore Digital Library and Web of Science Core Collection.

The following search string was used: (“Underrepresentation”) AND (“Girls” OR “Women” OR “Females”) AND (“Information Communication Technology” OR “Information Technology” OR “Technology” OR “ICT” OR “IT” OR “Tech”).

The papers selected in this research study complied with the inclusion criteria as presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Selection criteria

Inclusion criteria
1. Papers published between 2018 and 2024, as the field of ICT is rapidly evolving, necessitating recent studies for a comprehensive evaluation.
2. Papers written exclusively in English.
3. Papers with full access to the complete text, including the abstract, introduction, discussion, methods, conclusion, and references.
4. Peer-reviewed papers from published literature, including peer-reviewed journals and articles.
5. Papers directly related to the topic of study

3.1 Prisma Flowchart

A Prisma flowchart is a diagram that outlines the breakdown of papers identified for analysis. Using the search string, a total of 736 papers were found across all the specified databases. The use of multiple databases resulted in 45 duplicate papers, leaving a final set of 691 papers. These were then screened by reviewing the abstracts and keywords. Following the screening protocol, 613 papers were excluded, leaving 78. After a full evaluation of the remaining papers, 49 were excluded, resulting in a total of 29 papers selected for this systematic literature review as indicated in Figure 1.

Fig. 1: Prisma flowchart

4 Findings and Discussion

4.1 Findings

This section presents the general findings from the 29 papers identified using the process described in the Prisma Flowchart in Section 3.

4.1.1 Descriptive Analysis of Literature Sources

Table 2 shows the distribution of selected papers across the databases used for this literature review from 2018 to 2024. Scopus has the highest number of selected papers, with 15, while ScienceDirect has the lowest, with only 1.

Table 2: Papers by database source

Source	Count	%
ScienceDirect	1	3.4
Scopus	15	51.7
IEEE Xplore	8	27.6
Web of Science Core Collection	5	17.3

4.1.2 Thematic Analysis

In this section, thematic analysis, as defined by Naeem, Ozuem, Howell and Ranfagni [18] is performed using VOSviewer, a tool for visualizing data networks. A network map, shown in Figure 3, was created through a keyword/code co-occurrence analysis

[19].

The lines in the map represent the relationships between keywords, while the circles indicate the number of research papers featuring each keyword. Larger circles signify keywords that appear in more papers, as detailed in Section 4.3 [19]. The map also features color-coded clusters, which are further interpreted in Table 3, based on the data network map in Figure 2.

Fig. 2: Data network map based on authors keywords

Table 3: Interpretation of relevant identified clusters

Cluster	Colour	Keywords/Codes	Thematic analysis
Cluster 1	Blue	Gender difference in STEM Career Choice Computer science education	The themes focus on the gender differences encountered by women in STEM and the implications of their career choices in computer science education
Cluster 2	Green	IT exclusion dynamics	The themes focus on the exclusion dynamics faced by girls in ICT and how these dynamics influence their career choices
Cluster 3	Yellow	Ability to work long hours Gender bias	The themes address the expectation that women must work long hours to be perceived as competent.
Cluster 4	Red	Gender stereotypes, bias and awareness	The themes focus on gender stereotypes, biases, and awareness

4.2 Discussion of Findings

The aim of this paper is to examine the challenges contributing to the underrepresentation of women in the ICT field and explore how women are taking control of their futures within it. Historical events have shaped the relationship between women and technology, contributing to the low representation of women in ICT. This underrepresentation is recognized as a global crisis, as current software and technological solutions are predominantly developed from a male perspective. This results in the exclusion of women from society, as future ICT products may be designed to cater primarily to men.

The findings in this paper also highlight the barriers leading to the underrepresentation of women in ICT. The "Individual Differences Theory of Gender and Information Technology (IT)" framework [10] is applied to identify three key categories: Environmental Factors, Influential Individuality Factors, and Identity Factors. The clusters identified in the thematic analysis (Table 3) are organized according to the three key categories of the Individual Differences Theory of Gender and Information Technology.

Serenko and Turel [10] define *environmental factors* as the impact of society's behavior, culture, and economic state on an individual. This systematic literature review explores how environmental factors create barriers to women entering the ICT field. The following environmental factors are identified in the findings:

1. **Workplace Environment (Cluster 2, 3, 4: Table 3):** A culture rooted in hypermasculinity, competitiveness, and gendered expectations is often unwelcoming to women [5]. As a result, many women leave the ICT field due to performance anxiety, unhealthy working conditions and exclusion from the work environment [4].
2. **Work-Life Balance (Cluster 3: Table 3):** The ICT field is constantly evolving, with new skills required to keep up with its rapid changes. As a result, professionals in this field must continuously upskill to stay current [5]. Additionally, Tretiakov, Bensemann, and Jurado [5] note that the ICT field is high-pressure, characterized by demanding workloads, strict deadlines, and projects that require 24/7 attention. This often leads to the need for overtime work. However, for women in the ICT field, balancing upskilling and overtime can be challenging. Societal expectations often place women in traditional family roles [11], where they are expected to prioritize family and household responsibilities over career ambitions. Guo, Eccles, Sortheix, and Salmela-Aro [11] highlight that women in traditional households are expected to focus on caregiving, while men are often viewed as the breadwinners, expected to prioritize work over family duties. This reinforces the stereotype that women cannot work overtime due to societal expectations of managing household responsibilities [14]. It's important to note that the assumption that all women struggle with work-life balance is a generalized stereotype.
3. **Gender Biases in Hiring (Cluster 2: Table 3):** In the ICT field, men are hired more frequently than women, largely due to discrimination during the interview process [14]. Women face both conscious and unconscious biases, including the expectation to work overtime due to household responsibilities, which hinders their entry into the workforce [14]. Furthermore, male managers tend to exhibit gender favouritism, favouring male candidates over female ones during the hiring process [14].
4. **Societal Expectations (Cluster 4: Table 3):** Society often defines how women should behave, reinforcing gender divisions in the ICT field. The theory of social constructionism shapes how women and men are treated in society by establishing predefined gender expectations and identity attributes for each gender [8]. This theory contributes to the creation of gender differences, which influence how both genders are perceived within society [8]. Social constructionism manifests through several key ideas: First, it perpetuates the perception that women are less competent than their male counterparts. Second, it promotes the idea that the ICT field is more suitable for men. Third, it fosters the belief that men are inherently smarter than women [20]. Moreover, social constructionism impacts career decisions for girls and women, as noted by Tanwir and Khemka [20]. Their survey in Pakistan revealed that societal gender norms are a primary reason for the low representation of women in the IT sector. These norms prevent women and girls from pursuing education and careers in demanding fields like ICT. As a result, women in the ICT workforce are subjected to discrimination, rooted in societal norms and stereotypes.

Serenko and Turel [10] define *identity factors* as the mindset and behaviors of an individual. The following identity factors were identified:

1. **Lack of Career Guidance (Cluster 1: Table 3):** Career guidance plays a critical role during adolescence, as individuals are highly influenced by external factors when choosing their career paths [9]. In this regard, females are often discouraged from pursuing careers in ICT [9]. Family members, teachers, and friends play a key role in shaping the career decisions of females [9]. The tendency for females to choose non-technical degrees is frequently influenced by observing their mothers working in non-technical professions [9]. Moreover, educators have the most significant impact on females' career choices, as they guide students throughout their educational journey [9]. Consequently, the low representation of women in the ICT field can be attributed to the lack of encouragement from educators to consider careers in technology [8]. With limited awareness of technical STEM degrees, many women are drawn to fields like health or social sciences, where there is already a larger female presence.
2. **Imposter Syndrome and Computer Anxiety (Cluster 4: Table 3):** Computer anxiety arises from a lack of exposure to technology [21]. It often manifests as impostor syndrome and low self-esteem, both of which are common among women in the ICT field [21]. According to Tahsin, Ahmed, Asad, and Sakib [4], males are typically exposed to computing devices at an earlier age than females, which means they are less likely to experience computer anxiety, having had more time to become familiar with technology [21].

Influential individuality factors represent a set of characteristics that define an individual, including experiences [10]. The following influential individuality factors were identified:

1. **Lack of Role Models (Cluster 1, 2, 4: Table 3):** Role models are crucial in any sector. Tahsin, Ahmed, Asad, and Sakib [4] highlight that female role models are particularly important as they inspire younger women and spark their interest in the ICT field. The visible leadership of women in ICT motivates the younger generation of females [1]. However, the lack of women in leadership positions can discourage those considering an ICT degree [4]. As a result, the current absence of female representation in the ICT field contributes to the lack of interest among younger women [21].

Despite these challenges, women are actively reshaping the ICT industry and driving inclusion through various initiatives. These measures contribute to promoting gender equality:

1. **Mentorship Programs:** Female mentorship plays a pivotal role in increasing the representation of women in the ICT field [20]. Mentorship programs create opportunities for girls to interact with female role models in the industry, which fosters greater interest in ICT careers. These programs offer career guidance, educational opportunities, and peer support to participants [21]. Over the years, the ICT sector has seen a rise in female mentorship initiatives aimed at inspiring and empowering women and girls [3]. For example, the Million Women Mentors program focuses on educating girls and women about STEM careers while providing individualized support [3]. Other notable mentorship organizations include the IEEE Women in Computing Society, Girls Can Code, and Women in Technology [3], [21].
2. **Coding Boot Camps:** Coding boot camps are intensive programs designed to teach fundamental concepts in software development, data science, artificial intelligence, and cybersecurity, typically over a period of three months [7]. These boot camps provide girls and women with valuable coding skills, encouraging them to explore and pursue careers in the technology industry.

The rise of mentorship programs and coding boot camps is helping to attract girls in high school and women seeking to transition into ICT careers. These programs are providing women with the resources and support to overcome barriers and contribute to a more inclusive and diverse ICT field. Through these efforts, women are creating a visible path for change in the industry.

5 Towards a Conceptual Framework for Women to Reshape the ICT Field

The conceptual framework in Figure 3 outlines strategic measures women can take to reshape the ICT field for equal representation and opportunities. The findings of this paper reveal that women face challenges in entering the ICT field, influenced by their environment, which is divided into two key areas: the workplace and the educational environment. This division, illustrated in the framework, aims to provide targeted solutions for the unique challenges in each area. The framework identifies the root causes of these issues and organizes them into construct categories. Figure 3 visually represents the framework, emphasizing the strategic measures women can use as a toolkit to transform the ICT field and promote equal representation for an inclusive community such as Society 5.0.

Fig. 3: Conceptual Framework - strategic measures taken by women in reshaping the ICT field

Table 4 presents a breakdown of strategic measures that women can take to reshape the ICT field. It outlines various actions grouped into specific construct categories. The construct categories applicable to the workplace include inclusive hiring, supportive work environments, and flexible work policies. Additionally, the construct categories relevant to the educational environment are career guidance and technical upskilling.

Table 4: Strategic Measures for Women to Reshape the ICT Field.

These construct categories are explained in more detail:

Measures to be Taken in the Workplace Environment

1. **Inclusive Hiring Practices:** Women are often subjected to gender bias during job interviews, largely due to the male-dominated hiring panels and the use of biased recruitment technologies. To address this, strategic measures should include forming diverse hiring panels and implementing unbiased recruitment technologies to eliminate gender biases in the hiring process.
2. **Supportive Working Environment:** The lack of support in the workplace manifests in several ways. For example, pregnant women in managerial positions are often treated differently from their male counterparts, with their work ethic harshly criticized, which can hinder their chances of receiving salary increases. Additionally, women often face challenges balancing overtime work with household responsibilities, which can lead to perceptions of incompetence and increase the risk of job loss. To address these issues, the following strategic measures can be implemented:
 - a. Companies can provide on-site childcare services for employees working overtime.
 - b. Employers can ensure job security for all employees, particularly those returning from maternity leave.
 - c. Companies should offer additional support for women after maternity leave to help them reintegrate into the workplace.
3. **Flexible Work Policies:** Women often face challenges in achieving work-life balance. To address this, the following strategic measures can be implemented:
 - a. Companies should offer remote work options.
 - b. Flexible working schedules should be provided to help accommodate household responsibilities.
 - c. Overtime work should be voluntary, allowing employees to maintain a healthy work-life balance.

Measures to be Taken in the Education Environment

1. **Career Guidance:** Women and girls often choose to pursue degrees in health sciences and humanities due to limited career guidance and exposure to career opportunities. To increase the number of women and girls interested in studying ICT-related degrees, several strategic measures can be implemented. First, career expos and mentorship programs can provide platforms for exposure to the ICT industry and offer access to career mentors. Additionally, networking events can connect women with a community of other women

already working in the ICT field.

2. **Technical Upskilling:** Women often experience computer anxiety, and coding bootcamps can help bridge the technical gap they face.

6 Conclusion

This paper continues the discourse on the underrepresentation of women in the ICT field and industry. Using a systematic literature review (SLR) of 29 studies, the paper aims to identify and discuss the barriers contributing to this underrepresentation (research question 1). Additionally, it explores ways in which women can take an active role in reshaping the field to foster greater gender inclusion, especially in preparation for future societies such as Society 5.0 (research question 2).

By applying the "Individual Differences Theory of Gender and Information Technology" [10], the barriers to women's participation in the ICT field are categorized into three areas: environmental factors, influential individuality factors, and identity factors. Environmental factors focus on workplace culture, which is often shaped by misogyny and challenges related to work-life balance. Influential individuality factors highlight the lack of mentorship opportunities for women in ICT, while identity factors examine the lack of career guidance and the negative attitudes many women hold, often due to limited exposure to technology.

This paper proposes potential solutions to overcome these barriers, emphasizing the importance of mentorship programs and coding bootcamps as key strategies for increasing women's representation in the field. A conceptual framework is derived from the theoretical framework, focusing on strategic measures that women can take to reshape the ICT field and promote greater inclusion in future societies, where women can contribute equally alongside their male counterparts. The framework emphasizes two environmental dimensions: the workplace and educational settings, advocating for inclusive hiring, supportive work environments, flexible policies, career guidance, and technical upskilling.

In conclusion, addressing the gender representation crisis through awareness and targeted measures can help dismantle the barriers identified in this paper. The solutions proposed in the conceptual framework provide actionable steps to overcome these challenges.

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Comparison and Evaluation of Speech to Text in Italian for Understanding Dementia

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Abstract. Dementia is a neurodegenerative disease characterized by decreased cognitive functions, including memory and problem-solving. Monitoring the progression of dementia is essential to improve quality of life, adapt treatment, avoid potential complications, and help family members to understand what to expect and how to behave. Conventional diagnostic methods are based on questionnaires distributed by doctors and require time-consuming procedures, as the person must travel to the facility. Models based on deep learning techniques, such as large language models (LLMs), are emerging as promising resources to improve the speech-to-text and text-to-speech techniques that can support the diagnosis. These models require considerable computational power, especially for real-time operations.

This work presents a comparative study to identify the best combination of speech-to-text systems and spelling correction for real-time applications on device with an non importan hardware. We evaluate three speech-to-text systems: Whisher Tiny, Whisher Base, and Vosk, along with two spelling correction methods. The systems were trained and tested using a publicly available Italian dataset, called Common Voice dataset. The results shows that Whisher Base outperforms both Whisher Tiny and Vosk. Furthermore, the performance of Whisher, with and without spelling correction, is comparable when background noise levels are low.

Keywords: Speech-to-text Systems Evaluation · spelling correction · Dementia.

1 Introduction

Dementia is a syndrome characterized by a progressive decline in cognitive function across various domains, consequently impairing functional abilities, as defined by the World Health Organization (WHO) [5]. Currently, over 55 million people worldwide are affected by dementia, with more than 60% residing in low-and middle-income countries, and each year, nearly 10 million new cases

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15703961
In Proceedings: Corradini, F.; Hinkelmann, K.; Re, B., Smuts, H., eds. (2025). Proceedings of the 5th Conference Society 5.0 - Co-Existence Between Human Being and Machine Being, Vol. 2. San Benedetto del Tronto, Italy, 25-27 June 2025.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15422355>

are diagnosed [7]. The Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders-5 (DSM-5) lists 13 possible causes of dementia [14]. However, Alzheimer’s disease (AD) is the cause in about 70% of all cases [24], while other causes include Lewy body disease, brain injuries, blood vessel problems, and frontotemporal dementia [6]. Early detection and continuous monitoring of disease progress are crucial, as it enables timely interventions to management of the disease and improve the quality of life for affected individuals, through both pharmacological and non-pharmacological treatment strategies [17]. Moreover, understanding the course of the syndrome helps caregivers and their families cope with changing needs and prepare for future challenges. Questionnaires are widely used in dementia screening and monitoring. The Mini-Mental State Examination (MMSE) is the most widely used tool for diagnosing dementia and is considered the gold standard for cognitive screening. Other screening tools, such as the AD8 [15] and Mini-Cog and Montreal Cognitive Assessment (MoCA) [11], are also used.

Although these methods provide valuable insights, they are time-consuming and often require patients to visit healthcare facilities, which may be inconvenient or burdensome for individuals with mobility issues or those in the later stages of the disease. Automated tools that can monitor the progression of dementia syndrome with the possibility of administering non-pharmacological treatments, such as cognitive training personalized according to one’s level of education and personality, are of fundamental importance. Recent advances in artificial intelligence have introduced new possibilities for supporting the monitoring of dementia syndrome and cognitive training. Different results have been reached in that area. Recent advances in artificial intelligence have introduced new possibilities for supporting the monitoring of dementia syndrome and cognitive training. For example, smartphone apps like Sea Hero Quest assess spatial navigation skills, which are often impaired in early dementia [12]. At the same time, AI models that take wearable device data as input allow us to track physical activity and sleep patterns, potential early indicators of dementia [27]. On the other hand, the new improvement of speech-to-text and text-to-speech technologies via large language models (LLMs) have shown promise in automating and improving diagnostic processes. These models can process and analyze speech in real time, offering potential benefits in clinical settings where rapid assessments are needed. However, the computational power required to run these models, especially in real-time applications, remains challenging, mainly when using devices with limited hardware capabilities.

This paper presents a comparative study aimed at identifying the optimal combination of speech-to-text systems and spelling correction methods for real-time applications on devices with constrained computational resources. We evaluate three widely used speech-to-text systems, i.e., Whisper-tiny, Whisper-Base [23], and Vosk API [1], along with two different spelling correction approaches. To ensure the generalizability of our findings, we train and test the systems using a publicly available Italian dataset, called Common Voice dataset. Our results demonstrate that Whisper-Base outperforms both Whisper-tiny and Vosk in terms of accuracy and efficiency. Additionally, we show that the performance of

Whisper, with and without spelling correction, is comparable when background noise levels are low. Finally, we integrate Whisper into a demo application to evaluate their effectiveness in real-world scenarios, providing a proof of concept for their potential use in dementia monitoring.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: In Section ??, we introduce the basic knowledge related to deep learning models. Section 2 describes the main automatic speech recognition systems, from early-stage approaches to modern methods based on deep learning architectures. Section 3 introduces the performed experiments and the selected toolkit’s main reasons. The paper ends with some conclusions and future works, Section 4.

2 Overview of Automatic Speech Recognition

ASR, or automatic speech recognition, is the technology that recognizes and converts spoken language into text. It is applied in various scenarios, such as voice assistants, media applications, and voice-command systems. ASR has witnessed remarkable progress, revolutionizing human-computer interaction across diverse domains [18, 19]. Nevertheless, this progress has not been uniformly distributed across all languages. Figure 1 shows some recent improvements in speech recognition models from the Google Voice Search app, introduced in 2010, to Whispers, presented in 2023.

Fig. 1. A timeline of some of the significant advances in speech recognition from 2010 to 2023

In the early stages, manual feature extraction and standard approaches such as Gaussian Mixture Models and Hidden Markov Model have been developed and used. These architectures were most suitable for addressing fundamental issues,

as their limitations might complicate large-scale, complex real-world problems. Recently, models such as RNNs and CNNs, as well as Transformers, were applied to ASR with considerable success. ASR models like Wav2Vec, Wav2Vec2, HuBERT, Whisper, and WavLM have significantly improved the accuracy and robustness of ASR systems, paving the way for more efficient and reliable STT transcription technologies.

Wav2Vec Wav2Vec is an end-to-end architecture that utilizes self-supervised learning, combining transformer and convolutional layers [25]. The model employs a multi-layer convolutional feature encoder to transform raw audio waveforms into latent speech representations. These latent representations are input to the network, which is transformer-masked. The self-supervised learning objective is defined by the discrete outputs generated when the transformer network quantizes the continuous representations. These quantized representations are contextualized by the transformer module’s attention blocks, producing a set of discrete contextual representations. The feature encoder consists of seven convolutional blocks with 512 channels. The transformer network consists of 24 blocks, each having 1024 dimensions, 4096 inner dimensions, and a total of 16 attention heads.

DiscreteBERT DiscreteBERT is an adaptation of the BERT architecture designed to process discrete token inputs instead of continuous token embeddings [21]. This modification makes it particularly suitable for handling tokenized inputs from various sources, such as audio or text, where the tokens represent distinct information units. Unlike traditional models that operate in a unidirectional manner (either left-to-right or right-to-left), DiscreteBERT can understand the context in both directions. It uses a transformer architecture that employs self-attention mechanisms to assess the importance of each token within the sequence. Additionally, DiscreteBERT is trained using Masked Language Modeling (MLM), where the model learns to predict randomly masked tokens in the input sequence, improving its ability to capture and understand the broader context of the language.

Whisper. Whisper is a model developed by OpenAI based on integrating supervised and self-supervised learning techniques [23]. It is trained on a diverse dataset of 680,000 hours of multilingual and multitask supervised data, allowing it to learn robust representations from noisy audio. This approach performs well in transcribing speech accurately across a variety of languages and tasks, making it ideal for real-world applications. Whisper excels in challenging scenarios, improving speech recognition even in difficult conditions. Additionally, it is capable of performing multiple speech-related tasks effectively.

WavLM WavLM is an ASR model developed by researchers that integrates concepts from ASR and language modelling [13]. The model extends the self-supervised learning framework to language modelling for speech, with the goal of improving the contextual understanding of spoken language. By pre-training on

large-scale, unlabeled speech corpora, WavLM learns contextual representations that capture the underlying semantics of spoken language. This approach eliminates the need for text transcriptions during pre-training, making the model highly scalable and applicable to a wide range of languages and dialects. Its performance remains competitive across various ASR tasks, demonstrating its effectiveness in capturing the complexities of spoken language in real-world scenarios. Notably, WavLM extends self-supervised learning to language modelling by directly extracting contextual information from raw audio signals. At the same time, its scalability allows it to handle large-scale datasets, further contributing to its strong performance.

Kaldi and Vosk Kaldi and Vosk are powerful speech recognition toolkits with distinctive features and capabilities that address various user needs. Kaldi is known for its flexibility, which allows for extensive customization of speech recognition systems and supports some models. Its comprehensive toolchain includes feature extraction, training, and decoding. Additionally, Kaldi benefits from a robust community and extensive documentation, aiding users in troubleshooting and system improvement. Based on Kaldi, Vosk is designed to be lightweight and efficient. Therefore, it can be easily integrated into mobile and embedded applications, such as on devices with limited resources like the Raspberry Pi. Vosk stands out for its multilingual support, making it especially useful for applications targeting diverse user groups. It uses a pre-trained model and allows us to train the custom model. Its capability for real-time speech recognition with low-latency responses makes it ideal for interactive applications.

2.1 Dataset

The performance of ASR systems depend on high-quality, annotated speech datasets for effective training and testing. Datasets such as the Italian Spontaneous Dialogue Dataset [2] and the Common Voice project [3] provide a wide range of authentic speech samples, allowing ASR models to manage spontaneous speech, regional accents, and background noise. These resources are valuable for advancing voice assistants, automated transcription services, and accessibility tools tailored for Italian speakers.

Common Voice Mozilla’s Common Voice dataset is an open-source initiative [3]. It allows users to contribute by either recording texts or helping to verify if an audio recording matches its transcription. To date, the project has collected 18.6k hours of data across multiple languages, with 14.1k hours validated. The platform currently offers speech datasets in 112 languages and is continually updated. The information provided above is accurate as of May 2022.

Italian Spontaneous Dialogue Dataset The Italian (Italy) Spontaneous Dialogue Telephony speech dataset contains dialogues on over 20 topics. It includes transcriptions of 676 native speakers with text content, speaker ID, gender, age, and

other attributes. The dataset covers a wide range of geographic regions, improving model performance in real-world, complex tasks. The dataset ensures full compliance with data protection regulations and privacy standards, maintaining user privacy and legal rights throughout the collection, storage, and usage.

2.2 Evaluation criteria in ASR

Different metrics have been defined to evaluate the effectiveness and suitability of ASR techniques. In addition to classic metrics such as accuracy, F1-score, recall, precision, and specificity, specific metrics for ASR have also been established, including word error rate (WER), Word Recognition Rate (WRR), and Character error rate (CER) [20]. WER determines the ratio of incorrectly recognized words to the overall number of processed words, as follows

$$WER = \frac{S + D + I}{N} \quad (1)$$

Where I, D, S, H, and N denote the number of insertions, deletions, substitutions, hits, and input words, respectively. WRR, also known as the Word Accuracy Rate, is a variant of the WER used to measure the efficiency of an ASR. The metric is computed as follows

$$WRR = \frac{N - S - D - I}{N} = \frac{H - I}{N} \quad (2)$$

$H = N - (S + D)$ is the number of correctly predicted words. The CER follows the same evaluation principle, except that it measures errors in characters rather than words. The CER value can be determined using the equation below.

$$CER = \frac{S + D + I}{N} \quad (3)$$

Where S , D , and C denote the number of substitutions, insertions, deletions, and correct characters, respectively. N is the total number of characters in the source.

3 Experiments

We conducted experiments on the Common Voice dataset, focusing exclusively on the Italian language, to identify the optimal combination of ASR systems and spelling correction methods for real-time applications on devices with constrained computational resources. We selected Whisper and Vosk models and compared their performances before and after fine-tuning, which exploits the Italian part of the Common Voice dataset. The obtained results are reported in the Table 1. In particular, we fine-tuned the Whisper Base model with 74 million parameters, the Whisper Tiny model with 39 million parameters and Vosk. Whisper utilizes a Transformer architecture for its encoder and decoder, which

share an identical structural setup. In the Whisper Base and Tiny versions, the encoder and decoder consist of 16 and 6 Transformer blocks, respectively. Additionally, the convolutional layers at the encoder’s front end were initialized randomly, while the encoder’s CTC projection layer was initialized with weights from the word embeddings used in the decoder. During fine-tuning, all model parameters were updated using gradients. We set the batch size to 8 with a gradient accumulation of 4 to have an effective batch of 32 per step and the learning rate to $2.5e-05$, which is the one advised for fine-tuning this model with a warm-up linear learning rate scheduler that included 240 warm-up steps. The fine-tuning process consists of 5 epochs, and the final evaluation was based on the average of the model checkpoints from the epochs.

Vosk, suitable for working in devices with limited computational capacities, utilizes an architecture based on deep learning models. It combines deep neural networks, Deep Neural Network Hidden Markov Models (DNN-HMM) and RNN-LM, and Mel-frequency Cepstral Coefficients (MFCC) as an acoustic model based on Kaldi to extract features that are the input of DNN-HMM that associates MFCC to spoken language. After that, a n-gram language model combined with RNN-LM predicts the probability of a word based on the context. The fine-tuning process of a Vosk model is time-consuming. It requires updating the language model and using Kaldi scripts to recreate the acoustic model based on the dataset’s audio. For this reason, Vosk is only considered as a baseline for a small and fast model, suitable for devices with limited computational power, as the results obtained from the model were acceptable.

Model	WER	CER	Fine-Tune	WER(Fine-Tuned)	CER(Fine-Tuned)
Vosk-Small-It	40%		No	-	-
Whisper-Tiny	62%	24%	Yes	28.3%	10.08%
Whisper-Base	45%	16%	Yes	21.7%	7.28%

Table 1. Difference between the baseline and fine-tuned models

By observing the result reported in Table 1, we observe that the Whisper-Base outperforms the others. The Vosk-Small-It model, which serves as a baseline for low-resource devices, achieved a Word Error Rate (WER) of 40%. In contrast, the Whisper-Tiny model initially showed a higher WER of 62%, indicating a relatively poor performance for general ASR tasks. However, after finetuning, the Whisper-Tiny model significantly reduced WER, improving to 28.3%. Similarly, the Character Error Rate (CER) also improved to 10.08%. These results suggest that finetuning Whisper-Tiny on the Italian data substantially enhances its recognition capabilities, making it a viable option for tasks requiring higher accuracy. The Whisper-Base model demonstrated a WER of 45% in its baseline form, which was already an improvement compared to performance without the finetuning of Whisper-Tiny. After finetuning, Whisper-Base achieved a WER of 21.7%, the best performance among the models tested. The CER also showed a notable improvement, reaching 7.28%. The finetuning process signifi-

cantly improves the performance of Whisper models, especially Whisper-Base, which shows the most promising results for high-accuracy transcription tasks.

4 Conclusion and Future Works

In this paper, we conducted a comparative study to understand the best ASR systems for real-time applications on devices with constrained computational resources. We evaluated three widely used ASR systems: Whisher-tiny, Whisher-base, and Vosk API in Italian. Although significant progress has been made in recent years in ASR models, this progress has not been uniformly distributed across all languages, as the availability and quality of datasets heavily influence it. To understand such ASR systems for real-time applications, we fine-tuned the three pre-trained models using a public Italian dataset called the Common Voice dataset. The performances of the three models are comparable to those in the literature for English, the most commonly used language.

In future works, we consider other models, such as WavLM [13], SeamlessM4T [8] and DistilWhisper [16]. Moreover, we also intend to consider other datasets, such as the Italian Spontaneous Dialogue Dataset and Speech DatCar database [4], to study the robustness of such methods in noisy environments. To address the current limitations of spoken Italian datasets, we intend to develop a new dataset that expands demographic and linguistic diversity, including under-represented dialects, minority languages, and diverse speaker groups. Another challenge is to apply such systems to other scopes, like emotion recognition or stress detections from speech, to integrate different approaches based on analysis of wearable sensors data like proposed in [22, 26] Another challenging aspect is to extend the approach proposed in [10, 9] for programming Graph Neural Networks to transformers and DNN-HMMs in the ASR applicative scenarios.

Acknowledgments. This work has been funded by the European Union - NextGenerationEU under the Italian Ministry of University and Research (MUR) National Innovation Ecosystem grant ECS00000041 - VITALITY - CUP J13C22000430001.

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Neo Vernacular Kitchen: A Sustainable and Adaptive Housing Module Integrating Parametric Simulations and Real-Scale Prototyping

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Abstract. The Neo-Vernacular Kitchen (NVK) is a temporary housing prototype developed as part of WP4 of SPOKE 5 of the VITALITY project. It explores how vernacular architectural principles can be reinterpreted through digital modelling, environmental simulation and transdisciplinary design approaches to formulate a self-sufficient and climate-sensitive housing system. The project synthesises passive environmental strategies with computational tools to optimise both energy efficiency and indoor environmental quality. At the heart of the design is a variable thermal transmittance wall, designed to modulate heat exchange in response to external climatic conditions, and a home garden that facilitates on-site food production and enhances ecological resilience.

The architectural layout prefabricated cross-laminated timber (CLT) structure and use of bio-based materials contribute to the creation of an environmentally sustainable and contextually adaptable housing model. The research uses a dual methodological framework: predictive simulations using Ladybug/Honeybee and EnergyPlus guide the iterative development of the design, while empirical data collected through a full-scale prototype provides real-world validation. A digital twin, continuously updated by real-time sensor feedback, enables behavioural optimisation, predictive maintenance and dynamic recalibration of the system. NVK seeks to challenge conventional, static and resource-intensive building paradigms. It proposes a responsive architectural system capable of adapting to both user interaction and environmental variability. Its design also allows NVK to be considered both as a stand-alone emergency shelter module and as a comfort-generating living module within a housing complex.

By integrating traditional architectural intelligence with advanced simulation workflows and continuous in-situ monitoring, NVK offers a methodological framework that combines digital technologies and ecological adaptability.

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15704059

In Proceedings: Corradini, F.; Hinkelmann, K.; Re, B., Smuts, H., eds. (2025). Proceedings of the 5th Conference Society 5.0 - Co-Existence Between Human Being and Machine Being, Vol. 2. San Benedetto del Tronto, Italy, 25-27 June 2025.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15422355>

Keywords: Adaptive design, Digital simulation, Transdisciplinary approach

1 Introduction

In architecture, the term “vernacular” describes building practices shaped by local environmental, cultural, and material conditions, developed over time through collective knowledge rather than codified design [1]. As demonstrated in studies such as [2], vernacular typologies—particularly in Mediterranean and arid climates—exhibit high thermal performance, largely due to passive design strategies like thermal mass and natural ventilation. The main strategies observed in Mediterranean vernacular architecture [3] include compact urban and rural layouts, thick masonry walls, optimal orientation of building volumes and openings, spatial organization around internal courtyards, the use of semi-open spaces, external shutters, lightweight shading devices such as pergolas, and integrated vegetation. Research conducted on traditional Cypriot architecture highlights its capacity to adapt to diverse climatic zones across the island. A fundamental feature is the use of local materials with high thermal mass, which contributes to passive thermal regulation. As demonstrated in southern Italy, the thermal inertia of the envelope plays a key role in maintaining stable indoor temperatures, allowing adequate comfort with minimal energy input during colder periods [4].

The Neo-Vernacular Kitchen (NVK), developed within WP4 of SPOKE 5 of the VITALITY project,—specifically within Spoke 5, “Environmental, Economic, and Social Sustainability of Living and Working Environments”—and developed as part of Output 4.1 “Innovative Design Methods for Eco-Sustainability of Products for the Living Environments”, reinterprets these principles through computational modelling, environmental simulation, and transdisciplinary design [5]. It investigates how architectural knowledge embedded in traditional forms can inform low-energy, self-sufficient living systems responsive to climate variability [2], [3].

The main features of the project include a variable thermal transmittance wall (VTTW), which can influence the thermal stability of the external wall instead of traditional masonry, and a home cultivator (HC), which promotes on-site food production and circular metabolic flows. The prefabricated CLT structure and the integration of natural materials improve the sustainability and replicability of the prototype.

The research employs a dual methodology: predictive simulations using tools such as Ladybug, Honeybee, and EnergyPlus guide early-stage design, while a full-scale prototype allows for in-situ testing. A continuously updated digital twin, fed by real-time environmental and behavioural data, enables adaptive calibration, predictive maintenance, and user-involved control [6].

NVK challenges conventional static housing models by proposing a performative architecture that evolves through user interaction and environmental feedback. It aligns with contemporary posthumanist theories, such as Harman and Morton’s concept of hyperobjects and Object-Oriented Ontology (OOO), which frame buildings and their components as active agents in ecological systems [7], [8]. By merging vernacular intelligence, ecological sensitivity, and digital innovation, NVK establishes a methodological framework for a dynamic and context-aware architecture, where sustainability is treated not as a fixed metric, but as a continuously negotiated performance.

2 Digital & Green Transition in Contemporary Architecture

The accelerating shift towards sustainable and high-performance buildings has prompted architectural research to embrace a more holistic paradigm—one that synthesises vernacular intelligence with digital innovation. The Neo-Vernacular Kitchen (NVK) is situated within this evolving framework, proposing a housing model that reinterprets traditional construction principles through computational methodologies, thus enabling a form of architecture that is both culturally grounded and technologically responsive [9].

The NVK investigates how vernacular passive environmental strategies—derived from local climatic, material, and cultural contexts—can be systematically re-integrated into contemporary zero-energy architectural frameworks. Moving beyond the replication of historical aesthetics, the research isolates the performative logic of traditional typologies, emphasizing the functional value of thermal inertia, optimal solar orientation, and passive ventilation systems. These strategies, historically refined through empirical adaptation, are reframed as foundational principles for regenerative and resource-efficient design, aligning with Banham’s interpretation of pre-industrial architecture as environmentally attuned systems. [10] [11].

The Mediterranean trullo is a paradigmatic example. With its thick dry-stone walls, vaulted conical roof and strategically placed openings, the trullo embodies a passive climate control strategy that has endured over time. Numerical simulations without HVAC systems show that the Trullo maintains comfortable internal conditions in summer without mechanical cooling, thanks to its thermal mass and natural ventilation linked to the shape of the structure [12]. The aim is to reproduce an innovative spatial device that can offer the same thermal stability, using the wooden mass of CLT (Cross Laminated Timber) combined with a responsive and dynamic plant support system distributed throughout the wall and with low energy consumption. This reinterpretation is made possible by parametric tools and energy simulation software, which allow performance variables to be tested and optimised in a predictive manner]. This transition—from historically passive systems to intelligent, adaptive frameworks—demands a transdisciplinary research culture. In the NVK, traditional passive strategies are augmented through technological innovations such as the Variable Thermal Transmittance Wall, which modulates thermal behavior in real time. This component reflects a broader architectural shift from fixed energy-saving features to dynamic systems that respond to changing environmental inputs [13] [14].

The philosophical foundation of this approach is informed by Object-Oriented Ontology (OOO), which decentralises non-human actors—materials, systems, environments—as co-agents in architectural performance [7]. Morton’s notion of extends this understanding, portraying systems such as climate as temporally and spatially distributed entities beyond full human apprehension [8] [15]. Within this ontological framework, the NVK emerges not as an object in space, but as a relational and performative interface.

In rejecting formal mimicry and embracing operative principles, the NVK exemplifies how traditional knowledge can be retranslated through computational processes. Real-time simulation, bio-integrated systems, and data-informed adaptability converge to form a design model in which sustainability is not a static attribute but a condition in

flux—shaped by feedback, transformation, and interdependence among human and non-human agents. This dynamic understanding of performance challenges conventional sustainability metrics, proposing instead a system that evolves in dialogue with its users and its environment.

3 The Neo-Vernacular Kitchen System: Structure and Components

3.1 Beyond Disciplines: The Transdisciplinary Synthesis of NVK

The Neo-Vernacular Kitchen (NVK) emerges as the outcome of a transdisciplinary design process that integrates expertise from architecture, engineering, agronomy, and computational design. Developed within WP4 of Spoke 5 of the VITALITY project, the NVK is not merely a building prototype but a systemic architectural organism in which material, technological, and ecological components operate in synergy.

The collaboration between institutions has played a critical role in shaping the NVK's architecture. The University of Camerino contributed to the development of the technological and environmental design approach, while digital modelling and simulation systems were supported by its Department of Computer Science. The Polytechnic University of Marche was instrumental in developing parametric tools and sustainable product design methods, particularly in integrating industrial design methodologies with environmental control strategies. The Home Cultivator System (HCS)—a defining element of NVK—was developed in conjunction with agronomic specialists, facilitating the integration of vertical indoor agriculture into the architectural envelope. The University of Perugia contributed key innovations in the design of the Variable Thermal Transmittance Wall, a system that bridges passive thermoregulation strategies and real-time climate responsiveness.

In this sense, NVK is not merely a housing prototype but a systemic integration of material, digital, and ecological processes. Each component—from construction materials to interactive environmental controls—functions as part of a holistic architectural organism. This systematisation of good practices allows researchers to quantify and validate both the isolated performance of each subsystem and the overall contribution of NVK as an integrated, self-sufficient entity. While this integrated perspective enhances the capacity to address complex environmental and spatial challenges, transdisciplinary approaches remain the subject of ongoing debate. They are often contested and not yet fully embedded in mainstream research and practice, despite being increasingly recognized as essential tools for interpreting and engaging with the shifting ontologies of contemporary ecological phenomena [16] [17].

3.2 Structure and Architectural Envelope

The Neo-Vernacular Kitchen (NVK) presents a compact and highly integrated spatial layout, occupying a square footprint of 3.9 x 3.9 meters and reaching a total height of 4.50 meters. The volumetric configuration is defined by a truncated pyramidal roof,

which begins at 2.10 meters and culminates in a central clerestory skylight, enhancing both natural ventilation and zenithal illumination (see Fig.1). This geometry, inspired by traditional rural annexes and trulli, reinforces a context-sensitive yet simplified architectural language.

Fig. 1. NVK plans: roof plan (left), plan (center) and 3d view.

The internal environment combines cooking and living functions in a continuous, flexible space. The entire structure is elevated on a modular timber platform that rests on prefabricated footings, allowing for minimal site impact and integrating the technological systems below the floor level. The platform's aluminum substructure is clad in wooden decking panels, enhancing the project's commitment to sustainability and reversibility.

The primary load-bearing system consists of 12 cm cross-laminated timber (CLT) panels, prefabricated for efficient assembly. Approximately 56 m² of vertical surfaces and 15 m² of flooring are covered by these panels, ensuring structural stability and thermal mass. Externally, the envelope is insulated with 6 cm of expanded cork, a breathable, renewable material that supports both thermal inertia and acoustic performance. A three-coat lime-based plaster, applied over the insulation, ensures fire resistance and moisture control while evoking Mediterranean vernacular aesthetics with its warm reddish hue. Internally, lime-based plaster provides continuity, contributing to a healthy and breathable indoor environment.

A radiant heating system is embedded within the internal lime finish of the vertical walls, forming part of the Variable Thermal Transmittance Wall strategy. Polypropylene pipes extend over 135 linear meters across approximately 30 m² of surface, transforming the CLT panels into active thermal regulators by leveraging their mass to stabilize indoor temperatures efficiently.

The fenestration strategy prioritizes energy performance. A glazed entrance door (90 x 205 cm) ensures accessibility and daylight, while a large wooden-framed aperture accommodates the integrated home cultivator system—described in Section 3.4—which links food production with interior comfort and ecological design principles [19]. The clerestory skylight (90 x 90 cm), placed at the apex of the roof, directs natural light into the heart of the space, reinforcing both thermal gain and visual comfort.

Sectional drawings illustrate the building's material layering, from the prefabricated piers and raised platform to the insulated CLT walls and skylight. The total wall stratigraphy reaches 30 cm, evidencing the project's focus on performance and envelope optimization.

The elevations reveal a compact, monolithic volume where solid-to-void ratios favor enclosure and insulation. Openings are deliberately limited and strategically placed to preserve energy efficiency and formal clarity. The glazed main façade provides daylight and cross-ventilation, while the other façades remain largely opaque, punctuated only by shallow recesses that accentuate the building's visual simplicity and vernacular references.

3.3 Variable Thermal Transmittance Wall: An Adaptive System for Energy Comfort

The Variable Thermal Transmittance Wall system integrates a network of fluid-carrying pipes within standard wall constructions (horizontal, vertical, or oblique) of any material. A circulating heat transfer fluid, driven by a pump, facilitates heat exchange through the wall's thickness, enabling transfer from interior to exterior and vice versa. The system control relies on a differential temperature strategy: outdoor and indoor temperature sensors (T_i and T_e) guide pump activation (see Fig.2).

Fig. 2. The Variable Thermal Transmittance wall principle

During winter, effective wall insulation typically prevents operation. However, in transitional seasons, solar radiation can heat the exterior wall, allowing the fluid to efficiently transport this heat indoors. Conversely, during warm periods when outdoor temperatures fall below the indoor thermal comfort setpoint, especially at night, the system enhances heat dissipation from the interior to the exterior by reducing the wall's effective thermal resistance and thermal mass. The system incorporates a control unit that processes temperature data and manages pump operation. The pipe-embedding layers are built from high thermal conductivity materials (e.g., plasterboard, cement), while the core layers can be of any suitable material. Temperature sensors are strategically placed within the high-conductivity layers, avoiding thermal bridges and direct heat sources. The wall can be segmented into independently controlled fluid circuits. Pipes are typically made of plastic, copper, or iron, similar to radiant panel materials, and the

heat transfer fluid is water-based, potentially with glycol additives (10-40% concentration) for freeze protection, adjusted to the local climate [18].

3.4 Home Cultivator: From Traditional Windows to Integrated Biological Systems

Domestic vertical farming is a new frontier for urban agriculture. This technology that was built for space will likely be the home appliances of the kitchens of the future. The original idea, developed in the 90s by researchers from the North American Space Agency (NASA) to support long space missions and travels, has been translated first into a new industry with the appearance of the first plant factories in the 2010 [19], followed then by the “container farms”, and lately by relatively small size devices that could fit both in domestic environment and in the hospitality sector.

The basic principle of these devices is to cultivate plants in an indoor environment in stacked layers using artificial lights. In this fully controlled environment where water, light, nutrients, oxygen, and carbon dioxide are opportunely supplied, various vegetables could be grown. Leafy greens, aromatic plants, and edible flowers could be grown up to different stages ranging from seed sprouts and microgreens to baby leaves and full-grown crops.

Some of the most important and best features of these appliances can be summarized by the fact that these devices can produce high quality vegetables productions with characteristics of incommensurable freshness and taste and include high nutritive values as well. These products are real zero kilometers, since they are produced directly in the place of consumption. This could reduce the carbon footprint related to the transport of these vegetables; this impact nowadays could be very high if these products are coming out of season from the other hemisphere. It could be reduced also the food waste by reducing the large amount of food that becomes unsaleable before being on the shelf due to longer storage time and transport. These products are also considered real pesticide free, being grown in absence of any chemical treatments by choice thanks to the reduced risks of pathogens infections due to the protected environment.

Integrating these devices into the domestic environment can introduce an alternative agricultural production system able to contribute to food production in situations of climatic stress that could occur temporarily, or permanently such as in extreme environments. In this sense it could be only one of the potential solutions to cope with future food security challenges.

These appliances may have positive effects on both human wellbeing and on environmental health. They could introduce potentially relevant air quality improvements inside the domestic environment. This technology is seen as a water use efficient technology and could be considered also as a viable alternative to land consumption in certain densely urbanized areas.

However, it should be noted that these systems could have a significant impact on the carbon footprints due to high energy consumption, if not properly managed, and unless the required energy is mainly or entirely derived from renewable resources that possibly could be auto produced in the domestic environment.

New technologies and innovations have been integrated in this new generation of domestic appliances that could help in reducing some of the drawbacks of the actual

devices and that could promote both the rational use of scarce resources and a more sustainable circular economy.

These new devices proposed are challenging the way the indoor environment will be conceived and perceived in the next future and we think that the integration into the NVK could make an important contribution for many reasons, some of them already mentioned above.

4 Predictive Simulations in NVK Design

4.1 Objectives and evaluation criteria of the simulation process

The evaluation of the Neo-Vernacular Kitchen (NVK) relies on two complementary simulation environments, aimed at cross-verifying modeling approaches using data from the full-scale prototype [20]. The first environment, developed in Rhino/Grasshopper with Ladybug, Honeybee-Radiance, and Honeybee-Energy, enables detailed analysis of solar radiation, daylight, and passive gains through a parametric modeling approach. However, it lacks precision in simulating transient heat transfer and dynamic energy demand. The second environment, based on EnergyPlus and OpenStudio (integrated into SketchUp), offers deeper insights into internal gains, thermal mass, and ventilation through time-based simulation. A key feature of the NVK is the variable thermal transmittance wall, designed to dynamically respond to external climate conditions, optimizing heat flow for seasonal comfort and ensuring the thermal stability of the wall.

To enhance simulation reliability, a customized EPW weather file based on the "Representative Monthly Day" methodology was employed. These representative days condense monthly average climatic parameters (solar radiation, temperature, humidity, wind speed, etc.), reducing computational effort and supporting simplified design simulations [20]. Widely used in scientific contexts, representative days offer consistent performance results and are easier to construct than full climate datasets, making them suitable for iterative comparisons based on real conditions of a real day. Cross-validation between both environments ensures a more robust evaluation. Rhino/Grasshopper is most effective during early design exploration, while EnergyPlus provides deeper energy and comfort assessments. Empirical data from NVK's physical monitoring—operative temperatures, solar gains, and ventilation—will validate simulation outputs. This iterative feedback loop supports a performance-driven design approach where simulations inform construction choices [21][22].

4.2 Methodologies and Tools for Environmental Simulations: Environmental Simulation in Rhinoceros 7 with Ladybug and Honeybee.

The NVK CAD model was implemented in Rhinoceros 7, using Ladybug, Honeybee-Radiance, and Honeybee-Energy plug-ins. Simulations were fundamental in defining the thermal "core" of the structure, designed for stable interior comfort and potential emergency use.

Simulations employed the EPW climate file for San Benedetto del Tronto, limited to the 5:00–22:00 interval and analyzed for North and South orientations to reduce computation time. Ladybug tools calculated direct sunlight hours, incident radiation and irradiance, and shading effectiveness on building surfaces.

Honeybee refined the model, simulating indoor solar exposure, cumulative annual irradiance, and operative temperature distributions. A basic HVAC system was implemented to maintain interior temperatures between 13 °C and 21 °C. Material characterization—absent in Ladybug—was handled in Honeybee: transparent components featured $U = 1.5 \text{ W/m}^2\text{K}$, $\text{SHGC} = 0.5$, $\text{VT} = 0.6$; default software values were used for opaque elements.

Natural lighting was assessed using the “Daylight Autonomy” tool, and surface temperature distributions were visualized through “Color Faces” and “Color Rooms,” offering a comprehensive picture of the NVK’s thermal behavior

4.3 Energy Modelling and Dynamic Simulation Workflow in EnergyPlus.

Dynamic thermal simulations were conducted in EnergyPlus to assess NVK’s energy demand and comfort performance [20]. The geometry was modeled in SketchUp with OpenStudio, enabling the development of a multi-zone energy model aligned with the NVK’s internal layout. This was exported to EnergyPlus, where material properties (U -values, thermal mass, solar absorptance) were assigned for realistic heat transfer simulation. Simulations incorporated the representative day EPW file [21], capturing typical local conditions for San Benedetto del Tronto. Glazing properties and shading systems were included to evaluate solar gain, daylight, and adaptive fenestration strategies for comfort and energy efficiency. The building was modeled as a single thermal zone with internal loads (occupants, lighting, appliances), and airflow modeled based on permeability and wind exposure. Key outputs included operative temperatures, solar radiation, daylight availability, and natural ventilation effectiveness.

EnergyPlus supports a feedback-driven design process, where results guide material and technological decisions. Empirical data from the constructed prototype will further validate and refine the simulations. While computationally robust, model predictions may diverge from real-world performance due to construction-phase variabilities [22] [23]

5 From Virtual Model to Physical Prototype: Validation Through Digital Twin

The Neo-Vernacular Kitchen (NVK) represents not only a digitally informed housing prototype but also a systemic model capable of adaptation, replication, and real-world application. As the project transitions from computational design to physical implementation, it initiates a critical validation phase through full-scale prototyping and empirical monitoring. The prototype, currently under preparation for construction at the University of Camerino’s San Benedetto del Tronto campus, will be installed in a site selected for its climatic diversity and contextual relevance. This testing ground provides an opportunity to assess the NVK’s capacity to perform under dynamic environmental conditions and to confirm the predictive accuracy of the simulations outlined in previous phases.

The construction process—based on prefabricated CLT panels, modular footings, and integrated passive-active systems—serves as a means of verifying the feasibility and replicability of the design logic. The prototype is conceived as both a demonstrative artefact and a functional living unit, intended to host a dense array of sensors and data collection systems.

These will record operative temperatures, solar exposure, humidity levels, and airflow patterns, offering a robust dataset for comparing projected and actual performance. The Variable Thermal Transmittance Wall will undergo thermal response assessment to verify its ability to regulate comfort through passive and semi-active modulation. Likewise, the integrated home cultivator system will be evaluated for its contribution to microclimatic regulation and food self-sufficiency, underlining the NVK's ambition to combine ecological intelligence with daily living.

A key feature of the validation strategy is the integration of a digital twin—an evolving virtual counterpart that mirrors the physical prototype by receiving continuous sensor input. This two-way interaction enables not only real-time behavioral analysis but also adaptive recalibration of system parameters. Through this feedback loop, the NVK becomes a dynamic, learning environment capable of predictive maintenance and energy optimization, aligning with emerging research in smart building analytics and high-resolution environmental monitoring [24]. Moreover, this approach facilitates long-term performance tracking, ensuring that the project remains responsive to both climatic and user-specific variables over time.

The digital twin architecture also plays a crucial role in enabling scalability. By capturing a range of environmental responses and occupant interactions, the system can inform site-specific variations of the NVK model. Parametric tools allow design elements—such as material layers, solar strategies, and energy systems—to be recalibrated based on diverse climatic inputs, enabling broader deployment scenarios from dense urban contexts to rural or off-grid environments. These adaptive potentials are closely tied to the concept of the Urban Digital Twin, which provides a framework for sustainable urban planning and multi-scalar design strategies [25] [26].

In this way, the NVK moves beyond its role as a one-off prototype. It becomes a methodological platform for architectural innovation—merging digital modelling, ecological awareness, and human-centered adaptability. By embedding transdisciplinary knowledge into a reproducible framework, the project offers a compelling model for future living systems that are responsive, data-informed, and environmentally grounded. This integrated approach challenges conventional architectural paradigms by positioning buildings not as fixed objects, but as interactive and evolving agents within a broader ecological and technological continuum.

6 Conclusions

The Neo-Vernacular Kitchen (NVK) demonstrates the potential of integrating vernacular architectural intelligence with advanced computational tools to address pressing environmental, social, and technological challenges in contemporary housing. As a modular and adaptive prototype, the NVK exemplifies a systemic design approach grounded in transdisciplinary collaboration, bridging architecture, agronomy, environmental engineering, and digital simulation.

While performance results are still under development and empirical data from the physical prototype are currently being processed, this article primarily aimed to highlight an innovative transdisciplinary methodology for architectural experimentation in sustainable living systems. The methodological framework—based on predictive simulations, full-scale prototyping, and digital twin integration—offers a robust foundation for iterative design and future validation.

The incorporation of features such as the Variable Thermal Transmittance Wall and the Home Cultivator System shows how passive design strategies can be reinterpreted through digital workflows to enhance resilience, comfort, and sustainability. The NVK challenges static architectural paradigms by framing the building as an active agent within a broader ecological system. The implementation of a digital twin further strengthens this paradigm, enabling real-time monitoring, adaptive calibration, and predictive maintenance.

Ultimately, the NVK serves as a methodological platform for future research and design innovation, where tradition and technology converge to form responsive, data-informed, and ecologically attuned living systems. Its replicability and adaptability mark it as a forward-looking model within the evolving discourse of regenerative architecture and sustainable urban development.

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Making Decisions about Privacy in Tertiary Education Recommendation Systems in South Africa: Privacy Calculus in Action

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Abstract. Recommender Systems (RS) play a crucial role in managing information overload, particularly in fields such as education, where decisions have significant and long-term implications. This study investigates the impact of System Privacy Concerns constructs on privacy calculus and information disclosure decisions in a tertiary education setting within the South African context. We employ the Design Science Research (DSR) approach and mixed methods to enhance a model that integrates privacy calculus theory with a user-centric RS evaluation framework. Results from three iterative studies involving 719 university students indicate that System Privacy Concerns (SPC) influence RS Perceived Recommendation Quality (PRQ), Perceived System Usefulness (PSU), Overall Trust in the Recommender System (OTRS), and Interaction (INT). These findings highlight the delicate balance between user privacy concerns and the need for accurate, context-aware recommendations. This research provides a deeper understanding of privacy-sensitive RS design, offering developers and tertiary institutions valuable insights into students' privacy-related decision-making processes when using educational RS.

Keywords: Recommender Systems, User Privacy, Privacy calculus

1 Introduction

Recommender systems (RS) algorithms employ innovative methods to match students' interests and abilities with relevant courses, thereby reducing the likelihood of misguided choices and frustration by analysing large datasets to provide personalised recommendations that assist students in making informed decisions [1, 2]. RS unlocks focused, data-driven choices that boost student performance and retention by navigating large course handbooks and narrowing down alternatives based on individual preferences and needs [2]. As a result of the information overload problem in technologies, users find it more challenging to discover the correct information at the right moment, and RS have developed as a contributor towards solving this problem [3]. One of RS's primary purposes is to assist users in filtering and easily finding information in large databases [4]. As users struggle with the paradox of choice, where too many options lead to inefficient decision-making, RSs have proved to be helpful

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15704126
In Proceedings: Corradini, F.; Hinkelmann, K.; Re, B., Smuts, H., eds. (2025). Proceedings of the 5th Conference Society 5.0 - Co-Existence Between Human Being and Machine Being, Vol. 2. San Benedetto del Tronto, Italy, 25-27 June 2025.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15422355>

for users in decision-making [5]. RS helps manage the problem of information overload by assisting users in making informed choices based on their personal data [6]. In the education domain, particularly in systems that recommend tertiary institutions and qualifications, students' choices driven by RS have long-term implications for their educational outcomes and career trajectories. Therefore, for RS to provide meaningful recommendations, users are required to provide sufficient personal and often sensitive, confidential data (e.g., biographical information, academic performance, household income) in real-life settings, ensuring accurate and context-aware recommendations. Studies on privacy reveal that many users are uneasy about sharing demographic information and have a negative perception of being monitored to collect contextual information [7].

The interaction between the users and RS for quality recommendations could drive social good in the education domain towards an equitable future in South Africa, however, this type of interaction necessitates careful engagement with ethical issues, such as data privacy, which arise alongside education RS innovations. This study aims to enhance the model proposed in Knijnenburg and Kobsa's (2013), addressing the limitations of the paper concerning behaviours related to privacy within a specific domain, education. This study conducts a user experiment in a real-life setting, rather than a lab experiment based on RS mock-ups.

This study was inspired by the unforeseen and evolving relationships identified in a related and ongoing evaluation study of education RS quality. The researchers observed several significant relationships associated with students' system privacy concerns during the initial data collection and analysis of the study iterations. The unexpected attitude of students towards their data privacy, alongside their lack of concern about system privacy when using an educational RS that benefitted them positively, prompted an observation and treatment of privacy concerns, which were explored in subsequent data collection iterations and analyses. Through this study, we attempt to answer the question: How do system privacy concerns mediate the processes behind users' privacy calculus and influence their information disclosure decisions in tertiary education RS? This study aims to extend the privacy decision-making model in [7], specifically within tertiary education RS, and address its limitations regarding real-life application and domain specificity. To answer the main research question, the DSR iterative approach was employed to construct a model that investigates the relationship between various constructs and SPC, aiming to contribute to an improved model that integrates privacy calculus theory and the RS user studies framework for RS developers and institutions.

2 Related work

2.1 Career Guidance and Decision Making in South Africa

Career Guidance, a vital topic in the Life Orientation curriculum for high schools in South Africa, is important for enabling students to make informed career decisions. A school-based Career Guidance program enables learners to maximise their earning potential, adapt to change, and recognise and utilise available opportunities [8]. Career Guidance is most effective when students align their interests with potential career

paths. This supportive environment enables individuals to showcase their skills and talents, resulting in significant success and job satisfaction [9]. In the 12th grade in South Africa, students make choices regarding their post-secondary career paths, whether that involves pursuing further education or seeking employment. The emergence of Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) have enabled Career Guidance services to be offered online. As an emerging trend, these services are provided through RS-enabled technologies, where RS-generated content is considered capable of managing career decision-making data [2]. In South Africa, the students' access to these tools may vary according to the school's quintile. The school quintile denotes the socio-economic or performance-based classification of a student's school. The National Department of Education (DBE) categorises public schools into five quintiles, with quintile 1 representing the poorest and quintile 5 the least poor. Users from higher-quintile schools may have greater technological exposure, which shapes their familiarity, acceptance, and usage of educational technologies [10, 11].

2.2 Information Disclosure Research on the Internet

Research on information disclosure explores the elements that can affect the amount of information users choose to share by viewing information disclosure as a decision-making challenge, where the individual must weigh various uncertain outcomes [7]. Privacy calculus theory (see Figure 1) posits that users disclose personal data based on a perceived risk-benefit analysis, influencing their willingness to engage with online services [10, 11]. Decisions regarding individual privacy are frequently characterised as a calculation where personal data is exchanged for specific benefits, often called privacy calculus [11]. Privacy concerns have become especially prominent since technology service providers might have access to more potentially sensitive data [11]. To understand information disclosure decisions regarding the data and personal information used by users on mobile applications, Figure 1 provides a theoretical framework that hypothesises that a trade-off between perceived privacy risks and perceived benefits shapes users' decisions to disclose personal information [10]. Higher perceived risks reduce disclosure intentions, while greater perceived benefits increase them. Privacy concerns indirectly affect these intentions by amplifying risks and diminishing benefits. Although intentions influence actual disclosure behaviour, the accuracy and honesty of disclosed information often moderate this relationship [10].

Fig. 1. Privacy calculus core theory

2.3 Existing Recommender Systems User Studies Frameworks

Research on privacy decision-making often focuses on privacy as a personal trait or variable influencing disclosure behaviour and rarely compares the two [7]. Additionally, the impact of personal attributes and system variables on information sharing varies significantly across different systems. Therefore, a unified approach to studying privacy decisions, which integrates privacy-related concepts, can potentially cover this gap [7]. Knijnenburg's (2012) user-centric evaluation framework integrates both personal and system attributes that influence user experience. This study employs a framework based on Knijnenburg & Kobsa's (2013) privacy concepts, emphasising SPC as a critical personal attribute that impacts RS interaction. Figure 2 outlines these integrations, highlighting the specific constructs and directional relationships that can be explored.

Fig. 2.: The framework for user-centric evaluation of RSs populated with the system privacy research concepts [7].

In line with the argument that the impact of personal attributes and system variables on information sharing varies greatly among systems, this study identified a gap in the literature in that there is a lack of a theory-based, real-life-tested framework for understanding how system privacy concerns mediate the processes behind users'

privacy calculus and influence their information disclosure decisions in domain-specific RS focusing on education. This paper addresses this gap by attempting to answer the question: How do system privacy concerns mediate the processes behind users' privacy calculus and influence their information disclosure decisions in tertiary education RS?

3 Method

This study was conducted using a Design Science Research (DSR) methodology with three iterative cycles of artefact refinement, adopting a mixed-methods approach to explore the research problem from users' perspectives. Employing mixed methods offers several advantages, primarily by providing more detailed and nuanced data through the integration of qualitative and quantitative patterns [12]. This study collected data using questionnaires and semi-structured interviews. The survey instrument included items measuring perceived recommendation quality, usefulness, overall trust in the recommender system, satisfaction, and privacy concerns. Each construct was assessed using multiple statements on a five-point Likert scale (1 = Strongly Disagree, 5 = Strongly Agree). To focus on and improve the quality of results for the local context, this study examined participants from South Africa only and asked a series of survey-based testing questions. In the combined three iterations, 719 post-secondary students with a minimum of six to ten months of university experience completed the questionnaires for this study, having selected their tertiary education paths through the educational RS while in high school. Furthermore, 26 students were interviewed for better insights into the quantitative data. The ontological stance adopted by the researchers in this study is pragmatism. A pragmatic philosophical perspective holds that reality is significant insofar as it has a practical effect on ideas, where knowledge is vital for facilitating the successful completion of specific actions [13]. Given this research's pragmatic focus, the adopted mixed-methods approach to data gathering effectively garnered both qualitative and quantitative insights necessary to understand students' experiences related to privacy in the education RS.

Table 1. Descriptive statistics of the privacy questions from the three iterations

Privacy Concerns	Count	Mean	Std	Min	25%	50%	75%	Max	Skewness	Kurtosis
Concerns of Data Disclosure	719	2.228	1.411	1.0	1.0	2.0	3.0	5.0	0.821	-0.643
Privacy Invasion	719	1.561	1.045	1.0	1.0	1.0	2.0	5.0	2.034	3.424
Confidence in Privacy Respect	719	4.420	1.069	1.0	4.0	5.0	5.0	5.0	-2.069	3.525
Data Sharing Comfort	719	1.848	1.255	1.0	1.0	1.0	2.0	5.0	1.366	0.684
Confidentiality Respect	719	4.428	1.170	1.0	4.0	5.0	5.0	5.0	-2.098	3.160

Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) was used as the integrative statistical procedure for analysing the online survey results. SEM is an integrative statistical procedure because it simultaneously tests the measurement model and all hypotheses [14]. SEM allows researchers to model and estimate intricate interactions among multiple dependent and independent variables, and consequently, this technique improves the precision of measuring theoretical concepts [15].

4 Research hypothesis

Drawing on the user experience framework [16] and the logic of privacy calculus [6, 10], which suggests that higher perceived privacy risk reduces perceived benefits, we hypothesised that higher system privacy concerns would negatively impact users' perceived RS benefits and behaviours. Accordingly, the following five hypotheses were formulated:

- H1: System Privacy Concerns will have a negative effect on Perceived Recommendation Quality
- H2: System Privacy Concerns will negatively affect Perceived System Usefulness
- H3: System Privacy Concerns will have a negative effect on Overall Satisfaction
- H4: System Privacy Concerns will negatively affect Overall Trust in the Recommendation System
- H5: System Privacy Concerns will negatively and significantly influence users' Interaction with the Recommendation System

5 Results

To understand the research's findings regarding the influence of SPC on PQR, PSU, OS, OTRS, and INT. It is imperative to provide a contextual explanation of the Objective Systems Aspects (OSA) according to the [16] framework to better understand the constructed relationship with SPC in the RS usage by the participants. The OSAs, which are the primary drivers of the tertiary education RS studied in the research, are the algorithm, the recommendation set composition, and the preference input data.

- Algorithm: Despite the research interest in RS, there is a notable lack of knowledge on how algorithm accuracy affects user experience [12]. In this study, we examined a real-life perspective by evaluating the impact of the RS algorithm's perception beyond theoretical lab experiments. In the studied education RS, students log in to the application with a specific Choice Goal (CG) concerning tertiary education qualification and institution selection and are thereafter asked for invasive personal data ranging from biographical data, family household income and detailed academic performance to generate context-aware recommendations for post-secondary education opportunities.
- Recommendation set composition: Another critical aspect of the OSA is the composition of the recommendation set presented to the user. The education RS that

was studied presents recommendations based on the student's CG and academic performance. In the first iteration, the students were presented with seven tertiary institution recommendations, with each institution showing three related qualifications where students stood the best chance of qualifying based on the Grade 11 results and the institutions' Admission Point Score (APS). Thereafter, in the third iteration, the students were presented with eleven institutions and thirty-three related qualifications.

- Preference input data: The convergence of the algorithm and interface occurs during the process of eliciting preferences. The Content-Based Filtering (CBF) technique recommends items based on the user's explicit preferences or implicit preferences, derived from the user's selection history or past preferences. The studied RS uses a CBF technique, where the matching of the students' attributes (situational characteristics, career interests, institutional interests, study geography preference and academic performance) is considered and stored to recommend qualifications and institutions that align with the user's interests. The core CBF student item selection works as follows:
 - Step 1: Creation of a user account with personal and family biographic data
 - Step 2: Selection of the student's school, grade, and Grade 11 subjects
 - Step 3: Confirmation of academic performance from a valid school report
 - Step 4: Elicitation of the career choices and career goal confirmation
 - Step 6: Confirmation of the preferred institutions and qualifications
 - Step 7: Monitoring of the feedback
 - Step 8: Student utility feedback once they have completed high school

From the user's perspective, the SPC was evaluated over three iterations, and the following results were obtained as presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Path Coefficients and Significance Levels of SEM in Iteration 3. *** $p < .001$, ** $p < .01$, * $p < .05$, Insignificant = $p \geq .0$

Relationship	Estimate	Bootstrap Mean	Bootstrap SD	T-Stat	Significance	2.5% CI	97.5% CI
SPC → PRQ [H1]	0.3484	0.3480	0.0453	7.6959	***	0.2610	0.4368
SPC → PSU [H2]	0.1240	0.1237	0.0231	5.3642	***	0.0843	0.1739
SPC → OS [H3]	0.0648	0.0655	0.0344	1.8840	-	-0.0009	0.1329
SPC → OTRS [H4]	0.1124	0.1127	0.0407	2.7596	**	0.0362	0.1918
SPC → INT [H5]	0.0488	0.0494	0.0210	2.3184	*	0.0087	0.0915

Overall, most relationships between SPC and the other constructs were positive rather than negative. Significant paths [H1, H2, H4, H5] show positive coefficients, whereas H3 was non-significant. Figure 3 illustrates the relationship between SPC and the PRQ, PSU, OTRS, and INT using the [6] framework. Within this context of education RS usage, some constructs that might be aggregated as SPC might correlate with greater RS attentiveness and engagement, leading to higher perceived system quality, usefulness, overall trust in the recommender system, and interaction. Additionally, subtle variations in question wording or socioeconomic factors such as school quintile

may lead students who are highly engaged with privacy questions to respond more positively overall. The discussion section enhances understanding of these results by providing additional insights from student interviews, which further clarify the meaning of the positive coefficients.

Fig. 3 : The framework for user-centric evaluation of RSs populated with the constructs tested in this study. *** $p < .001$, ** $p < .01$, * $p < .05$, Insignificant = $p \geq .0$

6 Discussion

This section aims to discuss the research hypothesis and support the claims using collected quantitative data, interviews from students (S) and existing theories from the literature. The section examines each hypothesis in detail and attempts to investigate the reasons behind the positive coefficients through direct student feedback, including interviews. Privacy calculus theory frames our exploration of SPC's role in education RS, especially regarding perceived benefits versus privacy risks.

H1. System Privacy Concerns will have a negative effect on Perceived Recommendation Quality. The gathered quantitative data does not support the hypothesised negative effect on PRQ. Instead, the results indicate a positive influence of SPC on PRQ, which contradicts some aspects of the Privacy Calculus theory [10]. Quantitative findings reveal a path coefficient of $\beta = 0.3484$ ($p < 0.001$) in the third iteration of the study. The descriptive statistics for “Confidence in Privacy Respect” ($M = 4.420$) and “Confidentiality Respect” ($M = 4.428$) exhibit high mean scores, underscoring robust trust in the application’s privacy measures. Qualitative interviews reinforce these insights, with most students reporting minimal apprehension about data misuse, citing password-protected access and the RS school's endorsement. S1 mentioned that “I wasn’t concerned... I didn’t see any need to be worried”. Even those

initially wary became reassured over time once they realised privacy safeguards were in place in the RS, where S16 commented, “I was sceptical... but at the same time, I was willing to take the risk.” Although some scepticism lingered among a minority of students, the overall consistency of positive relationships indicates that the perceived and experienced RS safeguards enhance the perceived quality of the recommendations by the students. The results show that the RS effectively aligns users’ privacy expectations with the recommendations provided.

H2: System Privacy Concerns will negatively affect Perceived System Usefulness. The research results do not support the hypothesised negative effect on PSU. Instead, they indicate a positive influence of SPC on PSU, highlighting how privacy features can enhance users’ perceptions of the system’s value in supporting tertiary and qualifications decisions. The SEM results for H2 show a significant relationship, with a path coefficient of $\beta = 0.1240$, suggesting that higher SPC align with higher perceived usefulness. Descriptive data similarly demonstrate strong confidence in the app’s privacy measures ($M = 4.420$ for “Confidence in Privacy Respect” and $M = 4.428$ for “Confidentiality Respect”), underscoring a group of students who see robust safeguards against misuse. Interview findings reinforce this perspective, revealing how privacy measures shaped students’ sense of the RS’s overall usefulness. For example, S10 explained, “The App gave me the exact match with my marks on how I was doing because I used my marks. The App showed me the specific qualifications that were relevant to me,” emphasising how a secure environment where confidential academic results contributed to more tailored, and useful recommendations. S14 also found the system both secure and useful, highlighting, “I trusted the app, and it helped me narrow down my course options. It is like it knew what I needed.” Likewise, S15 noted, “I never encountered any problems, so I never had any concerns about privacy,” while S11 highlighted the platform’s comparative reliability: “It is better than just Googling. Here, you know your information is safe, and the recommendations make sense for what you want.” These results reflect privacy calculus in action, where students weighed the potential risks of sharing their personal information against the tangible benefits of receiving accurate, personalised guidance. In this case, the advantage of accurate and reliable recommendations outweighed privacy reservations, thereby possibly explaining why higher levels of perceived privacy concern actually correlate with a stronger sense of the system’s usefulness.

H3: System Privacy Concerns will have a negative effect on Overall Satisfaction. Despite prior indications of significance, the final iteration reveals that the SPC relationship with OS is no longer statistically supported ($\beta = 0.0648$) in the third iteration of the DRS step. However, the positive direction suggests that mitigating privacy concerns may still contribute to overall satisfaction, even if it does not reach conventional significance levels. This sentiment is echoed by S26, who acknowledged initial wariness but felt reassured by the system’s benefits over time: “I was concerned...but then I realised it is helping us.” Such experiences align with the Privacy Calculus theory [11] and the Personalisation-Privacy Paradox, wherein students weigh potential risks against perceived utility, often discovering that the RS delivers sufficient value to alleviate privacy concerns. Considering the insignificance of the final path

coefficient, we cannot definitively conclude that privacy concerns directly influence user satisfaction in this explored context.

H4: System Privacy Concerns will negatively affect Overall Trust in the Recommendation System. The final iteration results do not support the hypothesised negative impact on OTRS. Instead, the path coefficient is $\beta = 0.1124$, with a T-statistic of 2.7596 ($p < 0.01$), demonstrating the opposite. This finding contrasts with earlier, inconclusive trends, underscoring a possible nuanced relationship that could reflect how strong privacy measures or transparent processes reassure students once they begin interacting with the RS. Qualitative insights further highlight why possible heightened SPC might translate into positive trust outcomes. S1 expressed minimal worry, attributing their confidence to the absence of perceived risk, while S10 emphasised the role of password security: “I have the password, so I did not think anyone could access my account,” thereby reinforcing their trust in the recommender system. S16 recounted feeling “sceptical” at first but acknowledged that continued usage and proven benefits eased those fears, and S26 similarly described how initial reservations faded as they discovered the RS truly aided their academic focus.

Although a few students retained some caution, the overall pattern, from both the SEM findings and student narratives, demonstrates that SPC, when sufficiently addressed by security features, can increase trust in the education RS. Thus, the final iteration’s evidence contradicts the negative hypothesis, showing a positive link between SPC and OTRS in this educational context.

H5: System Privacy Concerns will negatively and significantly influence users’ Interaction with the Recommendation System. Contrary to the expected negative effect, the final iteration shows a positive, but modest, relationship ($\beta = 0.0488$, T-stat = 2.3184, $p < 0.05$). While the coefficient has decreased from previous iterations, it remains significant, suggesting that students with higher SPC still engage with the RS, potentially due to the perception that privacy concerns are well-managed or outweighed by the system’s benefits. Descriptive data on privacy (“Privacy Invasion” $M = 1.561$, “Data Sharing Comfort” $M = 1.848$) confirm overall low concern, reinforcing the notion that such worries do not substantially deter system usage. Qualitative insights elaborate on this subtle connection. S1 admitted, “I was not quite aware of any privacy issues, and I did not think there was a need for me to feel worried,” showcasing how minimal privacy fears can facilitate confident interaction with the RS. Even students who initially hesitated, like S16, declared they were “willing to take the risk,” and S26 stated, “At first, I was concerned... but over time, I realised this helps children focus on studying and doing well.” Over time, these doubts diminished, suggesting a reciprocal relationship between privacy perceptions and continued RS interaction, potentially indicating that the more students used the system, the more they experienced its practical benefits, thereby alleviating their concerns.

Despite the positive direction, the relatively low coefficient may indicate that privacy concerns are only one of multiple factors influencing interaction. S11 summed this up by emphasising greater comfort with the application compared to other platforms: “I felt more comfortable sharing documents with the RS compared to other websites.” In this way, the final iteration’s results confirm that addressing privacy issues can facilitate interaction, contrary to the original negative hypothesis.

Overall, the results challenge traditional privacy calculus predictions, revealing nuanced relationships where enhanced SPC aligns with increased user engagement and trust, likely due to perceived effective privacy protections. Qualitative interviews support these findings, showing how explicit privacy features strengthen user trust and RS value perceptions. These findings highlight the Personalisation-Privacy Paradox, where users accept privacy risks for significant personalisation benefits.

Design implications for RS developers include embedding clear privacy assurances and effectively communicating data usage within RS interfaces, which significantly enhances user trust and interaction.

7. Conclusion and Future Work

This section draws conclusions based on the data collected in the broader study and the preceding discussion, addressing the core question: How do System Privacy Concerns mediate the processes behind users' privacy calculus and influence their information disclosure decisions in tertiary education RS. In line with the gap identified from literature [6], our study sought to extend existing privacy calculus theory into a specific educational domain, focusing on real-world usage rather than lab-based RS evaluation. Through iterative data collection and analysis using the DSR method, we observed positive relationships between SPC and critical RS constructs such as PRQ, PSU, OTRS, and INT. While the direct effect of SPC on OS was not statistically significant in the final model, qualitative insights suggest that RS privacy safeguards and transparent data-handling practices promote student privacy reassurance, and as such, students are more willing to share sensitive information.

These findings underscore that when privacy measures and user trust are cultivated through password protection, clear privacy statements, and institutional endorsements, such as schools, students are more readily engaged with the education RS, aligning with Privacy Calculus theory and the Personalisation-Privacy Paradox. Although a subset of students initially expressed caution, most concerns diminished once they recognised the platform's tangible benefits. This process illustrates how privacy considerations, rather than impeding system use, can heighten perceived value if thoughtfully managed from a design perspective. These findings emphasise that educational RS designers must implement visible privacy safeguards and transparent data practices to foster user trust. Educational institutions should also recognise the necessity of clear privacy policies and governance to protect student data, which will promote broader adoption and confidence in these RS systems. Furthermore, from a socio-economic perspective, no evidence was found to demonstrate differential results based on the school quintile in the collected data. Therefore, the results, having explored the socio-economic perspective, have shown that the SPC behaviour has not changed despite the student's background.

By testing these relationships in an authentic tertiary education setting rather than a controlled laboratory, our study helps fill a gap in the literature. Although the direct influence of SPC on overall satisfaction did not reach statistical significance, qualitative interviews suggest that privacy measures may provide reassurance and foster long-term

contentment for many students. Ultimately, this research highlights the social good potential of education RS in South Africa, provided privacy elements are carefully integrated to mitigate students' concerns and strengthen their trust. However, this study has certain limitations. First, the sample was limited to a single educational context in South Africa, using a single RS, which may restrict generalisability to other domains or regions. Second, our data relied on self-reported perceptions at a single point in time of each iteration. Longitudinal studies tracking actual long-term usage would offer deeper insights into how privacy calculus decisions evolve. Future studies should address these limitations to validate and expand our findings.

Future research will refine our understanding of privacy-related decision-making in context-aware RSs, building on the [7] model and extending our iterative model. In particular, exploring individual traits and objective system factors may further elucidate why some students remain wary of RS privacy. Additional data may also facilitate testing the explanatory and predictive power of the model in socially diverse educational contexts, thereby contributing to a more comprehensive picture of privacy's role in fostering meaningful and trustworthy system interactions, potentially enriching both academic discourses on RS privacy and the practical design of privacy-sensitive education RS.

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Components Required for Human-Centred AI

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Abstract. Artificial intelligence holds many benefits but can also cause harm when not following a human-centred approach. This approach is called human-centred AI (HCAI) and aims to augment human abilities to create safe, reliable and trustworthy solutions. A systematic literature review was used as a research approach to identify the components of HCAI. Thirty-two papers were analysed as part of the study using thematic analysis. Twenty-four themes were identified, namely agile, auditable, available, comprehensible, controllable, dependable, directable, explainable, fair, interpretable, observable, predictable, privacy, reliable, resilient, robust, safe, secure, traceable, trackable, transparent, trustworthy, unbiased, and usable. Ethics, fairness, governance, privacy, safety, security, reliability, explainability, transparency, and trustworthiness were the more apparent themes. The identified components can be utilised in developing AI solutions from a human-centred perspective. Including the components in a development approach should assist in developing ethical, fair, secure, reliable, understandable, trustworthy, and safe AI solutions while ensuring human and ethical impacts are considered.

Keywords: Human-centred, artificial intelligence, HCAI, augment human abilities.

1 Introduction

Artificial intelligence (AI) refers to tasks typically executed by humans being performed by computers [1]. It utilises algorithms like machine learning (ML), neural networks, and deep learning [1, 2]. The presence of AI in the daily lives of humans increases continually and influences daily activities [1, 3-6].

AI solutions are data-driven and learn independently to achieve the best results for the set goal, but they do not typically consider the human or ethical impact [3, 7]. The inclusion of AI into systems can harm humans through, for example, bias and security breaches [2, 5, 8, 9]. Users and stakeholders are not typically included in developing AI solutions [10]. The technical nature of AI is an obstacle to including non-technical individuals in the development process [10]. The increased presence of AI and its problems has given rise to human-centred AI (HCAI) [1, 4].

HCAI aims to aid humans by considering human input and feedback while considering human rights, safety, fairness, and dignity to enhance human competencies,

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15704177
In Proceedings: Corradini, F.; Hinkelmann, K.; Re, B., Smuts, H., eds. (2025). Proceedings of the 5th Conference Society 5.0 - Co-Existence Between Human Being and Machine Being, Vol. 2. San Benedetto del Tronto, Italy, 25-27 June 2025.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15422355>

imagination, efficiency, and confidence [2, 4, 11-14]. The HCAI approach differs from AI in its development process and the product delivered as output [11]. AI focuses on process autonomy and algorithm efficiency, whereas humans have become essential in HCAI [5, 11, 14, 15]. HCAI delivers products that support, strengthen, enable, and enhance human abilities and efficiencies [5, 6, 11]. HCAI does not aim to replace humans but rather to augment human capabilities by involving humans in the development process, thereby providing humans control over AI [4, 11, 13, 16]. In addition, having a more human-centred approach to developing AI systems would improve AI system adoption, allowing AI systems to exert a more significant impact on delivering human needs [2, 11, 15].

Therefore, the main research question of this paper is: *What are the components required for a human-centred approach for (sic) the development of systems that use artificial intelligence?* As delineated by the research question, the scope of the study encompassed identifying the key components promoting human-centredness in AI from the literature. The scope excludes investigating AI regulatory frameworks, standards, explainability methods or proposing a new methodological approach. Instead, the study aims to integrate existing knowledge to enhance the understanding of human-centred components highlighted in the existing literature. This study forms part of a larger, overarching study.

The remainder of this paper is organised as follows: Section 2 presents the research approach, Section 3 contains the data analysis, Section 4 discusses the results and findings of the literature review, and Section 5 concludes the paper.

2 Background

Schleith, Norkute [15] describe AI as a process that uses data to perform a task resembling human action, intending to elicit an outcome. In addition, AI fits the description of technologies imitating human thinking to improve complex processes and decision-making [12, 17]. AI strives to enable machines to execute human intelligence-related tasks, like learning, generalisation, problem-solving, interpretation, and statistics [8, 12, 18].

HCAI refers to developing AI algorithms through a human-centred development approach [2, 5, 11]. HCAI focuses on users at the centre of design and development [2, 4, 5, 14, 15]. The process considers user requirements and measures user efficiency and happiness [5, 14]. The main goal of HCAI is to allow for a significant amount of human control and automation, whereby humans can influence decisions and events [2, 4, 11, 12, 14, 19]. To that end, a balance must be found between efficiency, automation and humanity [4, 20].

HCAI solutions are achieved when designers, software developers, and management involve different stakeholders in their design and development [2, 14]. User involvement is essential to delivering a solution that would meet user needs and highlight the limitations of AI systems and the need for a human-centred approach [4, 11, 15, 16, 20]. Reliable human-centred AI solutions are achieved through trustworthy technical practices that depict human obligation [14].

3 Research Approach

This paper aims to understand the components required for a human-centred approach to developing AI solutions, using a literature review to understand the scope of HCAI. A literature review is the process of reading and evaluating literature to gain an understanding of the content and context and seek support for a research study [21, 22]. A sound literature review should follow a thorough step-by-step process to integrate peer-reviewed literature into a whole to provide support for the research problem in question [23-25]. Rouhani, Mahrin [26] suggest a three-step process for a systematic literature review: (1) planning, (2) execution, and (3) result analysis. The planning step entails determining the research questions, secondary questions, and scope of the study [26]. The execution step entails finding relevant literature based on keywords and explaining how literature was evaluated by defining inclusion and exclusion criteria [26]. The result analysis step entails reporting the study results by comparing and linking literature from different authors to provide new insights into the field of study [26].

As part of the second step, execution, the author executed a keyword search for “Human-centred AI” in *Scopus* for reviewed articles published between 2020 and 2024. Ben Schneiderman [27] presented the term HCAI in 2019, which industry and researchers had generally embraced by 2020. Only open-access reviewed articles and books were included; commentary, notes, and lecture notes were excluded. The included articles had to have been cited at least once. Only articles from the following databases were considered: *ACM Digital*, *IEEE Xplore*, *ScienceDirect*, *SpringerLink*, *Taylor & Francis*, and *Emerald* (**Table 1**). These databases are a source of high-quality peer-reviewed articles.

Table 1. Total number of papers and books

Database	Total	Included	Excluded
ACM Digital Library	20	13	7
IEEE Xplore	8	5	3
ScienceDirect	15	8	7
SpringerLink	6	2	4
Taylor & Francis	4	2	2
Emerald Insight	1	1	0
Oxford (Book)	1	1	0
Total	55	32	23

One hundred and ninety-four (194) articles emerged in the initial search using the search keyword for 2020 to 2024. Only the 55 articles from the databases listed in **Table 1** were reviewed. Twenty-three (23) articles were excluded due to relevancy or duplication. The remaining 32 articles were coded and themed.

Fig. 1. Components of HCAI: Network Graph

The pink circles (nodes) indicate the main topic identified by *InfraNodus*. The measure of betweenness centrality (BC) determines the size of the circle; hence, the higher the BC measure, the bigger the circle. The green lines represent the interrelationships between topics, whereby the closer the connection, the higher the weight of the connection.

5 Discussion of results

5.1 Components of Human-Centred AI

Shneiderman [11] lists twenty-five components in the literature contributing to human-centeredness in AI systems, as shown in **Table 2**. The most critical are reliability, safety, and trustworthiness [11], all of which are essential aspects of achieving ethical AI that ensures data governance [4, 11].

Table 2. Components of HCAI [11]

Component	Reference
Agile	[11]
Auditable	[9, 11, 14]
Available	[4, 11]
Comprehensible	[1, 3, 6, 7, 11, 16, 29]
Controllable	[2, 4, 6, 11, 30]
Dependable	[11]
Directable	[11]
Explainable	[2, 5, 9, 11, 16, 18, 31-35]
Fair	[2-4, 9, 11, 18-20, 29, 36, 37]
Interpretable	[2, 6, 9, 11, 16, 20]
Observable	[11]
Predictable	[1, 11, 16]
Privacy	[4, 5, 11, 17]
Reliable	[2, 4, 6, 11, 17, 18]
Resilient	[11]
Robust	[9, 11]
Safe	[4, 6, 9, 11, 17]
Secure	[11, 17]
Traceable	[11]
Trackable	[11]
Transparent	[1-4, 6, 7, 9, 11, 18, 20, 32, 34, 35, 37, 38]
Trustworthy	[2, 4-6, 11, 16-19, 30, 34, 37]
Unbiased	[2, 4, 9, 11, 14, 16, 19, 39]
Usable	[2, 6, 11, 16]

It is difficult to evaluate the impact of changes in the development process on these components [11].

5.2 Human-Centred AI

HCAI is the development of AI algorithms with a human-centred development approach [2, 5, 11]. HCAI aims to aid humans by considering human input and feedback while considering human rights, safety, fairness, and dignity to enhance human competencies, imagination, efficiency, and confidence [2, 4, 11-14]. For this study, the definition utilised for HCAI is that HCAI is a method for establishing human control over AI solutions and associating AI solutions with human, ethical, and legal standards to deliver reliable, safe, and trustworthy AI solutions [6].

The HCAI approach differs from AI in the development process it follows and the product it delivers as output [11]. In addition, the aspects deemed necessary at the time of development differ between HCAI and AI [11]. AI focuses on process autonomy and algorithm efficiency, whereas humans have become essential in HCAI [5, 11, 14, 15]. HCAI delivers products that support, strengthen, enable, and boost human abilities and efficiencies [5, 6, 11].

HCAI focuses on the users, placing them at the centre during design and development [2, 4, 5, 14, 15]. As such, user requirements are considered, and user efficiency and happiness are measured [5, 14]. HCAI mainly strives to allow for a significant amount of human control and automation, whereby humans can influence decisions and events [2, 4, 11, 12, 14, 19]. Hence, a balance must be found between efficiency, automation and humanity [4, 20]. In addition, the user interface should be user-friendly and pleasurable to use [3, 19].

HCAI solutions are achieved when designers, software developers, and management involve different stakeholders in the design and development [2, 14]. Human-computer interaction (HCI) principles are also incorporated into the design and development process [2-4, 12, 15].

The HCAI approach advocates for cooperative symbiosis between humans and AI, whereby users and stakeholders are included in design and development [2, 4, 12, 16]. The two main features of HCAI are systems that comprehend humans and human trust in these systems [2].

AI should improve and aid human capabilities to facilitate productivity and success [1, 2, 6, 17]. The aim should not be to replace humans, as AI cannot recreate human intelligence and insight [2, 6, 11, 17]. Humans can think logically, have discussions, make intelligent decisions, and execute physical and intellectual tasks without calculations [17]. Developing truly human-centred AI requires an understanding of human reasoning, behaviour, and skills [6, 40].

5.3 Discussion of main components

5.3.1 Ethics, fairness, and governance

The unethical use of AI poses substantial risks [9, 17]. AI is created using ML, which is statistical and can thus lead to discrimination if certain groups of people are clustered

together, and that group is impacted more positively or negatively as a consequence of such classification [4, 10, 19]. The quality of data being used by the ML is another risk factor [3, 9, 20]; AI relies on a significant amount of data, and the quality of the data determines the quality of the results [3, 9]. Data can be biased when using a skewed dataset as training data, which, in turn, can influence subsequent AI results and decision-making [3, 4, 9, 19, 20].

AI mainly focuses on generating revenue without considering how humans might benefit [9, 11]. A shift needs to occur from generating only profit to practices enabling ethical AI [9, 11]. The human-centred approach is a well-stated practice that requires a system to operate ethically [2, 9, 10]. Ethical AI aims to leverage the benefits of these technologies while aligning the design with regulations, human rights, values, and standards [3, 4, 17].

Ethics in AI and the speed at which AI develops is concerning [1, 17]. These ethical concerns are related to humanity, bias, fairness, disinformation, lack of transparency, safety, inaccuracies, confidentiality, and employment [4, 9, 17, 19]. These ethical concerns must be addressed in each phase of the system development lifecycle [9, 11]. The involvement of stakeholders in the design and development of AI systems ensures the mitigation of bias results [2, 4, 9]. The stakeholders involved in the design and development influence ethical views and fairness that are considered and embedded into an AI system [4, 9, 19]. Ethics is essential to HCAI [11, 17]. AI4People suggests an ethical framework that includes goodness, integrity, and accuracy [5]. Bingley, Curtis [5] point to the ethical AI principles per Microsoft: “fairness, inclusiveness, reliability, safety, transparency, privacy, security, and accountability”.

Nakao, Strappelli [19] explain fairness as freedom and justice, whereby people have identical opportunities and rights. AI systems are based on the developers' views, which can lead to bias. Therefore, it is imperative to include other stakeholders' views to enable fairness [3, 4, 9, 10, 19]. These systems should extend their focus beyond statistical fairness and consider future use of the system and its impact on humans [3, 20, 36, 37]. Fairness is also measured by the extent to which it adheres to social standards and values [19, 36, 37]; accordingly, fairness must be applied on an individual and group basis, where the individual and the group to which individuals belong are treated fairly [19, 29].

5.3.2 Privacy, safety, and security

AI systems raise privacy, safety, and security concerns and may experience external attacks [4, 9, 17]. Data privacy and safeguarding personal data should be considered in designing and developing AI systems [4, 17]. According to Alfredo, Echeverria [4], data privacy is safeguarding and managing personal and proprietary information. System security also protects against malicious code, failure, loss of control, and theft of personal data [17]. In addition, organisations must ensure they know what data may be shared without violating privacy [4].

User trust is established through the perception of data protection [4]. This perception is enabled by robust data privacy standards and precise, honest data collection methods [4].

5.3.3 Reliability

According to Shneiderman [11], AI solutions are reliable when they deliver the anticipated results and sound technical principles are applied in their design and development. Alfredo, Echeverria [4] explains reliability as an AI solution providing the correct information the user expects and when it performs consistently. Reliability can be achieved by comparing data sources, implementing audit trails, testing, and implementing privacy, safety, and security measures [4, 11].

5.3.4 Explainability and transparency

Explainability refers to the ability to generate and present understandable explanations of complex AI models to users to enable the visibility of the system processes [16, 18, 31-34, 38]. Explainability is vital for creating responsible AI [9, 18, 33, 34] and a means to create transparency and accountability in AI solutions and their evaluation [9, 18, 32-35].

Transparency is imperative for AI solutions and assists in building trust [3, 4, 6, 7, 9, 18, 32, 35, 37, 38]; the principle relates to storing and managing data openly and understandably [4, 38]. Openness extends to explaining in an understandable way how decisions are made [3, 7, 18, 38]. Transparency is required to facilitate understanding, which enables evaluation of the AI system regarding changes and improvements [32, 34, 35]. According to Schmitt, Csomor [35], the AI Act requires human oversight and clear explanations of the system for transparency. Users should be able to audit the decision-making of AI solutions and interpret the data to ensure that the outcome aligns with their expectations [2].

5.3.5 Trustworthiness

Trustworthiness is a primary concern in AI systems and should be planned for in the design phase [4, 17]. Alfredo, Echeverria [4] list three components of trustworthiness, namely trust, transparency, and accountability. Bingley, Curtis [5] state that the European Union lists seven fundamental stipulations for AI solutions to be deemed trustworthy, with transparency, accountability, and consideration of societal and environmental norms as the main requirements. Accountability can be explained as accepting liability for decisions and the outcomes of such decisions [4, 9, 18].

Trust is influenced by humans having to surrender control and decision-making to automated systems [30]. Therefore, AI systems must be trustworthy for humans to adopt them [3, 17, 34]. Trust is only achieved when an AI system performs its primary function safely and reliably [4, 17]. In addition, trust can be facilitated through transparency and explainability [2, 4, 16, 37]. Rong, Leemann [16] explain trust in an AI system as the amalgamation of users' assurance of its precision, its level of grasping and usability, and the level of decision-making the user accepts.

6 Conclusion

HCAI is the development of AI algorithms with a human-centred development approach [2, 5, 11], for which this article aims to identify the requisite components.

The authors utilised a systematic literature review as a research approach to identify the components of HCAI. Thirty-two papers were analysed as part of the study using thematic analysis, from which twenty-four themes were identified: agile, auditable, available, comprehensible, controllable, dependable, directable, explainable, fair, interpretable, observable, predictable, privacy, reliable, resilient, robust, safe, secure, traceable, trackable, transparent, trustworthy, unbiased, and usable. Ethics, fairness, governance, privacy, safety, security, reliability, explainability, transparency, and trustworthiness were more apparent themes.

The identified components have practical significance in their utilisation for developing AI solutions from a human-centred perspective. Including the components above in a design approach would assist in developing AI solutions with the following characteristics: ethical, fair, secure, reliable, understandable, trustworthy, and safe while considering the human and ethical impact and delivering AI solutions that aid humans.

Furthermore, the identified components contribute theoretically to a larger, overarching study aimed at developing a human-centred framework for the development and evaluation of online systems that apply artificial intelligence. The larger study aims to develop a human-centred framework to guide the development and evaluation of AI solutions.

This study was limited to identifying and analysing the vital components in existing literature that encourage human-centredness in AI. The scope was limited to AI solutions developed for integration with online systems. The study did not perform empirical testing or evaluation of AI systems. Lastly, the study focused on general principles of human-centred design rather than domain-specific applications.

Future research might investigate how these components could be included in a formal development approach to ensure that AI is developed in a human-centred manner that ensures it is not biased, benefits humans, augments human abilities and is ethical, transparent, reliable, trustworthy, and explainable.

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Towards an Inclusive Digital Society: Digital Accessibility Framework for Visually Impaired Citizens in Swiss Public Administration

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Abstract. As we progress toward Society 5.0's vision of a human-centered digital society, ensuring digital accessibility becomes increasingly critical, particularly for citizens with visual impairments and other disabilities. This paper examines the implementation challenges of accessible digital public services within Swiss public administration. Through Design Science Research, we investigate the gap between accessibility legislation and practical implementation, analyzing how current standards translate into real-world usability.

Our research reveals significant barriers including resource constraints, fragmented policy enforcement, and limited technical expertise. To address these challenges, we present the Inclusive Public Administration Framework, which integrates Web Content Accessibility Guidelines with the HERMES project management methodology. This framework provides a structured approach to embedding accessibility considerations throughout digital service development. Our findings contribute to the discourse on digital inclusion in Society 5.0 by providing actionable strategies for implementing accessible public services. As we move towards a more integrated human-machine society, ensuring digital accessibility for visually impaired citizens is crucial for building an equitable and inclusive digital future.

Keywords: Digital Accessibility · Visual Impairment · Public Administration · WCAG · Digital Inclusion

1 Introduction

The digital age has fundamentally transformed how we interact with government services. As we progress toward Society 5.0, a human-centered society that balances economic advancement with social challenges, ensuring digital accessibility becomes increasingly critical. However, this transformation has created new barriers for individuals with disabilities, particularly those with visual impairments [12] [8].

In Switzerland, where digital transformation of public services is rapidly advancing, approximately 61% of citizens express readiness to engage with digital

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15704219

In Proceedings: Corradini, F.; Hinkelmann, K.; Re, B., Smuts, H., eds. (2025). Proceedings of the 5th Conference Society 5.0 - Co-Existence Between Human Being and Machine Being, Vol. 2. San Benedetto del Tronto, Italy, 25-27 June 2025.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15422355>

public services [3]. However, this general acceptance masks significant accessibility challenges. Despite Switzerland’s commitment to inclusive accessibility through the Federal Act on the Elimination of Disadvantages for Persons with Disabilities (DDis) [5], many digital platforms remain difficult or impossible for visually impaired individuals to navigate independently.

Recent incidents highlight the persistent gap between policy and practice. For instance, in 2023, a mandatory Federal Statistical Office survey was found to be inaccessible to blind individuals [10]. Such cases underscore the critical need for better alignment between accessibility legislation and practical implementation. With approximately 1.8 million people in Switzerland reporting disabilities in 2020 (21% of the population) [4], addressing these accessibility gaps becomes paramount.

This research examines the challenges and opportunities in implementing accessible digital public services within Swiss public administration, focusing on visual impairment. Through Design Science Research, we investigate how current web accessibility standards [6] and regulations translate into real-world usability. To address identified barriers, we present the Inclusive Public Administration Framework, which integrates Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG) with the HERMES project management methodology [11] [17] widely used in Swiss public administration.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section 2 reviews theoretical foundations, Section 3 presents our methodology, Section 4 describes the framework development, Section 5 presents evaluation results, Section 6 discusses implications, and Section 7 concludes with recommendations for future research and practice.

2 Literature Review

Digital accessibility has become increasingly critical in the context of Society 5.0, which emphasizes human-centered technological advancement [12]. The digital divide, initially focused on basic computer access, now encompasses broader issues of digital literacy and participation [14]. According to the World Health Organization, approximately 15% of the global population lives with disabilities [1], with Switzerland reporting a higher rate of 21% [4].

Visual impairment presents unique challenges in digital environments, requiring various accommodations depending on severity [2]. While moderate vision loss may require magnification and contrast adjustments, total blindness necessitates screen readers and specialized assistive technologies [8]. Recent incidents, such as Switzerland’s inaccessible Federal Statistical Office survey [10], highlight ongoing gaps between accessibility policies and their practical implementation.

Switzerland’s approach to digital accessibility is governed by the Federal Act on the Elimination of Disadvantages for Persons with Disabilities (DDis) [5], complemented by international standards like the Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG) [6]. The HERMES project management methodology, widely

used in Swiss public administration [16], has begun incorporating accessibility considerations [17], though implementation challenges persist.

While digital transformation of public services offers opportunities for increased accessibility, poor implementation can create new barriers. Studies show that 61% of Swiss citizens are ready for eGovernment services [3], but this general readiness doesn't reflect varying accessibility needs. Emerging technologies, particularly artificial intelligence, present new possibilities for enhancing accessibility [7][15], though their implementation requires careful consideration.

Despite advances in policy and technology, a significant gap remains between theoretical frameworks and practical implementation of digital accessibility in public administration. This gap, shaped by resource constraints, technical limitations, and organizational challenges, forms the focus of our research, which aims to develop a practical framework integrating accessibility considerations into existing project management methodologies.

3 Research Methodology

This research employs Design Science Research (DSR) methodology to address the challenges of digital accessibility in Swiss public administration. DSR's focus on creating and evaluating artifacts to solve organizational problems [9] aligns with our goal of developing a practical framework for implementing accessibility in public services. The methodology's emphasis on utility and effectiveness corresponds with our aim to create actionable solutions, while its iterative approach enables continuous refinement through stakeholder feedback.

In the context of Society 5.0, where human-centered technological solutions are paramount, DSR's focus on creating practical, user-oriented artifacts makes it particularly appropriate. The methodology enables us to systematically address the socio-technical challenges of digital accessibility while ensuring solutions remain grounded in real-world applicability [18].

Our research follows five sequential yet iterative phases:

The Problem Awareness phase began with a systematic literature review of digital accessibility challenges and current standards, complemented by expert interviews with stakeholders to identify practical barriers in implementing accessible digital services. This phase provided a comprehensive foundation for solution development by documenting real-world accessibility challenges within Swiss public services.

During the Solution Suggestion phase, we analyzed interview findings to identify key requirements and reviewed existing frameworks and methodologies. This analysis informed the initial conceptualization of our accessibility framework, ensuring alignment with the HERMES project management methodology commonly used in Swiss public administration.

The Development phase focused on creating the Inclusive Public Administration Framework, carefully integrating WCAG principles with HERMES methodology. The framework underwent continuous refinement based on stakeholder feedback to ensure practical applicability. In the Evaluation phase, we distributed

surveys to cantonal project managers to assess the framework’s effectiveness, collecting detailed feedback on practicality and implementation feasibility.

Data collection employed multiple methods to ensure comprehensive understanding. We conducted semi-structured interviews with key stakeholders including project managers, heads of eChannels, product owners, and IT providers specializing in cantonal systems. These interviews were analyzed using Mayring’s qualitative content analysis approach [13], enabling identification of recurring themes and critical insights. The framework evaluation employed a mixed-methods approach, combining quantitative assessment through structured surveys with qualitative feedback through open-ended questions.

Our literature review encompassed academic publications, policy documents, and technical standards, focusing particularly on accessibility guidelines, legislative frameworks, and developments in assistive technologies. This provided both theoretical foundation and identification of current best practices in digital accessibility.

Several methodological limitations must be acknowledged. The study’s focus on cantonal-level administration may limit generalizability to other administrative levels. Additionally, our emphasis on visual impairment means other disabilities received less attention in framework development. Time constraints affected the depth of framework evaluation, potentially limiting observation of long-term implementation effects. These limitations were carefully considered throughout our analysis and interpretation of results, informing our recommendations for future research.

4 Development of an Inclusive Public Administration Framework

The Inclusive Public Administration Framework represents a novel integration of established methodologies with new approaches to accessibility implementation. Our framework builds upon three existing foundational elements: the Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG) [6], the HERMES project management methodology [16], and Swiss accessibility legislation [5]. While these elements provide robust individual foundations, our contribution lies in their innovative integration and extension to address specific challenges in Swiss public administration.

4.1 Framework Foundations and Novel Integration

The foundational structure of our framework, illustrated in Figure 1, demonstrates how we systematically integrate accessibility considerations throughout the public service development lifecycle. This visualization shows how our approach addresses both website content management and software development projects, ensuring comprehensive coverage of digital public services.

Fig. 1. Visualization of the Inclusive Public Administration Framework logic

4.2 Integration with HERMES Methodology

As shown in Figure 2, our framework introduces accessibility-focused elements within each HERMES phase while maintaining the methodology’s established structure [17]. This integration creates a seamless blend of project management practices and accessibility requirements, representing a significant contribution to both fields.

Fig. 2. Integration of WCAG principles with HERMES project management methodology

Initiation Phase (Perceivable) The initiation phase extends HERMES’s traditional project inception activities with novel accessibility considerations. While HERMES typically focuses on general project planning, our framework introduces specific mechanisms for embedding accessibility requirements from

the outset. We developed new approaches for integrating WCAG’s perceivability principle into initial project documentation and planning processes, creating original templates and guidelines for accessibility-aware project initiation.

Concept Phase (Operable and Understandable) Our innovative approach to the concept phase involves developing new methodologies for translating WCAG’s operability and understandability principles into practical project requirements. Our framework systematically addresses key accessibility considerations during this crucial planning stage, ensuring that both technical and user experience aspects are comprehensively covered.

Implementation Phase (Robust) In the implementation phase, we introduce specialized technical implementation guidelines that bridge the gap between WCAG requirements and HERMES development processes. Our newly developed workflows for integrating accessibility testing into existing development practices include specific protocols for assistive technology compatibility testing within the Swiss administrative context.

Deployment Phase (Conformance) The deployment phase structure represents our novel approach to ensuring long-term accessibility maintenance in public services. Our original framework for accessibility auditing and maintenance planning is specifically designed to address the unique challenges of Swiss public administration.

4.3 Novel Framework Components

Building upon established accessibility standards, we developed several original components to address specific needs in Swiss public administration:

1. **Customized Accessibility Checklists:** New assessment tools that combine WCAG requirements with HERMES project phases.
2. **Role-Specific Guidelines:** Original documentation defining accessibility responsibilities within Swiss administrative structures.
3. **Context-Specific Testing Protocols:** Newly developed testing approaches tailored to cantonal administrative requirements.
4. **Implementation Templates:** Original templates and tools designed specifically for Swiss public service contexts.

4.4 Integration with Existing Processes

While building upon established administrative procedures, our framework introduces new methods for implementing accessibility requirements within existing constraints. We developed original approaches for resource allocation and accessibility implementation that acknowledge and work within the specific limitations

of Swiss public administration. This practical integration represents a significant contribution to the field, demonstrating how accessibility requirements can be effectively implemented within existing organizational structures.

These novel contributions collectively create a framework that not only builds upon established methodologies but also introduces new, practical approaches to implementing accessibility in public services. Our work addresses a significant gap in existing practice while providing concrete solutions for accessibility implementation in Swiss public administration.

5 Evaluation of the Inclusive Public Administration Framework

The evaluation of the Inclusive Public Administration Framework was conducted through a comprehensive assessment involving cantonal project managers and stakeholders in Swiss public administration. Our evaluation approach focused on three key dimensions: policy and process alignment, technical usability, and adaptability for future needs. This section presents the evaluation results and their implications for framework implementation.

5.1 Evaluation Methodology

The assessment was conducted through a structured survey distributed to project managers involved in digital transformation initiatives at the cantonal level. The survey employed both quantitative measures using a 5-point Likert scale and qualitative feedback through open-ended questions, allowing for a comprehensive understanding of the framework's effectiveness.

5.2 Policy and Process Alignment

Our evaluation first examined how effectively the framework aligns with existing internal regulations and policies. Figure 3 presents the stakeholder feedback regarding policy alignment and enforcement gaps.

The results indicate moderate to strong alignment with existing regulations, with 60% of respondents rating the framework's effectiveness as 'good' or 'excellent.' However, the evaluation also revealed challenges in role definition and responsibility assignment, with 40% of participants indicating that clearer stakeholder role delineation would be beneficial.

5.3 Technical Usability Assessment

The technical assessment focused on the framework's practical implementation aspects and ease of adoption. Figure 4 illustrates the stakeholders' evaluation of technical clarity and implementation feasibility.

A significant majority (80%) of respondents rated the framework's technical guidance as 'good,' indicating strong potential for practical implementation. The

Fig. 3. Stakeholder assessment of framework's policy alignment and process integration

evaluation highlighted particularly positive feedback regarding the framework's integration with existing technical processes, with minimal additional training requirements reported.

5.4 Future Adaptability

The framework's capacity to accommodate future technological advancements was assessed through both quantitative ratings and qualitative feedback. Figure 5 presents the stakeholders' perspectives on the framework's adaptability.

The evaluation revealed strong confidence in the framework's adaptability, with 60% of respondents rating it as 'good' for future technological integration. Stakeholders particularly appreciated the framework's modular structure, which allows for incorporation of emerging accessibility technologies and standards.

5.5 Implementation Recommendations

Based on the evaluation results, several key recommendations emerged for successful framework implementation:

1. **Enhanced Role Definition:** Development of more detailed role descriptions and responsibility matrices to address the identified clarity gaps in stakeholder responsibilities.
2. **Training Support:** Creation of supplementary training materials and guides to support framework adoption, despite the generally positive assessment of implementation ease.
3. **Customization Guidelines:** Development of specific guidelines for framework adaptation to different organizational contexts within cantonal administration.
4. **Monitoring Mechanisms:** Establishment of clear monitoring and feedback processes to ensure sustained accessibility compliance.

Fig. 4. Technical usability assessment results

5.6 Evaluation Limitations

Several limitations of our evaluation approach should be acknowledged:

The evaluation primarily focused on cantonal-level administration, potentially limiting insights into framework applicability at other governmental levels. The assessment timeframe provided limited opportunity to observe long-term implementation effects, and the reliance on self-reported data may introduce certain biases in our findings. Additionally, while the response rate was adequate for our analysis, a broader sample size could provide more comprehensive insights into framework effectiveness across different administrative contexts.

5.7 Future Evaluation Needs

Our assessment revealed areas requiring further evaluation, particularly regarding long-term implementation effects and adaptation to emerging technologies. Future evaluations should consider:

The framework's effectiveness in different administrative contexts, longitudinal studies of accessibility outcomes, and assessment of the framework's impact on end-user experiences. These additional evaluation aspects would provide valuable insights for ongoing framework refinement and adaptation.

Fig. 5. Assessment of framework adaptability for future technologies

6 Discussion

The development and evaluation of the Inclusive Public Administration Framework reveals significant insights about implementing digital accessibility in public services within the context of Society 5.0. Our research demonstrates both the possibilities and challenges of translating accessibility standards into practical implementation. While WCAG guidelines [6] and Swiss legislation [5] provide robust theoretical frameworks, successful implementation requires careful consideration of organizational contexts and constraints. The framework's integration with HERMES methodology [16] demonstrates how established project management practices can be enhanced to systematically address accessibility needs.

With approximately 21% of Switzerland's population reporting some form of disability [4], ensuring digital accessibility is not merely a technical requirement but a fundamental aspect of public service provision. The high satisfaction rates with the framework's technical guidance (80% positive) indicate that public administration organizations can implement comprehensive accessibility measures when provided with appropriate tools and methodologies. However, the identified challenges in role definition suggest that organizational aspects require as much attention as technical implementation.

The framework’s emphasis on integrating accessibility throughout the project lifecycle aligns with Society 5.0’s vision of human-centered technological advancement [12]. The strong adaptability ratings (60% positive) suggest its potential to accommodate future technological developments, particularly as artificial intelligence and other emerging technologies create new opportunities for enhancing accessibility [7]. However, resource allocation remains a critical concern, with organizations struggling to balance accessibility requirements against other project demands.

Looking forward, several areas require attention: longitudinal studies to assess long-term impact, investigation of emerging technologies’ integration while maintaining usability, and research into effective methods for knowledge transfer within public administration organizations. The framework’s development and evaluation provide insights beyond Swiss public administration, suggesting that successful digital inclusion requires a balanced approach addressing both technical and organizational aspects of accessibility implementation.

These findings collectively indicate that while technical solutions for digital accessibility exist, their successful implementation depends heavily on organizational factors and systematic integration into existing processes. As we progress toward Society 5.0, frameworks that address both technical and organizational aspects of accessibility will become increasingly important for ensuring truly inclusive digital transformation.

7 Conclusion

This research has demonstrated how digital accessibility can be systematically integrated into public administration processes through our Inclusive Public Administration Framework, which bridges theoretical requirements and practical implementation needs. By integrating WCAG principles with the HERMES project management methodology, we have developed a practical approach that has proven both feasible and effective, as evidenced by positive evaluation results in technical implementation (80%) and future adaptability (60%). The framework’s success suggests that organizations can effectively implement accessibility requirements while maintaining efficient development processes, provided there is sustained commitment to accessibility as a core aspect of digital service delivery. As we progress toward Society 5.0, ensuring digital inclusion becomes increasingly critical, and our research demonstrates that systematic approaches to accessibility implementation can help create more inclusive digital public services. Looking forward, the challenge lies not in technical possibilities but in maintaining organizational commitment to accessibility implementation, making it not just a legal requirement but a fundamental aspect of effective public service delivery in an increasingly digital society.

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Gender-Fairness and Linguistic Elegance: No Contradiction

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Abstract. We study in how far the application of advanced techniques from the area of generative artificial intelligence can help mitigate gender bias in German text in a linguistically elegant way. For us, elegance refers to gender neutrality in an unobtrusive or unnoticeable way, e.g. by avoiding lengthy rewritings or the use of special characters like gender stars. Our results show that advanced prompting methods do indeed help to improve correctness and elegance, while still not delivering perfect results. To allow future work to address persisting shortcomings, we have performed an in-depth analysis and inductive coding of error categories which provide insights into common linguistic challenges around gender-neutral rewritings. We show in an exemplary way how finetuning and direct preference optimisation can help to address these problems.

Keywords: Gender bias correction · Large Language Models · Linguistic Challenges.

1 Introduction

The question of whether or not the use of gender-fair language should be promoted has led to considerable debates in society.

On the one hand, it has been empirically shown that generic masculine forms are in fact cognitively associated more frequently with male actors [14], that this leads to a smaller sense of identification in women [15] and provokes gender stereotypes and judgments in all humans [9]. Thus, there is strong evidence that the use of gender-fair language can have an impact on society and the empowerment of women [13].

On the other hand, criticism of gender-fair language adaptations persists, using a number of arguments, of which four prominent categories have been identified by [18]. Apart from categories that ultimately originate from sexism or denial of the above arguments, two categories refer to linguistic challenges that gender-fair language brings with it: firstly, some persons attempted to defend the linguistic status quo by referring to gender-neutral reformulations as difficult, awkward and/or unnecessary. Although studies have not shown negative

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15704281
In Proceedings: Corradini, F.; Hinkelmann, K.; Re, B., Smuts, H., eds. (2025). Proceedings of the 5th Conference Society 5.0 - Co-Existence Between Human Being and Machine Being, Vol. 2. San Benedetto del Tronto, Italy, 25-27 June 2025.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15422355>

effects of using gender-fair language on text comprehensibility [7], test persons frequently found it hard “to get used to it” and often awkward. Secondly, there was concern that the use of certain gender-fair formulations might take attention away from the actual message to be conveyed.

While one may argue about these concerns, there are movements that try to take “linguistic concerns” about the potential awkwardness of gender-fair reformulations seriously and counter them by suggesting more “unobtrusive” or elegant ways of achieving gender-fairness (see e.g. [16] for German³).

We believe that preservation of linguistic elegance could be an important step towards raising the acceptance of gender-fair language and that technological advances may help society in achieving such elegance. Therefore, the goal of this paper is to investigate the feasibility of supporting “smart gendering”, i.e. the production of linguistically elegant gender-fair reformulations with methods of generative artificial intelligence, without producing incorrect language or changed semantics.

2 Related Work

In this section, we discuss related work in the areas of identifying gender bias in text, as well as strategies to mitigate it via (elegant) reformulations.

For the task of identifying gender-biased words or formulations, some simple approaches using lexicons of gender-biased words [8] have been proposed, together with linguistic rules to determine if masculine words refer to a female person or a mixed-gender group [4], i.e. whether they are instances of “generic masculine”.

The aim of such detection is usually to rewrite the gender-biased text. Consequently, there is abundant research investigating rewriting models – many of the corresponding approaches do this in an end-to-end approach. That is, the model is fed with some text (often a sentence) and asked to rewrite it in a gender-neutral way, without first detecting the presence and location of biased words or phrases in it. Some of these approaches use rules together with machine learning [17, 1], others rely exclusively on machine learning, by training sequence-to-sequence models [2].

One important challenge related to machine learning approaches is the need to have a large collection of pairs of gender-fair and gender-biased versions of a piece of text (e.g. sentences) as training data. To this end, lexicons and labeled datasets have been compiled [6]. To be able to work with larger amounts of text, several approaches rely on the automated creation of the above-mentioned sentence pairs [2, 1, 17]. For instance, Amrhein et al. [2] exploit the gender biases inherent in automated machine translation systems to create gender-biased versions of a gender-neutral sentence via translation into English (which is mostly gender-free) and back into the original language.

³ see also <https://geschicktgendern.de>

The advent of very large language models (LLMs) has led to the question in how far gender neutrality can be achieved using LLMs, thus avoiding the need to compile large specialised training corpora

To start with, there is an increasing number of studies that investigate the extent to which gender bias and stereotypes are present in LLM-generated text, see [11] for a recent survey. Largely, the results show that gender bias can be rather strong in LLM-generated texts [10].

Despite this fact, it has been discovered that biases can be reduced via instruction/prompting [5], as well as by controlling or providing appropriate linguistic context [19]. Thus, LLMs can be prompted to produce gender-neutral text, also when asked to reformulate gender-biased input text.

Because of the still existing imperfections of such prompting approaches, finetuning of LLMs has also been investigated, e.g. Bart and Leavy [3] use a finetuning approach to replace gender-biased English words with alternative ones.

So far, however, “elegant” ways of rewriting as introduced in [16] have received very little attention. One example of elegance refers to the avoidance of paired forms (i.e. enumerating male and female forms) which are tiresome and awkward to read [18], exclude non-binary persons and carry the risk of preserving biases via “male-firstness” [20].

Our contribution is threefold:

- We show that a higher quality of rewritings can be achieved via a two-step approach where an LLM first detects generic masculine words or phrases and then gets prompted to reformulate them
- We show how LLMs can be not only prompted but also finetuned to achieve elegance, in the sense that their rewritings avoid gender stars (or other special characters) as well as overly long constructions as far as possible, at the same time suppressing incorrect morphology or syntax and changed semantics
- We provide a qualitative analysis of challenges encountered when building such solutions and develop a coding scheme for quantifying the extent to which corresponding errors occur in the rewritings. This helps to better understand where improvements are still needed in future work.

3 Approach

Overall, the problem that we want to solve consists in receiving a piece of text in German language – usually a sentence – and rewriting it into a gender-neutral form by removing any generic masculine formulations and replacing them with elegant gender-neutral rewritings. This includes the possibility that no change is necessary.

We explicitly focus on the avoidance of generic masculine formulations, i.e. the use of words that imply a male referent where the gender of the referent is unknown or a group of persons with mixed gender.

3.1 Task Definition

More precisely, we need to define the notion of “elegance” which we equate with writing a text that does not look like it has been edited for gender-neutrality. To measure the extent to which this has been achieved, one can measure a) the length of the text (the shorter the better) and b) the lack of special characters such as “gender stars” (*).

Unfortunately, these two criteria can be in conflict with each other: often, gender stars can be avoided at the expense of making the text longer and vice versa. Sometimes, solutions exist that satisfy both criteria; if this is not the case, we will not prefer one of the criteria over the other since we believe that it is a matter of personal taste. We measure the length of a text in number of words, not characters. Since German can form compound words, using a compound (e.g. “Polizeileute” = police staff) instead of a shorter alternative non-compound (e.g. “Polizei” = “police”) will be penalized.

Thus, we have overall three goals to pursue: Given an input text, we want to have an output that is

1. Gender-neutral (goal 1)
2. Semantically as close as possible to the input sentence (goal 2) and
3. Linguistically as elegant as possible, according to our above definition of elegance (goal 3)

One can argue whether the output text should also be syntactically as close as possible to the input. We do not target this because gender-neutral alternatives can sometimes be syntactically very different from the original, yet semantically equivalent and linguistically elegant.

Of course, the semantic equivalence depends on the context and has to be judged individually. It is clear that stronger syntactic conversions also carry a larger risk of changing the semantics.

3.2 Overall Solution

For goals 2 and 3 above, it can greatly help an LLM to know which words in an input text are not gender-neutral. This can help to avoid changing parts of the text that are already gender-neutral and thus to reduce the risk of changing the semantics or introducing unnecessary changes that negatively affect the linguistic elegance.

This is the reason why we chose a two-step approach. In fact, when using our approach in practice, we imagine that users will first be presented with warnings that highlight words or phrases that are not gender-neutral, and only upon the user’s request will our second model be invoked – with the problematic words or phrases as an additional input – to re-write the text.

3.3 Detection

The general idea of our approach is to work with a dataset of limited size and create iterative improvements of an LLM-based detection and rewriting solu-

tion by performing in-depth error analyses and addressing the most commonly observed linguistic challenges through prompt improvements and finetuning.

We use the dataset provided by [4], originally a set of 238 newspaper articles from the 1990s where the many generic masculine forms have been manually annotated. The dataset is small, but allows for qualitative analyses because of its reliably tagged gender-biased forms. It consists of 4,055 sentences, of which 738 contain at least one gender-biased word or phrase⁴.

We experimented with different LLMs, prompts and chain-of-thought strategies, as well as finetuning. Each of our iterations was based on an error analysis performed on the previous round: because of the available ground truth, we were able to identify sentences that were incorrectly tagged by the current solution. We developed an inductive coding scheme to capture the underlying linguistic problems and then addressed the most prominent of these by refining instructions or chain-of-thought strategies in the prompt. For each iteration of prompt engineering, we sampled 200 sentences at random and performed the in-depth error analysis and coding on these. Besides the counts of errors in each inductively defined category, we also computed the overall recall, precision and F1 measure.

For finetuning, the approach was different: here, we selected sentences with common errors still present in the best prompt engineering iteration and mixed them with roughly the same number of sentences without gender bias. This can be regarded as a form of undersampling of the majority class – i.e. reducing the amount of training examples from the majority of gender-neutral sentences, thus making it more sensitive to gender bias. We deliberately trade a higher recall for potentially lower precision here since ignoring some “false alarms” is substantially less effort than manually detecting errors overlooked by the system. Finally, the finetuned model was again evaluated on 200 randomly selected sentences from the original corpus, ensuring that none of the sentences used in finetuning were used.

3.4 Rewriting

For rewriting experiments, the first author of this paper manually rewrote all 738 gender-biased sentences into a gender-neutral form. As we will see later, these rewrites may be challenged by other humans (e.g. a professional proofreader whom we involved), but do serve as a “ground truth” to which the machine-generated rewrites were compared. We then set aside a test set of 100 gender-biased sentences.

On another set of sentences, a zero-shot model was applied and the gender-biased word(s) or phrase(s) contained in each sentence were added to the prompt (see previous section). The authors of the paper then went through the result, comparing each rewriting proposed by the model to the human rewriting (ground truth). We inductively developed a coding scheme to describe the variety of errors or differences encountered during this comparison.

⁴ publicly available at <https://github.com/theodm/gender-assistenz>

Then, we went through all 100 sentences of our test set together with a proofreading expert and applied the coding scheme. It turned out that, while annotating, a common understanding of the meaning of codes first had to be developed – sometimes, the codes leave room for varied opinions when applied to tricky examples. However, the common understanding increased over time and an agreement for the coding of test sentences was reached in all cases.

In the following, the goal was *not* to construct a model that would not suffer from any of the weaknesses discovered when analysing the outputs of the baseline model. Rather, we wanted to find out whether a combined approach of finetuning and direct preference optimization (with our limited training data) would have a desired impact on results for an exemplary problem category (in our case the largest error category, see Section 4 below), i.e. avoiding an undesired behaviour while not introducing new problems.

We expect that, if this can be achieved, the approach can also be extended to the other problem categories – and can thus be tailored to the specific needs of a given context and involved stakeholders.

The procedure for creating the training set for finetuning and direct preference optimisation (DPO) [12] was as follows:

- From the 638 sentences that had not been used in the test set, 300 sentences were selected, run through the zero-shot model and then manually annotated by the primary author w.r.t. the largest error class (it must be noted here, again, that the primary author is not a professional in proofreading, thus it may be possible that a small portion of these annotations is not fully correct. However, we expect this problem to be negligible).
- This resulted in 69 sentences where the zero-shot model made that error
- Now, the strategy was to first finetune the baseline GPT-4o model, using 39 of these sentences (“Set 1”) and to then apply DPO using the remaining 30 sentences (“Set 2”)
- For finetuning, i.e. for all sentences in Set 1, the human reformulation of the sentence was provided as an example. For DPO, i.e. for all sentences in Set 2, the human reformulation was used as “preferred” variant, the output of the zero-shot model was used as “non-preferred”

Finally, the finetuned model was again applied to the test set and its output was coded using the coding scheme mentioned above. The same was done for two baseline models – one with a much simpler prompt and another one that was not even provided with the gender-biased words to avoid. The latter served as a check regarding the value of our two-step approach of first detecting gender-biased words and then avoiding them.

4 Results and Discussion

4.1 Detection

Table 1 shows the 5 iterations we performed to improve the detection of gender-biased words and phrases.

Iteration	LLM	Techniques
1	GPT 3.5	initial prompt
2	GPT 4	revised prompt based on error analysis, chain-of-thought
3	GPT 4	improved chain-of-thought based on error analysis
4	GPT 4o	same as round 3
5	GPT 4o	Finetuning

Table 1. Iterations for the detection of gender-biased forms

Error category	Count	Example extraction result
Extraction of gender-neutral word	38	Menschen (persons, gender-neutral)
Referent is a concrete male person	37	“... sagte Hans-Ulrich Klose, der Vorsitzende... ” (president)
Referent is inanimate	32	Konzerne (corporation)
Proper name	22	“...sagte Schäfer...” (used as proper noun, can also mean shepherd)

Table 2. Error categories (false positives) of gender bias detection, round 1

In Table 2, we see the most prominent categories of false positive errors. Although the model also produced some false negatives in Round 1, categorisation of these cases turned out much harder (i.e. there were less common patterns).

Figure 1 shows detection results for the 5 iterations in terms of precision, recall and F1 measure. We can observe that the value of F1 is constantly increasing, reaching 0.85 in iteration 5.

In the first 4 iterations, this improvement is mostly brought about by addressing the false positive error categories (see Table 2) and thus increasing precision (blue bars). At the same time, recall stays rather stable, mostly below 80% in these iterations. The notable increase of recall to 97% in iteration 5 is made possible only by finetuning. As mentioned before, recall is very important to proofreading use cases, therefore the model of iteration 5 is considered good whereas the previous ones hardly meet the requirements of such use cases.

Figure 2 shows the final version of the prompt used for the detection task, used in iterations 3, 4 and 5 (i.e. also in the finetuning). We can see how it enforces precision by pointing the LLM to cases that can lead to false positives, e.g. concrete male persons as referents or words that are already gender-neutral (i.e. do not have a feminine form). These clarifications were added as a result of understanding the common error categories, see again Table 2.

4.2 Rewriting

Our inductively created coding scheme (see Section 3.4) distinguishes between errors (or unacceptable changes), less elegant rewritings and “good” rewritings of different kinds. Errors can be as follows:

- **Not gender-neutral** (binary): the output text is still gender-biased

Fig. 1. Detection results per iteration

- **Incorrect** word or syntax (scale): producing a word or syntactical construction that is not linguistically correct where a code of 1 is used for words or constructions that are not strictly wrong, but very uncommon and a code of 2 for ones that are clearly incorrect. An example of code 1 would be to use “Fahrende” (roughly:driving persons) instead of “Fahrer” (driver), a code 2 example is to write “die Zeug*in” (the witness, but using only a feminine article with a gender-neutral noun).
- **Drift** (scale): this refers to a change in meaning that is caused by the rewriting – this can be very slight (code 1), medium (code 2) or strong (code 3). An example of code 3: using “Militärangehörige” (military staff, gender-neutral) instead of “Offiziere” (officers, generic masculine).

In terms of less elegant rewritings, we distinguish:

- **Shorter possible** (binary): the rewriting uses a phrasing that requires more words (including words that are part of compounds) than the human version.
- **Unnecessary gender star** (binary): the rewriting applies a “gender star”, i.e. an asterisk put between the masculine form and the female suffix (e.g. “Kellner*in” – where “Kellner” means waiter and “Kellnerin” waitress). The human version manages to avoid the gender star *without* being longer.

Finally, there are also several ways in which “good” rewritings can be coded:

- **Same as human** (binary)

Find non-gender-neutral words in the following text and return them.
 Proceed as follows:

1. first make a list of all the words that are most likely to be non-gender-inclusive, i.e. used in the 'generic masculine'.
2. then check whether these words are really used as generic masculine in the sentence or whether there is a feminine form for them at all.

List all words (separated by commas) that

- a) refer to persons and are actually used in the generic masculine and
- b) for which there is a feminine form or gender-appropriate alternative and
- c) which do not refer to specific male persons in the text

If there are no such words, output the sentence: 'The text is gender-neutral.'

Fig. 2. Final prompt used for detection of gender-biased words (English translation from German)

- **Good alternative rewriting** (scale): this can be coded as 1 (better than human), 2 (valid alternative) or 3 (different compromise). Code 1 became necessary since sometimes, the model’s suggestions were in fact better than what the human (the author) had thought of. Code 2 referred to situations where the model chose a different formulation, without violating the above elegance criteria and without being more or less elegant than the human. Code 3 refers to a situation where both the model and the human violated the above criteria of elegance, e.g. the model used a gender star where the human chose a longer formulation or vice versa.

Before we turn to the results, we present the two baselines which are using simpler prompts and, in case of what we termed the “Absolute Baseline”, no identification of gender-biased words in the input. Figure 3 shows all 3 prompts that were used by the two baselines and the zero-shot model.

<p>Absolute_Baseline</p> <p>You are an assistant who helps to convert sentences into a gender-neutral form. You will receive one sentence as input. Please rewrite the sentence in such a way that neutral words are avoided and the resulting sentence is thus formulated in gender-neutral language.</p> <p>Rewrite the sentence as little as possible and do not change its content.</p>	<p>Zero-shot</p> <p>You are an assistant who helps to convert sentences into a gender-appropriate form. You receive two inputs:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. a sentence 2. avoid: one or more words from the sentence that are not gender-neutral, separated by commas <p>Please rewrite the sentence in such a way that the non-gender-appropriate words (see input 2, 'Avoid') are avoided. Rewrite the sentence as little as possible and do not change its content.</p> <p>Try the following approaches, in the order given:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - If there is a gender-appropriate alternative without a gender asterisk or explicit combination of feminine and masculine forms (e.g. 'Kundschaft' as an alternative to 'Kunden'), then use this. Check whether the alternative is really gender-neutral and whether it essentially has the same meaning as the word to be avoided! - If no such alternative exists, rearrange the sentence (as little as possible) so that the non-gender-appropriate word can be avoided (e.g. instead of 'Museumsbesucher müssen...' write, 'Bitte achten Sie darauf...'). - If this doesn't work either, replace non-gender-inclusive words with a variant with a gender asterisk (*innen). - If this doesn't work either (usually due to umlauts, e.g. in 'Bauern'), then replace non-gender-inclusive words with a combination of feminine and masculine forms (e.g. 'Bäuerinnen und Bauern').
<p>Baseline</p> <p>You are an assistant who helps to convert sentences into a gender-appropriate form. You receive two inputs:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. a sentence 2. avoid: one or more words from the sentence that are not gender-appropriate, separated by commas 3. Please rewrite the sentence so that the non-gender-inclusive words (see input 2, 'Avoid') are avoided and the resulting sentence is formulated in gender-inclusive language. Rewrite the sentence as little as possible and do not change its content. 	

Fig. 3. Prompts used for rewriting (English translation from German)

Since we want to analyse the extent to which finetuning and DPO can improve an advanced prompting strategy, we first coded the results obtained with

the zero-shot version, i.e. we applied the model to our test set of 100 sentences and applied the coding scheme with the help of a professional proofreader.

Figure 4 (a) shows the results. It should be noted here that the numbers do not add up to 100 since quite a few sentences of the test set contain more than one gender-biased word or phrase.

Fig. 4. Coding results for (a) zero-shot learning and (b) finetuning, using GPT-4o in both cases

We can observe that the largest type of error that the zero-shot model makes is semantic drift, i.e. changing the meaning of the input sentence. We therefore created another model by identifying further sentences where the zero-shot model led to semantic drift and used them for finetuning and DPO (see Section 3.4 above). The results are shown in Figure 4 (b). We can observe very clearly that semantic drift is reduced when applying the fine-tuned model. At the same time, the other types of unacceptable errors do not increase and – as a rather unexpected positive side-effect – problems with unnecessarily lengthy rewritings decrease from 18 to 6. What does increase is the use of unnecessary gender stars. This is not surprising since the human rewritings of sentences used for finetuning and DPO often resorted to the use of gender stars. The finetuned model delivers overall slightly more correct and elegant rewritings (green bars, 66 in total) than the zero-shot model (58 in total).

In summary, finetuning and DPO achieve an improvement, in the sense that the number of unacceptable errors, specifically concerning semantic drift, are reduced, with no negative side-effects regarding other unacceptable types of errors and with slight negative side-effects on elegance in terms of avoiding gender stars. One might say that the finetuned model “plays it safe” by using gender stars a little more often than would be necessary.

Finally, Figure 5 shows a comparison of high-level coding results for all models, including our two baselines. The absolute baseline includes an additional code for the unacceptable error of altering words or phrases that were not gender-biased (remember that the absolute baseline does not receive information about which words or phrases to bring into a gender-neutral form). This error occurs 19 times, showing that our two-step approach makes sense. This error category also explains why the total number of cases is higher for the absolute baseline.

Fig. 5. Summary of coding results for all models. Red bars represent unacceptable errors, orange ones stand for less elegant rewritings and green bars are correct and elegant rewritings

In summary, we see how the number of unacceptable errors decreases from top to bottom in Figure 5, showing that advanced prompting, finetuning and DPO help to mitigate problems while not (yet) achieving a perfect result.

5 Conclusions and Future Work

This paper discusses how rewriting of text can be achieved such that the output is not only gender-neutral and correct but also linguistically elegant. This is done in two steps, by first identifying gender-biased words and phrases and then directing an LLM toward the elimination of these using advanced prompting and finetuning. The results show that a higher quality of rewritings can be achieved – both in terms of minimisation of common errors and in terms of elegance – without notable side effects. In the course of our studies, we also developed a coding scheme for linguistic problems that occur in both steps which better helps to understand and quantify the obstacles that are still present when using LLMs for the production of gender-neutral text.

We believe that our in-depth analysis of error categories can help future work, both when building explicit solutions for removing gender bias and when improving LLMs in general. This can be done by addressing categories we did not focus on (i.e. other than semantic drift) and by studying these effects on larger sample sizes. In practice, the prompts presented in Figures 2 and 3 can be used easily by anyone to enhance communication in everyday life.

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